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“Certainly no subject or field is making more progress on so many fronts at the present moment, than biology, and if we were to name the most powerful assumption of all, which leads one on and on in an attempt to understand life, it is that all things are made of atoms, and that everything that living things do can be understood in terms of the jiggings and wiggings of atoms.”

Richard Feynman

Abstract

Recent years have greatly expanded evidence on quantum and vibrational effects impacting functionality of biological systems fueling new hypotheses. This creates need and opportunity for rigorous experimental paradigms testing these hypotheses. This thesis establishes methodologies allowing manipulation of well established model systems with atomic precision as well as quantitative experimental readouts which can be tied to physiological effects allowing to investigate such hypotheses. Unifying molecular and behavioral experimental workflows and precisely placed molecular spectroscopic probes allow to sample the proteins on a time-scale relevant to quantum and vibrational effects and provide functional readouts at the same time.

This thesis explores the potential functional impact of selected, molecular interactions to explore the potential presence of vibrational or quantum effects on relevant timescales and investigate its potential impact on *in vitro* and *in vivo* higher order function.

(1) Exploring the potential impact of classic protein sub-domain vibrations and quantum resonances on the selectivity of the potassium channel KcsA. For this, targeted isotope labeling strategies were developed and resulting samples characterized using 1D and ultrafast 2DIR spectroscopy as well as electrophysiology. In addition, spectroscopic modeling and mutations investigated the impact of ion induced conformational changes on large-scale vibrational modes of the protein.

(2) The impact of isotope effects on allosteric transitions in proteins for oxygen sensing of *C. elegans* was investigated using isotope effects. Calcium signaling of the neuronal response to changes in isotope composition of oxygen were investigated using a newly designed experimental setup.

(3) Lastly, the ability to discriminate odorants in Zebrafish was investigated to test a disputed vibrational theory of olfaction. Isotope labeled amino acids were used as vibrational probes to perturb the olfactory perception based on *in vivo* whole brain calcium imaging. Isotopomers of Phenylalanine and Lysine showed disparate brain states in olfactory related brain regions which might support vibrationally assisted electron tunneling in olfactory receptors.

Taken together this thesis integrates methods across structural biology, molecular dynamics simulations, ultrafast spectroscopy, electrophysiology and neurobiology. The novel experimental paradigms and evidence of this thesis established a general way to quantitatively characterize the limits of quantum and vibrational effects on the structure of biomolecules and *in vivo* functional behavior of organisms. The results provided in this thesis on well established biological model systems unlocks the testing of a plethora of similar hypotheses aiming to discover links between the atomic world and biologically relevant macroscopic phenomena.

Zusammenfassung

In den letzten Jahren haben sich die Erkenntnisse über Quanten- und Schwingungseffekte, die sich auf die Funktionalität biologischer Systeme auswirken, stark erweitert und neue Hypothesen aufgestellt. Dies schafft Bedarf und Gelegenheit für rigorose experimentelle Paradigmen zur Prüfung dieser Hypothesen. In dieser Arbeit werden Methoden entwickelt, die eine Manipulation etablierter Modellsysteme mit atomarer Präzision sowie quantitative experimentelle Messwerte ermöglichen, die mit physiologischen Effekten verknüpft werden können, um solche Hypothesen zu untersuchen. Die Vereinheitlichung von molekularen und verhaltensbasierten experimentellen Abläufen und präzise platzierte molekulare spektroskopische Sonden ermöglichen es die Proteine auf einer für quanten- und vibrationeller Effekte relevanten Zeitskala zu untersuchen und gleichzeitig funktionelle Messwerte zu liefern.

In dieser Arbeit werden die potenziellen funktionellen Auswirkungen ausgewählter molekularer Wechselwirkungen untersucht, um das potenzielle Vorhandensein von Schwingungs- oder Quanteneffekten auf relevanten Zeitskalen zu erforschen und ihre potenziellen Auswirkungen auf Funktionen höherer Ordnung *in vitro* und *in vivo* zu untersuchen.

(1) Erforschung der potenziellen Auswirkungen von klassischen Protein-Subdomänen-Schwingungen und Quantenresonanzen auf die Selektivität des Kaliumkanals KcsA. Zu diesem Zweck wurden gezielte Isotopenmarkierungsstrategien entwickelt und die resultierenden Proben mittels 1D- und ultraschneller 2DIR-Spektroskopie sowie Elektrophysiologie charakterisiert. Darüber hinaus wurde durch spektroskopische Modellierung der Einfluss von Ionen und mutations-induzierten Konformationsänderungen auf großräumige Schwingungsmoden des Proteins untersucht.

(2) Die Auswirkung von Isotopeneffekten auf allosterische Übergänge in Proteinen für die Sauerstoffsensitivität von *C. elegans* wurde anhand von Isotopeneffekten untersucht. Die Kalzium-Signale der neuronalen Reaktion auf Veränderungen in der Isotopenzusammensetzung von Sauerstoff wurde mit Hilfe eines neu entwickelten Versuchsaufbaus untersucht.

(3) Schließlich wurde die Fähigkeit zur Unterscheidung von Geruchsstoffen bei Zebrafischen untersucht, um eine umstrittene Vibrationstheorie des Geruchsinns zu testen. Isotopenmarkierte Aminosäuren wurden als Schwingungs sonden verwendet, um die Geruchswahrnehmung auf der Grundlage von Ganzhirn-Kalzium-Bildgebung zu perturbieren. Isotopomere von Phenylalanin und Lysin zeigten unterschiedliche Hirnzustände in olfaktorisch verwandten Hirnregionen, was die Theorie von vibrationsunterstütztem Elektronentunneln in olfaktorischen Rezeptoren unterstützen könnte.

Insgesamt werden in dieser Arbeit Methoden aus den Bereichen Strukturbiologie, Molekulardynamiksimulationen, ultraschnelle Spektroskopie, Elektrophysiologie und Neurobiologie integriert. Die neuen experimentellen Paradigmen und Beweise dieser Arbeit haben einen allgemeinen Weg zur quantitativen Charakterisierung der Grenzen von Quanten- und Schwingungseffekten auf die Struktur von Biomolekülen und das funktionelle Verhalten von Organismen *in vivo* aufgezeigt. Die Ergebnisse dieser Arbeit an gut etablierten biologischen Modellsystemen ermöglichen die Prüfung einer Vielzahl ähnlicher Hypothesen, die darauf abzielen, Verbindungen zwischen der atomaren Welt und biologisch relevanten makroskopischen Phänomenen zu entdecken.

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Contents

Abstract	iii
Zusammenfassung	iv
Acknowledgements	v
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Testing the limits of quantum behavior in biological systems	1
1.2 Quantum mechanics and their limitations in biological systems	2
1.2.1 Quantization of energy and definition of non-triviality	2
1.2.2 Quantum delocalization and superposition	3
1.2.3 Quantum coherence, decoherence and coupling	4
1.3 Review of biological systems currently investigated in quantum biology	6
1.3.1 Coherent excitation transfer in photosynthetic light-harvesting complex	6
1.3.2 Magnetoreception	10
1.3.3 Role of vibrational and quantum effects for enzymatic catalysis	10
1.3.4 Direct observation of quantum effects in single molecule inter- ferometry	11
1.4 Experimental approaches of this thesis	12
2 Vibrationally and quantum coherence assisted ion transport	19
2.1 Introduction	19
2.1.1 The classical view of ion transport in KcsA	19
2.1.2 Hypothesis of quantum coherence in ion transport	21
2.1.3 Potential quantum resonances probed by electrophysiology	22
2.1.4 Potential signatures of quantum and vibrational effects probed by IR-spectroscopy of KcsA	24
2.1.5 Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport	31
2.1.6 Potential signatures of vibrationally assisted ion transport	35
2.2 Materials and Methods	38
2.2.1 Isotope labeling of Amino acids	38
2.2.2 Heterologous expression and purification of KcsA	40
2.2.3 FTIR of KcsA	42
2.2.4 tRNA transcription and aminoacylation	43
2.2.5 Cell free expression of KcsA	46
2.2.6 Structure-based spectral modeling	47
2.2.7 Electrophysiology of KcsA	49
2.3 Results	50
2.3.1 Isotope labeling of amino acids	50
2.3.2 Expression and characterization of KcsA	52
2.3.3 IR spectroscopy of KcsA	56
2.3.4 Electrophysiology of KcsA	68

2.4	Discussion	71
2.4.1	Discussion of hypothesis of quantum assisted ion transport in potassium channels	71
2.4.2	Discussion of vibrationally assisted ion transport	74
3	Neuronal readout of isotope effects on <i>C. elegans</i> oxygen sensing	89
3.1	Introduction	89
3.1.1	Sensitivity of allosteric transitions to isotopomers	89
3.1.2	Hypothesis of sensitivity of allosteric transitions to isotopomers	90
3.1.3	Experimental approach of <i>C. elegans</i> as a model organism for studying the influence of isotopomers in chemotaxis	90
3.2	Material & Methods	94
3.2.1	Gaussian network model analysis of dynamics in H-NOX proteins	94
3.2.2	Crossing of imaging wormline	95
3.2.3	Oxygen delivery setup	95
3.2.4	Imaging setup	95
3.3	Results	96
3.3.1	Structural dynamics of H-NOX proteins by normal mode analysis	96
3.3.2	Experimental measurement of neuronal responses to isotope substitution	96
3.3.3	Direct determination of isotope effect of oxygen isotopomers . .	96
3.3.4	Differential determination of isotope effect of oxygen isotopomers	98
3.4	Discussion of neuronal readout of isotope effects on <i>C. elegans</i> oxygen sensing	100
3.4.1	Systematic errors of experimental setups	100
3.4.2	Vibrational effects compared to classical isotope effects	101
4	Brain dynamics as a readout for quantum tunneling in olfaction	105
4.1	Introduction	105
4.1.1	Missing origin of olfactory processing in vertebrates	105
4.1.2	Theory of vibrational molecular mechanism of olfactory receptors	106
4.1.3	Previous experimental approaches utilizing isotope effects . . .	107
4.1.4	Experimental approach for inducing isotopes effects in the olfactory system <i>in vivo</i>	108
4.2	Material & Methods	110
4.2.1	Odorant characterization	110
4.2.2	Animals and odor delivery	110
4.2.3	Imaging, image processing and signal extraction	111
4.2.4	Preprocessing of neuronal activity traces	114
4.2.5	Data preparation, correlation and dimensionality reduction . .	114
4.3	Results	115
4.3.1	Spectroscopic characterization of odors	115
4.3.2	Animals and odor delivery	118
4.3.3	Image processing	118
4.3.4	Analysis of neuronal traces	119
4.3.5	Dimensionality reduction	129
4.4	Discussion of isotope induced changes in brain dynamics in olfaction .	131
5	Appendix A	139
6	Appendix B	143

List of Figures

1.1	Size scales of biological complexity and governing physical principles	2
1.2	Youngs' double-slit experiment without observer	3
1.3	The scale of the membrane protein KcsAs selectivity filter	4
1.4	Youngs' double-slit experiment with observer and noisy protein environments	5
1.5	Crystal structure of the bacterial FMO-complex	7
1.6	Schematic comparison of traditional vs quantum assisted excitation energy transfer in photosynthesis	8
1.7	Introduction to 2DIR spectroscopy	9
1.8	Light-dependent magnetic compass sensing hypothesis in birds	11
1.9	Youngs' double-slit experiment using biological molecules	12
2.1	Schematic structure of KcsA	20
2.2	Signature of quantum resonances and experimental patch clamp setup	23
2.3	Explanation of isotope labeling in 2DIR spectroscopy	26
2.4	Spectral modeling approach for 2DIR of KcsA	27
2.5	Spectroscopy of model compounds	29
2.6	Modeling of spectral differences between ion states in isotopomers of KcsA	29
2.7	Schematics of combined site directed and uniform isotope labeling of KcsA	30
2.8	Aminoacylation of tRNA	31
2.9	Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport of KcsA	32
2.10	Vibrationally assisted ion transport hypothesis for ion binding to S4	33
2.11	Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted transport of KcsA	34
2.12	Characteristics of Mutant KcsA channels	36
2.13	Structural properties of selected mutant channels.	37
2.14	Isotope labeling of amino acids by acid hydrolysis	39
2.15	Schematics of IR-spectral modeling from structural ensembles	48
2.16	Mass spectrum of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ amino acids L-Tyrosine and L-Valine	51
2.17	FTIR of isotopomers of Valine and Tyrosine	52
2.18	Biochemical characterization of KcsA in low K^+ conditions	53
2.19	Mass spectrum of wt and uniformly isotope labeled KcsA	55
2.20	Site-specific isotope labeling by amber suppression in CFE	57
2.21	Absolute and difference FTIR spectrum of KcsA in KCl and NaCl	58
2.22	FTIR of mutants compared to WT KcsA	59
2.23	Simulation and experimental results of difference spectra for different subregions of KcsA	60
2.24	Contribution of ion binding states to the simulated difference spectrum of the extended filter region	61
2.25	Doorway modes of the extended filter region	62
2.26	Theoretical and experimental 2DIR spectra of KcsA with isotope labels in different ion environments	65

2.27	Experimental 2DIR difference spectrum between K^+ and Na^+ with and without isotope label	66
2.28	Optical control of unblocking of KcsA	67
2.29	Reflectance of RF-frequencies in Nanion setup	69
2.30	Electrophysiology of isotope labeled single channel KcsA	70
2.31	Overview of spectral signatures and potential functional significance of mode analysis	76
2.32	Hypothesis of spectral signatures of mutants	79
3.1	Overview of oxygen sensing neurons in <i>C. elegans</i>	91
3.2	Structure and oxygen binding in H-NOX proteins.	94
3.3	cele	97
3.4	Transient switching between oxygen species	99
4.1	Principle of vibrationally assisted olfaction	106
4.2	Key steps in olfaction and relevant studies.	107
4.3	Olfaction in Zebrafish	109
4.4	Olfactory pattern discrimination in neuronal space	109
4.5	Image processing work-flow	112
4.6	Computed vibrational spectra (IR intensities) of normal and deuterated amino acid odors	117
4.7	Masking of periodic grid artifacts in FFT-space	119
4.8	Result of the FFT-filtering	120
4.9	Result of registration	121
4.10	Segmentation of neurons and brain regions and extracted signals	123
4.11	Overall comparison of Datasets	125
4.12	Correlation coefficient between different subsets of neurons responding to different odorants over time.	126
4.13	Euclidean distance in neuronal space over time	127
4.14	Distances in neuronal space between stimuli.	128
4.15	PCA trajectories of neuronal stimuli.	130
5.1	Nanion setup and dimensions	142
6.1	1D NMR Spectra of L-Leucine-d10	144
6.2	1D NMR Spectra of L-Lysine-2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-d9 HCl	145
6.3	1D NMR Spectra of L-Phenyl-d5-alanine-2,3,3-d3	146
6.4	1D NMR Spectra of L-Tryptophan-2,4,5,6,7-d5 (indole-d5)	147
6.5	Averaged stimulus responses with corresponding standard deviation	149

List of Tables

1.1	Thesis overview	14
2.1	DH medium stock	40
2.2	Trace metal mix	41
2.3	DH growth medium	41
2.4	Simulation results of AC-voltage across bilayer in millivolt as a function of distance and RF-Frequency	68
2.5	Comparison of single channel parameters	71
4.1	Important IR-vibrations of non-deuterated Aminoacids	116
4.2	Number of stimuli recorded from 7 fish.	122

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Testing the limits of quantum behavior in biological systems

In the early days of biology the common focus on zoology and botany was rarely compatible with contemporary mathematical and physical methods. However, measurement tools which allowed the description of biological processes with atomic precision changed this view dramatically. As a consequence, progress in modern biology is nowadays dependent on the accurate description of molecular interactions using concepts derived from mathematics and classical Newtonian physics. Quantum physics, on the other hand, started by describing the behavior of single atomistic particles but is now used to explain features of objects of increasing complexity and size. The relevant scales of both disciplines overlap on the molecular level and it became clear, that simple quantum physical concepts can explain some specialized biological functions like some mechanisms of enzymes. Already Schrödinger recognized the fundamental fact, that all biological systems arise from the stability, structure and conversions of molecules due to quantum effects ubiquitous on the atomic level [1]. Delocalized electrons and discrete orbitals allow biological systems to store energy or hereditary information in molecular bonds and assemblies stable for millennia. Derived thereof, Van der Waals and electrostatic forces determine the three-dimensional structure of proteins and DNA as well as their molecular recognition and interactions enabling life as we know it. Thus, quantum physics influence on biology was - and for the most part still is - considered to be of trivial nature mainly providing the basis for the ball-and-rod view of size, shape and chemistry of the molecules.

Nonetheless, quantum physics is a fundamental theory and as such its consequences are not limited to atoms and molecules but can in principle reach into the macroscopic everyday world we experience. However, the unique "weirdness" of quantum behavior namely non-locality manifested in particles being in many places at once (e.g. superposition, tunneling and entanglement as introduced below) are in stark contrast to the deterministic and mechanical, machine-like behavior we encounter in cellular processes on the micro scale and every-day life. Still, the functional elements of living biological matter continuously spans across all time and size scales, from atoms and molecules to humans and whales, but it is not clear if and where there is a boundary to be drawn between the quantum and the classical world (see figure 1.1). The flow of information however is bottom-up with molecular processes replicating DNA ultimately defining macroscopic behavior [2].

Thus, especially at the boundary of molecular interactions non-trivial quantum effects might influence biological function beyond its trivial function which ultimately could translate to the classical, macroscopic world: evolving a way of harnessing the parallelism of quantum behavior to gain an advantage in speed and efficiency of a biological process could allow for natural selection of the fitter organism [2]. If this

type of evolution is generally possible a host of questions arises: Is there a limit to which quantum effects impact biological function? Can complex quantum effects directly influence higher level functionalities of living systems such as more sensitive perception of environmental stimuli? Could better perception provide a competitive advantage that can be selected for by evolution? Can we generalize our understanding of such mechanisms and use it to reverse engineer novel biology- and quantum inspired technological tools with classically impossible features?

FIGURE 1.1: Atoms and molecules are governed by trivial quantum effects. Biological proteins are on a fuzzy border between the quantum and the classical world.

We know from precisely verified experiments of single, isolated particles under what circumstances quantum phenomena transition to the classical world. We can apply this knowledge to narrow down the possible scale and complexity up to which quantum effects might be relevant to biological systems.

The main hypothesis of this thesis was to develop a robust toolset to investigate if quantum and vibrational effects induced on the atomic level can impact physiological function on much larger size and time-scales. As an introduction I will introduce typical quantum phenomena and show their limitations in the context of the wet, noisy and warm environments of biological systems. Then I will present current theories and model systems of quantum biology which have an experimentally accessible approach. Finally, I will summarize the three approaches pursued in this thesis.

1.2 Quantum mechanics and their limitations in biological systems

1.2.1 Quantization of energy and definition of non-triviality

Quantum effects are discrete and very small as illustrated by the fundamental unit of quantum mechanics Planck's constant of action $h \approx 10^{-34} Js$. This means, that any systems energy can change only in discontinuous multiples of this minimal increment of energy. This is reflected in the discrete set of electronic or vibrational states of a molecule, measured by spectroscopy as a samples discrete absorption lines. Regularly structural biochemists use these spectral signatures to determine the current set of energy states of increasingly large biomolecules. This information can be used to characterize e.g. the molecular structure, environment and 3D-shape as well as inter and intra-molecular interactions and distances, to name a few.

The everyday routine use of this quantum effect demonstrates not only its triviality for the life sciences, but also the need for proper definition of non-triviality to justify its ascription to the field of quantum biology. As a rule of thumb, it is unlikely for quantum effects to exist if the energies exchanged by the quantum system are smaller than the energy of room temperature ($k_B T$). In this regime, environmental disruption typically decoheres the quantum state much quicker than the reaction rates of any biochemically significant information processing. Enzymes may catalyze bond breakage and bond formation which is at heart a quantum process but the proteins are considered classical entities throughout the process. Biological molecules work at room temperature and are in constant exchange with the environment which quickly decoheres any quantum state (see also section 1.2.3). In this case, quantum mechanics does not convey special functionality above the triviality of providing shape, size and chemical properties.

However, quantum effects in chemical systems allow large energy gaps between states where interaction energies of quantum systems can be higher than $k_B T$. These so called non-equilibrium states can be triggered by single events of quantum effects and can in theory trigger biochemical feedback systems with impact on the macroscopic biological functionality. Thus, excited electronic or vibrational states caused by single spins or photons that introduce special functions to the protein would be considered non-trivial.

1.2.2 Quantum delocalization and superposition

One key feature of quantum mechanics is that mutually exclusive quantum states can be summed to form another valid quantum state which is called a superposition. Hereby, superposed states correspond to a linear combination of solutions of the Schrödinger equation.

This counter-intuitive behavior is best illustrated by the wave-particle duality of light as observed in Young's double-slit experiment [3]. Single photons passing through two narrow slits are detected as localized particles on the detector. However, repetition of the experiment consecutively builds an interference pattern that can be explained only by wave-like properties of the photons during free flight. In order to generate interference, the single energy quantum (photon) has to be spatially delocalized across and diffracted at both slits (see figure 1.2). The subsequent interaction with the detector constitutes a measurement that forces the wavefunction to collapse. The probability to detect an individual photon is hereby determined by the waves squared amplitude.

After de Broglie, all matter exhibits the above described wave-like behavior according to $\lambda = \frac{h}{mv}$. As electrons are very light, their large wavelength of electrons allows them to be delocalized across complex aromatic biomolecules whereas heavier atoms or even molecules have small wavelengths which makes them act as points, and thus classical particles. Although, complex biochemical molecules were shown to exhibit interference in isolated experiments [4] only delocalized electrons and protons are classically considered to be of relevance throughout biological systems [5-7].

An important implication of delocalization for biology is tunneling through energy barriers. Tunneling occurs at energy barriers with a probability corresponding to

FIGURE 1.2: Young's double-slit experiment without observer shows interference patterns.

squared amplitude of the particle and the height of the barrier. This property is harnessed by many enzymatic reactions involving energy transfer to drastically increase reaction speeds at physiological temperatures compared to purely classical mechanisms [8]. In chapter 2 and 4 this thesis will explore methodologies to investigate possible mechanisms based on ion (see figure 1.3) and electron tunneling.

FIGURE 1.3: The scale of the membrane protein KcsAs selectivity filter. The bacterial potassium channel poses the formidable challenge of selecting ions of the same charge with only 0.4\AA difference in size. From left to right: EM of a Bacterium, drawing of cellular environment, crystal structure of KcsA embedded to the membrane (gray) and the conformation of the selectivity filter with Potassium and Sodium, respectively. Selecting these ions by modulating the ions tunneling rate in a wet and noisy environment of a living bacterium would be an extraordinary phenomenon and is investigated in chapter 2.

The probability of tunneling a given barrier drops exponentially amongst others with increasing mass and the number of molecular components. Hence, electron tunneling in biological systems can occur over the distance of many nanometers whereas proton tunneling is highly sensitive to distance fluctuations due to the protons small matter wavelength. The strong distance dependency of tunneling reaction rates allows subtle conformational changes of the proteins structure to modulate enzymatic function. It is hypothesized, that the time available for tunneling in a reaction center of an enzyme can be modulated by global, periodic conformational changes, so called low-frequency vibrations [9, 10]. In chapter 3 a methodological approach is presented to test for the prerequisites of such a mechanism in soil nematodes.

1.2.3 Quantum coherence, decoherence and coupling

Another phenomenon limiting the magnitude to which quantum processes can be relevant for biology is decoherence. The required preservation of the phase relationships between components of the wave functions can be scrambled by interactions with the environment. This so called decoherence forces particles to behave classically and depends on the nature, temperature and strength of coupling to the environment [11–13]

We can illustrate this fact again using Youngs' double slit: A definite phase relation between the waves emerging from both slits leads to interference patterns. The system is coherent until information is lost by interaction with the environment which is governed by random thermal fluctuations. Introducing a measurement device in one of the arms of Youngs' experiment decoheres the system: The quantum mechanical phases of the coherent wave and the detectors atoms differ by large amounts

FIGURE 1.4: Young's double-slit experiment with observer and noisy protein environments. Left: Young's double-slit experiment without observer shows collapse of the wavefunction and no interference pattern. Right: Wet and noisy environment of a protein. This rendering from a molecular dynamics simulation of a membrane protein gives an impression of the vast amount of interactions exhibited by the lipid molecules and the surrounding water. A long-lived quantum state would need to be extraordinarily shielded from the surrounding chaos.

Figure modified from University Calgary

since the detectors atoms are strongly coupled to the environment (heat bath). The addition of both wave functions across the whole system effectively averages out any coherence which destroys the interference pattern. The result is similar to classical behavior since one specific realization of the wave function had to be chosen (see figure 1.4 left).

All quantum systems are weakly coupled to the environment and thus decohere over time depending on the strength of coupling to the environment. As a result, physicists have to meticulously avoid decoherence by decoupling molecules in ultra-high vacuums and low temperatures to observe their quantum states.

However, biological systems present a warm, wet and noisy environments, where molecules continuously interact with other atoms of the same molecule or with other molecules (see figure 1.4 right). Any quantum coherence is quickly decohered due to strong coupling with the environment which itself is in thermal equilibrium. Thus, long lived coherence in a biological system has to be shield and isolated from disrupting thermal vibrations and interactions with the environment. Coupled protein motions can temporally isolate quantum systems and decouple them by coherently locking low frequency protein vibrations to the periodicity of the quantum processes [14]. This interplay of classical and quantum coherences is usually not possible. Low frequency motions of proteins have energies close to room temperature which strongly couple to the environment and dissipate their energy rapidly. However, under certain conditions some coupled protein motions can sustain coherent motion for long enough to facilitate the long-range excitation transfer.

In chapter 2 and 3 this thesis investigates the possible interplay between classically and quantum coherent protein vibrations and protein function.

1.3 Review of biological systems currently investigated in quantum biology

Many different model systems are being investigated in quantum biology [15]. Quantum biologists mostly focus on transport processes such as the transfer of charges and energy. It is investigated if the highly efficient excitation transfer processes in photosynthesis and enzymatic reactions exhibit essential quantum mechanical properties. Other proposals investigate sensing of biological systems such as magnetoreception or the origins of life. Some of these proposals are presented below and tools for studying these systems are investigated as part of this thesis.

1.3.1 Coherent excitation transfer in photosynthetic light-harvesting complex

The current paradigm for quantum coherence in biological systems is a possible quantum coherent mechanism for excitation energy transfer in photosynthesis [15]. The process of photosynthesis relies on so called Light-harvesting complexes (LHC) [16] which are transmembrane proteins that can harbor up to 400 light-absorbing chromophores and occur in all green organisms from green algae to higher plants. These protein complexes are either embedded in the thylacoid membrane of chloroplasts in plants or the cell membrane of bacteria. Together, these LHCs comprise an antenna complex that connects to a reaction center where transmembrane charge separation occurs and ultimately converts solar energy to chemical energy [17]. The pigment chlorophyll attaches to the protein complexes and is arranged in an often highly ordered spatial configuration. A well studied example, the Fenna-Matthews-Olson protein-pigment complex (FMO) from green sulfur bacteria shown in figure 1.5 holds highly symmetrically three pigment molecules. The spatial arrangement is thought to favor energy transfer between groups of pigments which contribute to the near perfect (95%) photon efficiency [18]. As a highly efficient process essential to most life is a highly interesting target to investigate the potential evolution of processes harnessing quantum effects.

The transfer process is initiated by a chromophore absorbing a photon. This leads to an electronic excited state which is usually short lived and decays within few ns [19]. Within this time, the excitation needs to be transferred to the reaction center which might be separated by transport length scales of up to 100 nm [18]. The energy is transferred through a mechanism referred to as resonant energy transfer (RET) [20] where electronic excitations hop between individual chromophores embedded in the protein complexes (see figure 1.6 A).

However, the energy transfer between chlorophyll molecules within these LHCs was believed to rely on a quantum coherent mechanism already in 1938 [21]. Advances in femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy allowed to detect long-lived vibrational coherences on the order of a picosecond and later long-lived (up to a few picoseconds) quantum-electronic coherence were found [22–24]. This wavelike synchronization of electronic excitations called excitons is spread across chromophores. The experimental signature manifests in a beating in amplitude of the so called cross-peaks when scanning the waiting time t_2 (see figure 1.7 B). The time t_2 at which the beating in amplitude of the cross-peak fades corresponds to the lifetime of the coherences. With this a general experimental paradigm of probing a protein system for long-lived vibrational coherences was established.

This evidence suggested, electronic excited states of individual chromophores are in a quantum superposition due to the strong electronic coupling between the densely

FIGURE 1.5: Crystal structure of the bacterial FMO-complex of *Prosthecochloris aestuarii*. Each of the three proteins in the complex contains a bacteriochlorophyll molecule (green)
(Courtesy: Laguna Design/Science Photo Library)

packed periodic arrangement of chlorophyll molecules. The coherence was found spread across the all chromophores of the FMO-complex which are embedded in close contact to the environment of the protein [25]. Usually, the exciton on one of the chromophores would quickly equilibrate with the bath and localize the wavefunction to the donor molecule. The localized exciton [26] would move in a classical hopping-type fashion across the chromophores which are strongly electrostatically coupled due to proximity and relative angles of their transition dipole moments. However, experimental evidence [22–24, 27] supported the suspicion, that initial coherence persists long enough to facilitate to transfer the energy to the reaction center. By being spatially superimposed across all chromophores, this wavelike motion increases efficiency of energy transfer by avoiding local minima in the energy landscape in a quantum random walk [28] (see figure 1.6 B).

The detection of long-lived coherence even at room temperature [27] triggered the investigation of how coherence can exist in wet, noisy and warm environments. Theoretical modeling of environment-assistant transport showed, that some degree of coupling to the protein environment is necessary to promote unidirectional flow and even

FIGURE 1.6: Schematic comparison of traditional vs quantum assisted excitation energy transfer in photosynthesis. **Left:** In the traditional model, a photon is converted to an exciton (round circle) when absorbed by a chlorophyll molecule (green). A random hopping mechanism across the chlorophyll molecules allows the exciton to reach the reactive center (red) where it is converted to chemical energy. **Right:** In the quantum model, the exciton is delocalized across the chlorophyll molecules and samples all possible paths and reduces energy costs by choosing the path of least resistance. Thus, wave-like propagation can lead to higher efficiency energy transport.

increase the transport efficiency of excitation transfer [28, 29]. This environmental-assisted quantum transport avoids localization through dephasing thermal fluctuations of the environment [30]. An optimum between quantum coherence and decoherence allows energy to travel efficiently without being trapped in the system [31–33]. Furthermore, transfer efficiency can be further improved by dephasing noise which modulates individual site energies to overcome large energy gaps due to weak pigment to pigment coupling. This further improves the transfer efficiency [34]. Recent investigations showed, that this electronic coherence originate mainly from ground state vibrations and decay within less than a picosecond [35, 36]. Nonetheless, the fact alone, that excited-state vibronic coherence could be identified is remarkable but its role for photosynthesis is not yet clear [36].

The discovery of these effects was made possible mainly by advancements in two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy (2DES). This methodology (see figure 1.7) uses sequences of broadband femtosecond (fs) infrared laserpulses to first excite and then probe the evolution of the excitation within the system with ps precision. Off-diagonal (so called cross-peaks) of the spectrum indicated strong coupling within the system [37] (see figure 1.7 B). Upon scanning the delay of the probing pulse t_2 a periodic beating of the intensity of this off-diagonal peak was determined [22], thus providing strong evidence for coherence within this system. Similar effects were discovered in photosystems of purple bacteria, marine algae and higher plants which showed that structurally vastly different protein complexes harnessed the same principle of transport [38]. Investigations into the evolutionary importance of quantum coherence [39, 40] and the application of its design principles in synthetic systems for light-driven processes could fuel quantum biology inspired nanotechnologies and materials. Amongst many ideas, the most direct impact could be more efficient solar conversion [41, 42]. This could improve the efficiency of solar panels which could help in advancing the electrification of the power grid to tackle challenges posed by climate change.

FIGURE 1.7: Introduction to 2DIR spectroscopy. The characterization of a hypothetical protein with three distinct spectral regions is depicted and the influence of pump-probe time-delay and isotope labelling is shown on 1DIR and 2DIR spectroscopic readout. **Top:** Two femtosecond IR pulses with a time-delay of t_1 excite the system and a third laser pulse probes the system after a variable waiting time t_2 . The pulse sequence is depicted for a) no pump-probe time-delay ($t_2 = 0$) and b) a waiting time of a few picoseconds ($t_2 > 0$). **Mid:** The 1DIR spectrum of the unlabeled protein (green line) shows the amide absorptions at 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1} . The x-axis corresponds to the pump-frequency of the 2DIR experiment and is given in wavenumbers. The pump sequence does not change the 1DIR spectrum significantly. **Bottom:** The 2DIR spectrum is usually depicted as ω_{pump} vs ω_{probe} . A) In the case of $t_2 = 0$, $\omega_{pump} = \omega_{probe}$ as there was no time left for the system to evolve and transfer energies between coupled sites. The peaks (green circles) appear on the diagonal at the same pump frequencies as in the 1DIR plot (1640 and 1620 cm^{-1}). The intensity of each peak is usually depicted as topological lines within a peak (not shown). Line-shape analysis of the ellipticity and topological intensity distribution within a peak contains information on the homogeneous broadening and intermolecular couplings amongst others. B) increasing the waiting time to $t_2 > 0$ allows for energy transfer between coupled sites. Coupling between the main peaks at 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1} gives rise to a so called cross-peak (filled green circle) that resides on the off-diagonal. The strength of the coupling is derived from the intensity of the cross-peak. Its time-evolution can be investigated by scanning t_2 .

Although the methodology of 2DES enabled good understanding of the photosystem, little progress was made towards generalizing this methodological approach to other biological systems exhibiting highly effective transport characteristics. Progress is often hampered by the lack of methodologies for complex isotope labeling and deuteration procedures. A thorough characterization of the possibilities to prepare suitable samples in other biological model proteins could open up the path towards similar discoveries and ultimately a better general understanding of vibrationally assisted transport processes in biological systems. In addition, better methodology might lay the foundation for a better understanding equilibrium states on ultrafast timescales. Thus, this thesis investigates in chapter 2 the applicability of current methodologies to enable 2DIR studies of quantum effects in a different warm, wet and complex yet highly efficient system, namely ion channels.

1.3.2 Magnetoreception

Birds can sense the earth's magnetic field and use it for navigation during migration [43]. Their magnetic compass provides directional information by detecting the inclination of the magnetic field [44] in a light [45] and resonance [46] dependent manner. The small strength of the earth's magnetic field suggests a molecular mechanism which is sensitive to both changes in intensity and direction of the field. A radical-pair based mechanism was proposed in 1978 [47, 48] and is completely independent of the competing classical magnetite based theory [43]. According to Schulten *et. al.* [47], a Cryptochrome type protein within the animal's retina forms a radical pair within the protein upon absorption of light [49, 50] (see figure 1.8). The simultaneous production of the two free radicals couples their spin in a long-lived quantum coherent state. Weak external fields can disturb this balance and effectively modulate the radical pairs' lifetime. The strength of the disruption depends on the orientation of the protein with respect to the magnetic field which could be the weak geomagnetic field of the earth [51]. It is unclear how the signal created by the radical pair is transduced to create magnetosensation, however, the electric field generated by the radical pair could modulate the absorption efficiency of adjacent photoreceptors. Thus, the magnetic field information could be effectively overlaid on top of the bird's visual field [52]. This is consistent with the observation that birds need blue light to navigate via magnetism [45].

Different types of Cryptochromes have been confirmed in the eyes of migratory birds [54] which displayed radicals lasting over a millisecond when excited by blue light [50]. Especially Cry4 is overexpressed during the time of migration of the birds and is located in the cones of the retina [55] narrowing the search for target molecules. Thus, model systems of cell types, *in vitro* molecular essays and crystal structures aim to confirm the concrete underlying building blocks for mediating the mechanism [56–58]. Reconstituting the whole magnetosensitive molecular pathway to other systems might allow exciting new possibilities i.e. magnetic control of neuronal firing with unprecedented new possibilities for neurobiology [59, 60].

1.3.3 Role of vibrational and quantum effects for enzymatic catalysis

Enzymes accelerate the reaction rates of otherwise slow chemical reactions which is essential for biological function. Quantum effects like tunneling are often found for enzymes catalyzing hydrogen-transfer [61]. Interestingly, standard quantum models can describe the reaction rates of the enzymes only if the conformational space of the protein is being included to the model. Classically, the protein's activity is modulated

FIGURE 1.8: Light-dependent magnetic compass sensing hypothesis in birds. The birds eye detects the inclination of the earths magnetic field most likely via chrytochrome molecules located in the retina. Light absorption within the chrytochromes generates a long-lived radical whose electromagnetic field could influence the absorption efficiency of adjacent light sensing molecules. Tethered and aligned cryptochromes adjacent to the rhodopsin molecules could result in different reaction yields in different parts of the retina based on the magnetic inclination. This would result in a visual impression of the magnetic bearing (modified from [53]).

by allosteric changes via the full array of known conformational changes [62] which can change reaction rates of the reaction center by modulating its spatial arrangement [63]. Ligands selectively enhance or damp certain vibrational modes of the protein which changes the pool of conformations the protein can access. This limits the probability of certain functional conformations (i.e. high affinity substrate binding site) and thus catalytic rate [64, 65]. These collective low-frequency, condensed matter waves - often referred to as phonons - like vibrational impact modes of whole protein domains in the terrahertz regime (<3 THz, <100 cm^{-1}) [10] and have been shown to impact protein function [9]. Recently, it was shown, that delocalized low-frequency modes are coupled to the reaction coordinate of the protein Lysozyme [66]. Such coupling could provide an catalytic advantage and as all proteins are considered allosteric [67] it is unclear if particular vibrational modes are a evolutionarily selectable trait for the modulation of enzymatic function. Disseminating such interactions requires highly sensitive and specific molecular tools, one of which will be investigated in chapter 3.

1.3.4 Direct observation of quantum effects in single molecule interferometry

A direct investigation of the wave-particle duality of biological matter can be achieved via atom interferometry. While all approaches above investigate the problem within complex proteins, here physicists apply Young's double-slit experiment to individual complex molecules (see figure 1.9). Bimolecular electronic properties, approximated as *de Broglie* waves, can be investigated independent of coupling to the environment in the gas phase in addition to new tests for general relativity and quantum physics [68]. The fact that these single-molecule experiments take place in vacuum allows larger and larger molecules to exhibit trivial quantum effects during the double-slit experiment. The methodology was limited to robust molecules due to the harsh conditions during molecule ablation. Albeit the chemical structures i.e. Fullerenes can be termed organic, for a long time the molecules used in these experiments were not naturally found in living organisms. This drastically limits the applicability of the methodology for the characterization of molecules more relevant to biological function. New methods for milder desorption [69] allowed to move from rigid small molecules towards large flexible molecules of up to 25 kDa [70] and even polypeptides with the molecular weight of 25 kDa [71]. Atom interferometry is conducted under highly non-biological circumstances which limit the transferability of the findings to biological function. Nonetheless, the polypeptide exhibiting quantum superposition is even larger than the monomer of one of the protein KcsA purified and investigated in the course of this thesis which motivates the investigation of potential quantumness of small parts of this protein in a physiological state.

1.4 Experimental approaches of this thesis

The summary of investigated systems and the methodologies used suggests there are no straightforward approaches to detect and investigate quantum effects in biology. Especially, discoveries were driven by novel experimental methodologies (e.g. Atom interferometry, ultrafast 2DIR). Especially novel ideas and experimental advances may drive discovery. For this, the tools need to be thoroughly characterized and linked to its impact on biological functionality in order to pave the way. In addition, small changes in the behavior of a protein might be amplified using naturally existing highly non-linear systems like neurons or a whole brain. With this natural amplification in signal, the potentially small effects introduced by interventions on the atomic scale could be measured macroscopically.

This thesis characterizes three different approaches with atomic scale interventions with readouts from the scale of sub-domains of proteins to neurons and whole brain dynamics, respectively. The models systems were carefully chosen to be well characterized and ubiquitously used throughout the scientific community. With this, I could draw from a large toolset of available methodologies which could be adapted to the specific question at hand. The individual hypothesis per system is different, however all investigated systems are linked to a macroscopic function which can be determined by some physiological function. The experimental methodologies had mostly be developed or adapted from existing approaches. They were tailored to the respective physiological functionality and involved ultrafast spectroscopy, single channel electrophysiology to Calcium imaging of neurons. An atomic scale manipulation

FIGURE 1.9: Young's double-slit experiment using biological molecules shows interference patterns as the molecule travels as a *de Broglie* wave.

was introduced in order to interfere with the hypothesized quantum or vibrational behavior which would then be measured via the respective developed experimental methodology. Each approach is accompanied by spectral characterization in order to determine the scale of the intervention (e.g. isotope labeling) or to read out the behavior of spectral probes giving insights of the local environment within the system.

With this, a comprehensive experimental framework is established which is uniquely suited to investigate the challenges in using such a toolset for the cause of quantum biological investigations. This thesis establishes methodologies allowing manipulation of well established model systems with atomic precision as well as reliable quantitative experimental readouts which can be tied to behavioral effects. Unifying molecular and behavioral experimental workflows and precisely placed molecular spectroscopic probes allow to sample the proteins on a time-scale relevant to quantum effects and provide functional readouts at the same time.

TABLE 1.1: This table explains amongst others the different models systems, associated physiological function and experimental paradigms investigated in this thesis.

Scale	Protein	Neuron	Brain
Model system	Ion Channel KcsA	Roundworm (<i>C.Elegans</i>)	Zebrafish (<i>D.Rerio</i>)
Amplification of signal	Linear	Non-linear	Highly non-linear
Hypothesis	Quantum / vibrationally assisted ion transport	Low frequency protein modes	Electron tunneling
Macroscopic function	Ion selectivity	Oxygen sensing	Discrimination of odorants
Atomic scale manipulation	Isotope label, Mutants	Isotope label	Isotope label
Physiological impact	Vibrational coupling	Neuronal dynamics	Brain dynamics
Experimental readout	2DIR, MD	Calcium imaging	Calcium imaging
Spectral characterization	FTIR, 2DIR	Normal mode analysis	FTIR, 1D-NMR
Chapter	2	3	4

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Chapter 2

Vibrationally and quantum coherence assisted ion transport

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 The classical view of ion transport in KcsA

Structural basis for selectivity and transport in KcsA

Ion-channels are integral transmembrane protein complexes through which ions can flow in or out of the cell along a concentration gradient. They are essential building blocks for maintaining the membrane potential and create electric excitability in cells [72]. One common feature of ion-channels is the presence of a gate that can be activated by chemicals, light, voltage or mechanical stress and a selectivity filter responsible for the conduction of only specific types of ions. One of the best studied example of the family of K^+ channels is KcsA [73–77]. Like all members of this family, it shares conserved features like the tetrameric helical structure spanning the transmembrane region and a selectivity filter near the extracellular surface. K^+ channels combine remarkable throughput rates as high as $\approx 10^8$ ions / sec [78] with a high ($\approx 10^4:1$) discrimination rate [73, 79] between Na^+ and the K^+ . The responsible structure for near-diffusion-limited efficiency of permeation and strong selection for K^+ is the selectivity filter. This conserved feature [80] is comprised of a short, peptide loop (TVGYG) from each of the four helices [73] (figure 2.1 A). The oxygen atoms of the filters backbone carbonyl groups are pointing towards the pores center and form four axial binding sites S1-S4 (figure 2.1 B) whose potential minima trap and coordinate positive charges. Studies by x-ray crystallography revealed what is believed to be two degenerate states where the filter is alternately occupied with K^+ and water molecules (see (S1,S3) and (S2,S4) in figure 2.1 B). These sites are axially only separated by 0.24 nm with a width between the carbonyl groups of 0.3 nm which implied a single-file fashion transport of ions without their hydration shells [74, 75]. Ions arrive from the extracellular site via an aqueous cavity where they are stabilized by helix dipole moments close to S4 [73]. The entrance to this cavity is regulated by a pH gate which can be voltage-modulated [81, 82]. A global twisting motion is caused by $pH > 4$, which blocks ion entry to the cavity and triggers the collapse of the selectivity filter into a non-conductive conformation [77, 83–85].

Traditional models of ion selection assumed that the selectivity filter is rigid and that ions are selected due to the precise positions of the selectivity filters carbonyl groups (the “Snug-fit” model) [73, 86]. In this case, the oxygen atoms of the selectivity filters carbonyl groups would snugly complex the dehydrated K^+ while the rigidity of the backbone does not allow to accommodate the smaller Na^+ . Basically, the different dehydration energies for Na^+ and K^+ would make it energetically unfavorable for a Na^+ ion to shed its hydration shell [87]. As a conclusion, the energy wells of the

FIGURE 2.1: Schematic structure of KcsA. A) Transmembrane region of KcsA with K^+ Ions (purple) in the (S1, S3) configuration inside the selectivity filter. The extended filter region comprised of filter and pore helices is shown in red. B) Ion binding configurations inside the binding sites (S1-4) of the schematic selectivity filter for the three most commonly discussed configurations.

channel are deeper for K^+ than for Na^+ and the less-preferred Na^+ is excluded also in equilibrium [73, 87–91]. The high throughput is described by a mechanism where the high transport rates rely on a delicate balance of ion-ion repulsion and ion-channel attraction called the "knock-on" mechanism [92, 93]. The two ion configurations (S1,S3) and (S2,S4) are thought to have almost similar energy with only a low energy barrier separating them [94]. The states would be able to easily interchange until an intracellular K^+ ion binds to the selectivity filter position S4. The strong repulsion between the K^+ ions inside the filter would initiate a concerted movement from of (S1,S3)-ions to (S2,S4) effectively releasing the S1- K^+ to the extracellular side [95, 96].

Dynamic models of selectivity and transport

Insights from mutational [97], computational [95, 96, 98–101] and NMR studies [102] challenged the view of a static selectivity filter and sparked an ongoing vivid debate on the importance of dynamics for the channel function (see [103], and references therein). Simulations showed, that the relative spatial positions of the carbonyl oxygens vary up to 1.0 Å due to thermal fluctuations [95, 98], whereas the difference in radius required for the "snug-fit" model of K^+ and Na^+ is only ≈ 0.38 Å. The coulombic ion-ion repulsion in the filter is subjected to significant fluctuations in this fluid-like environment. Thus, the delicate balance between ion-ion-channel attraction and ion-ion repulsion to facilitate the "knock-on" mechanism cannot be practically met [95, 96, 100].

In addition, the finding of a binding site for Na^+ and Li^+ close to S4 (figure 2.1 B) showed, that smaller ions are coordinated in an in-plane position [104]. This

suggested, that Na^+ ions are selected against by binding too rigidly to S4 and are selected kinetically by loosing their ability to knock on the ions inside the filter [105]. As recently demonstrated, the filter is able to allow for direct ionic contact between four K^+ ions in the filter. The binding energy of an ion entering S4 would therefore be able to energetically destabilize the energy surface of ions in S2 / S1 and enable diffusion-limited transport [101]. Short-term (ns) flexibility of the carbonyl groups is also thought to be the molecular transitions responsible for long-term (ms) modal gating events in KcsA. Interestingly, mutation of the contacts between pore-helix and filter were identified to play a crucial role for the stability and maintenance of selectivity of the filter [106] highlighting the importance of the surrounding structural support for the functionality of the filter [107]. In conclusion, this shows, that long-ranged rigidity is necessary to fold the channel and confines the carbonyl residues of the filter, whereas short-range flexibility enables the quick binding and rapid exchange of ions and water. However, an interplay between long-ranged rigidity and short-ranged flexibility could limit the extend of molecular transitions which allows for rapid kinetics [103].

Intuitively, a flexible filter would allow high-throughput but hardly be selective, whereas a rigid structure could potentially select well for ion type but limit the throughput certainly below the diffusion limit due to the tight interaction. Thus, the remaining question is how a non-rigid selectivity filter achieves both high throughput while being selectivity. It is now believed [95, 96, 100] that to answer this question, carefully balanced atomic interactions and oscillations need to be considered. For this models and experimental methods with atomic precision are needed.

2.1.2 Hypothesis of quantum coherence in ion transport

It is known that K^+ and water exist likely as two different sequences in the selectivity filter. Crystallographic analysis showed electrodensity for two K^+ ions within the selectivity filter at all times [75]. Two configurations namely S1,3 and S2,4 (1,3 and 2,4) referring to the binding sites along the filter (figure 2.1 B) are energetically nearly degenerate [95] and separated by a potential well. It is an open question whether these spatial configurations possess a functional significance for the properties of the ion channel [101]. In [100] it was shown by molecular dynamics simulation that the thermal vibrations of the carbonyl bonds may play a role in the transport as the jump of a K^+ water pair is accompanied by a strong rotation of a carbonyl group. The rotation of the carbonyl group can lower the potential well between the 1,3 and 2,4 states thus enhancing the direct tunnel interaction between these configurations. Furthermore, the coupling between close lying energy levels of the adjacent binding sites could lead to coherent superpositions of vibrational modes. In such a scenario the superposition of the vibrational modes could also translate into a superposition of the 1,3 and 2,4 conformational states which have individually been observed in x-ray crystallography data [88] and which are found to represent energetically nearly degenerated states in molecular dynamic simulations [94]. Adding quantum coherent tunneling to the purely incoherent model for transport of an ion channel that was presented in [108] can lead to significant changes in the conduction properties of this model. Hence, the simultaneous presence of quantum coherent tunneling and thermally activated hopping can lead to non-trivial behaviors. The following crude estimate illustrates an alternative view of a quantum assisted ion transport. Based on the thermal energy of $E = k_b T / 2 \approx 2 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$ of the ions, the de-Broglie wavelength $\lambda_{DB} = h / \sqrt{2mE}$ of the K^+ matter wave can be estimated to be $\approx 0.05 \text{ nm}$. Given that the periodicity of the axial modulation of the potential is $\approx 0.25 \text{ nm}$, it is within

a factor of five of the K^+ matter wavelength. In this sense, the transmission could involve a process that can be viewed as the diffraction of the K^+ matter wave of a one-dimensional (1D) axial ‘grating’ formed by the modulations of the potential energy. The extent to which quantum coherence exists in an ion channel and whether it would be of sufficient size to affect significantly the properties of the ion channel needs thorough experimental investigation.

The high fidelity of ion-selectivity could be facilitated by a mechanism involving interplay between quantum tunneling and vibrationally induced fluctuations. In this fashion in a manner similar to how stochastic resonances [109–112] allow classically the detection of a weak signal in a noisy environment, it has been theoretically shown [100] that thermally induced fluctuations of the K^+ binding potentials are lowering these barriers from time to time sufficiently such that tunneling can occur. The shape and the height of the ion-binding potential are strongly influenced by the position and the type of ions. Therefore a hypothetical binding of a Na^+ ion in the binding sites 1,3 or 2,4 would lead to a change of the binding potential with a significantly higher potential barrier such that, the thermal fluctuations around such a minimum would not lower the width and height of the binding potential sufficiently to allow tunneling. In this sense quantum assisted selectivity and transport for K^+ is facilitated through an interplay between thermal fluctuations and tunneling between the 1,3 and 2,4 state while the suppression of transport (and binding) for Na^+ can be seen as a result of an increase of the potential barrier. Theoretical simulations indicate [108] that this effect could be sufficient to explain the low affinity and hence low transport probability of the selectivity of the filter for Na^+ .

2.1.3 Potential quantum resonances probed by electrophysiology

Theory of quantum resonances

A hypothetical model which could be empirically tested to demonstrate that the ion selectivity and transport process cannot be an entirely classical process is based on a simplified model which was presented described by *Vaziri et al* [108]. The model calculates the Hamiltonian of the ion binding configurations in the filter while taking into account a Coulomb potential along the axis of the filter similar. This model of the filter can be approximated as chain of quantum harmonic oscillators that are coupled to the environment as a source and sink of excitations that traverse the selectivity filter. To make the model more realistic and account for the effects of the biological temperatures on quantum coherence, it was assumed that dephasing can occur through interactions with the thermal fluctuations of the carbonyl groups. Using experimentally determined parameters of the selectivity filter from [94, 100] and under certain circumstances this system is thought to exhibit behavior only explained by underlying quantum processes namely deconstructive and constructive interference. An external field across the selectivity filter that oscillates with frequencies similar to the rate of K^+ transport would drive the system externally and induce at certain deconstructively resonant frequencies the reduction in transport rate. Measuring the conductivity over the externally applied frequency of the external AC potential could serve as a sensitive measure for verifying the validity of this model (see figure 2.2 left).

This is in sharp contrast to what would be observed if dephasing would have destroyed all coherences leading to a classical “hopping type” transport process. In that case, the conduction of ions would have been governed by pure rate processes, making it essentially independent of the frequency of the external driving force. Hence quantum resonances provide us with a classical signature which allows determining

FIGURE 2.2: Signature of quantum resonances and experimental patch clamp setup. Left: Conductivity versus strength of the applied AC potential for a chain of 5 coupled quantum harmonic oscillators. As the AC potential or frequency is varied, the conductance is strongly modulated in a periodic manner. Even at dephasing rates of $2 \times 10^8 s^{-1}$ (i.e. comparable to the ion transfer rate) resonances can still be observed. Right: Patch clamp setup for delivery of external AC field. Equivalent circuit for the excised patch configuration and an external driving AC field to induce quantum resonances in the selectivity filter of K^+ channels embedded in a membrane. Figures adapted from [108].

the presence of quantum coherence in the underlying dynamics of a system. It is important to note, that quantum resonances do not need to occur in the ion channel during its natural function in order for one to be able to use them as a tool to report on the presence of quantum coherence. In a sense the induction of quantum resonances can be viewed as a dynamic probing of the system that reveals information about the systems parameters such as site energies, coupling and dephasing rates from which the presence of quantum coherence during its natural function can be deduced. Given the parameters of the selectivity filter, Vaziri and Plenio have shown that such quantum resonances can be expected for driving fields on the order of ≈ 100 MHz at which the transport would be significantly suppressed (figure 2.2 left).

Experimental approach of assessing quantum resonances by high-frequency AC field during single channel electrophysiological recordings

According to Vaziri and Plenio, the dynamics of a coupled quantum system might exhibit resonances that are absent in a classical system. The (artificial) induction of such quantum resonances in a system might modify classical observables such as the transport rate through the system. This change in the classical behavior serves as an experimentally testable readout of quantum coherence in the underlying dynamics of the system as it would not occur in a system whose dynamics can be described by purely classical rate equations. As mentioned above, quantum resonances do not need to occur in the ion channel during its natural function in order for one to be able to use them as a tool to report on the presence of quantum coherence. A novel electrophysiology approach similar to patch clamping [113] with electronic modifications for delivering high frequency external fields is needed to observe the quantum resonances as predicted in Vaziri and Plenio (see figure 2.2 right). Commercially available planar patch clamp setups (Nanion GmbH) based on black lipid membranes [114] provide reproducible experimental conditions and allow spatial degrees of freedoms to add the external electronic modifications needed for delivery of the high frequency field.

In this setup, the ion channel is reconstituted into a lipid vesicle which bursts upon physical contact with a glass surface and forms a bilayer across a small aperture in a glass chip. The ion solutions on both sides of the glass chip are chosen to open the pH-sensitive outer gate of KcsA only on one side of the chip [115, 116]. This allows uni-directional flow of ions through the membrane in the presence of an externally applied constant holding potential. The gating kinetics of KcsAs filter gate allows ion currents to flow over few hundred milliseconds to seconds at a time [106, 117] and can be amplified and recorded by a current to voltage converter. The high conductance of 100 pS through KcsA [79] enables pico-ampere single channel currents which provides the SNR necessary for detecting the proposed small modulations of the conductance by the external field. Typically multiple ion channels can be present on a membrane patch of the size of the glass chips aperture. This will not reduce the experimental sensitivity to the signature of quantum coherence as coherence is manifested in a change of a ‘bulk’ ionic current as a function of the externally applied AC-driving force [108]. To observe the predicted quantum resonances, an alternating driving potential, $\hbar\Omega_1\cos\omega t$ is applied across the channel at the frequency exceeding the ion-channel transmission rate of approx. 10^8s^{-1} [108] (figure 2.2 right). For an energy difference of $\hbar\Omega_0$ between adjacent potential wells it is expected, that the resonances will be found at the zeros of the Bessel functions $J_{\Omega_0/\omega}(\Omega_0/\omega)$ [108] (see figure 2.2 left). The AC field can be introduced by an external Radio Frequency (RF) source while recording the ionic current.

2.1.4 Potential signatures of quantum and vibrational effects probed by IR-spectroscopy of KcsA

Introduction to 1DIR, 2DIR spectroscopy and spectroscopic modelling of KcsA

Infrared spectroscopy and computational modelling is often used to characterize the structure and dynamics of proteins and peptides. One-dimensional infrared (1DIR) spectroscopy measures the infrared (IR) absorption of backbone carbonyl groups in the so called amide I band between 1600 and 1700cm^{-1} . The resulting spectrum is the ensemble average of all carbonyl groups within the protein. This means, the combination of all carbonyl groups of a protein composed of hundreds or even thousands of amino-acids all contribute to a single spectrum. To decipher the structural components contributing to the spectrum spectral decomposition is used to fit gaussian peaks to the absorption peaks. Typical types of structures give rise to these spectral components as the site frequency (ω) of each amide I vibration senses its local environment: α -helical and random coil structures are observed in the range of 1650 - 1660cm^{-1} whereas β -sheets have two peaks with a weak and strong mode at 1670 - 1690cm^{-1} and 1620 - 1630cm^{-1} , respectively. The different components derive from the ensemble-averaged local environments of all carbonyl groups in the respective structural arrangement. Isotope labeling (e.g. $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$) can shift the frequency of the manipulated carbonyl group of up to 60cm^{-1} . This might allow to investigate the carbonyl group in a region of the spectrum that is devoid of absorption bands of other non-labeled carbonyl groups. This allows the investigation of the local environment of the isotope labeled carbonyl group and changes to environmental conditions with high signal-to-noise ratio (see mid section of figure 2.3).

Amide vibrations can be coupled to adjacent sites if they share similar site frequencies and orientation in space. In order to resolve this coupling, two-dimensional infrared (2DIR) vibrational spectroscopy allows the readout of molecular dynamics of peptides and proteins on a picosecond time scale [118–121]. The principle behind

this methodology is similar to NMR spectroscopy: localized vibrations retain the vibrational energy of an IR pump pulse. After a certain waiting time, a probe pulse can assess the spectral evolution of the system. (see top and bottom section of figure 2.3). For 2DIR the time-scale depends on the lifetime of a carbonyl group excitation which allows sampling of the dynamics of the environment on the order of picoseconds. In case of the absence of coupling, the amide group absorbs at the same frequency when tested by the probe pulse after a certain waiting time. In the typical contour plots of 2DIR experiments with the pump and probe frequencies denoting the x and y axis, respectively, this leads to a peak on the diagonal. However, if an oscillator is coupled to another site it transfers the vibrational energy deposited by the pump pulse over time. The change in absorption frequency of the probe pulse after the energy transfer is depicted as a so called off-diagonal peak. Similarly, electronic 2D spectroscopy found similar coherently coupled oscillators in the photosystem [22, 27] which can shift energy back and forth. This is detected by scanning the waiting time between probe and pump pulse: The off-diagonal peak appears as a variation of the amplitude of the off-diagonal feature. Isotope labeling serves a similar purpose as in 1DIR experiments, namely as local probes with known position within the structure.

2DIR spectra are notoriously difficult to interpret. In order to have a direct method of deciphering the molecular origin of spectral signatures such as line-broadening and peak positions the computational approach of spectroscopic modeling can aid in the analysis of the experimental spectra (see 2.4). In short, a crystal structure of the protein is used to simulate the position of each carbonyl group within the target environment. Then the site strength and coupling between all carbonyl groups is modelled *in silico* and a synthetic 2DIR spectrum is calculated. This allows to match the underlying structure to the experimentally observed spectrum.

The thesis attempted to combine these methodologies to enable the investigation of the different hypothesis described below:

1. Expression of the membrane protein KcsA
2. Site directed or uniform isotope labeling of KcsA
3. 1DIR spectroscopy of KcsA
4. 2DIR spectroscopy of KcsA
5. Spectroscopic modelling of KcsA

The combination of these methodologies could potentially allow to investigate a complex system like KcsA on picosecond timescales with atomic resolution. The thesis uses a combination of these approaches to first simulate an expected effect and then compares the outcome to the experimentally observed data of the real world systems. At the time of design and execution of the experiments only limited research on the combination of methodologies was available for a membrane protein as complex as KcsA. While expression and reconstitution of wild-type KcsA was well established (see section [Expression of KcsA](#)) only limited evidence was available for site directed isotope labeling of KcsA (see section [Experimental approach of isotope labeling and transient 2DIR spectroscopy](#)). 1DIR studies of K^+ and Na^+ binding to KcsA in lipid membranes demonstrated that ion exchange produced peaks at 1680, 1659 and 1627 cm^{-1} which were confirmed to stem from the selectivity filter by studying mutations of the filter [122]. 2DIR experiments on model-compounds [123] mimicking KcsAs selectivity filter demonstrated the feasibility of investigating binding of K^+ to carbonyl groups that are similar to the selectivity filters structure in 2DIR. The same

FIGURE 2.3: Explanation of isotope labeling in 2DIR spectroscopy. The characterization of a hypothetical protein with three distinct spectral regions is depicted and the influence of pump-probe time-delay and isotope labeling is shown on 1DIR and 2DIR spectroscopic readout. **Top:** Two femtosecond IR pulses with a time-delay of t_1 excite the system and a third laser pulse probes the system after a variable waiting time t_2 . The pulse sequence is depicted for a) no pump-probe time-delay ($t_2 = 0$) and b) a waiting time of a few picoseconds ($t_2 > 0$). **Mid:** The 1DIR spectrum of the unlabeled protein (green line) shows the amide absorptions at 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1} . The x-axis corresponds to the pump-frequency of the 2DIR experiment and is given in wavenumbers. The pump sequence does not change the 1DIR spectrum significantly. Isotope labeling (e.g. by $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ carbonyl groups) shifts parts of the spectrum from the peak at 1620 cm^{-1} to 1580 cm^{-1} (purple peak). Shifting this peak to a background free region allows better experimental investigation, as changes in this spectral region can be unanimously attributed to the isotope labeled amino acids surroundings. **Bottom:** The 2DIR spectrum is usually depicted as ω_{pump} vs ω_{probe} . a) In the case of $t_2 = 0$, $\omega_{\text{pump}} = \omega_{\text{probe}}$ as there was no time left for the system to evolve and transfer energies between coupled sites. The peaks (green circles) appear on the diagonal at the same pump frequencies as in the 1DIR plot (1640 and 1620 cm^{-1}). The intensity of each peak is usually depicted as topological lines within a peak (not shown). Line-shape analysis of the ellipticity and topological intensity distribution within a peak contains information on the homogeneous broadening and intermolecular couplings amongst others. $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling of some of the carbony groups shifts a portion of the spectrum towards lower wavenumbers giving rise to the peak at around 1580 cm^{-1} (purple circle on diagonal). b) increasing the waiting time to $t_2 > 0$ allows for energy transfer between coupled sites. Coupling between the main peaks at 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1} gives rise to a so called cross-peak (filled green circle) that resides on the off-diagonal. The strength of the coupling is derived from the intensity of the cross-peak. Its time-evolution can be investigated by scanning t_2 . Cross-peaks can also exist between isotope labeled carbonyl groups and non-labeled carbonyls (purple circles). In this hypothetical sample, the $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled carbonyl groups at 1580 cm^{-1} are coupled both with carbonyls at 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1} , respectively.

FIGURE 2.4: Spectral modeling approach for 2DIR of KcsA. 2DIR in combination with spectral modeling allows to link experimental spectral data to molecular resolution atomic locations and dynamics via spectral modeling: First, an experimental 2DIR spectrum of KcsA is acquired. A crystal structure of the protein with ions in different binding states is then equilibrated in a short molecular dynamics simulation. This allows the calculation of site energies of the selectivity filter region where local ions influence the carbonyls bond vibrations. Calculation of the Amide-I Hamiltonian allows to characterize the strength of transition dipole coupling between sites. Strong coupling allows exchange of energy over time which relates to off-peak signal when calculating the resulting 2DIR spectra from the model. By subtracting the difference spectra of two separate simulations with different ion states a direct link can be established between spectral characteristics and the underlying molecular structure and dynamics.

publication used spectroscopic modeling to characterize the impact of isotope labeling strategies on the strength of spectral signature of relevant ion binding states (see [123] and section [Modeling driven isotope labeling strategy](#)). The thesis details an experimental approach for combining these five methods to a toolset for investigation of molecular dynamics of KcsA with high temporal and spatial resolution. During the course of the thesis a consortium of the labs of pioneers of the main methodologies (E. Perozo for expression of KcsA, B. Roux for molecular dynamics and spectroscopic modelling of KcsA, F. Valiyaveetil for isotope labeling of membrane proteins and M. Zanni for 2DIR spectroscopy) published a detailed characterization of KcsA ion configurations using this combination of tools [124].

Theory of transient signatures of quantum and vibrational effects using 2DIR

In order to link function to potential quantum and vibrational effects in KcsA similar spectroscopic features would need to be detected during channel function. Analogously, the change in the amount of energy transferred between the spectral features of the 1,3 and 2,4 states over time would support the hypothesis of quantum effects

in ion transport in KcsA. Requirements to use vibrational spectroscopy as a tool to validate this hypothesis are:

1. Unambiguous assignment of spectral signature of 1,3 and 2,4 states
2. Detection of off-diagonal feature between 1,3 and 2,4 states
3. Initialization of K^+ transport event synchronously in most channels with picosecond precision
4. Detection of amplitude beating in off-diagonal feature between 1,3 and 2,4 states

The individual eigenstates for which coherence is postulated (1,3 and 2,4 state) must correlate with distinct spectroscopic signatures. The strong positive charge of K^+ ions adjacent to the filters negative carbonyl groups drastically alters the carbonyls site-energies and coupling properties which is detectable by IR [125]. K^+ binding to the filter changes its conformation to accommodate chelation by six or eight carbonyl groups depending on the binding site. Studying these complexes in model compounds for biological K^+ binding resembling these coordination geometry revealed distinct IR-signatures of ion binding. Structural changes from the disordered states of the unbound ionophores to ordered, symmetric states after ion coordination lead to less variation in the carbonyls site-energies and environments. Upon addition of KCl, the spectroscopic data (figure 2.5A) revealed intensified and narrowed spectral peaks of Valinomycin carbonyl groups [123]. This change was even more apparent in 2DIR spectroscopy (see figure 2.5) where strong diagonal narrowing of the 2DIR lineshapes accompanies ion exchange. Similar behaviour was observed in the model compound Nonactin which exhibits an eight-fold coordination compared to the six-fold coordination in Valinomycin [123].

As a conclusion, ions binding to model compounds of K^+ binding states and to the real filter induced measurable IR-signatures reflecting the underlying structural changes and rigidification upon ion binding. However, unambiguous assignment of the molecular origin of each spectral feature in KcsA was not possible [122]. Thus, the individual signatures of states 1,3 and 2,4 were convoluted with the signal of all other parts of the protein. However, discerning the states might be accomplished by site-specific isotope labels (see section 2.1.4) combined with spectroscopic modeling. Latter method interprets spectral features with atomistic structural resolution without the need for labeling by correlating the vibrational frequency of an amide carbonyl with its electrostatic environment (see section 2.2.6 and [121, 126]).

Modeling driven isotope labeling strategy

As described above, the filters carbonyl groups comprise only $\approx 5\%$ (20 out of 408 groups) of KcsAs carbonyl groups. Site specific isotope labels in the filter could shift the filters spectral signature away from the protein background. Commonly, amino acids with $^{13}C^{18}O$ carbonyl groups introduce a 60 cm^{-1} redshift in the oscillation of the respective carbonyls [127]. This could allow for background-free observation of the K^+ induced frequency shifts and increase the SNR of these signatures.

This approach was validated by simulations of the expected spectroscopic signatures of all different $^{13}C^{18}O$ isotope labeling combinations inside the filter [123]. Hereby, FTIR and 2DIR spectra of the all possible isotope-labeling combinations ($2^5 = 32$) were calculated of the amino acids which coordinate ions in the selectivity filter (Thr74, Thr75, Val76, Gly77, Tyr78). The filter without isotope labels was denoted 00000, a single labeled Gly77 00010 and so forth. To find the best labeling

FIGURE 2.5: Spectroscopy of model compounds. Experimental results of A) FTIR of K^+ binding to Valinomycin (blue without, green with K^+). B) Experimental 2DIR spectrum of the carbonyl vibrational spectrum of Valinomycin without (left) and with (right) K^+ ions (adapted from [123]).

FIGURE 2.6: Modeling of spectral differences between ion states in isotopomers of KcsA. Expected difference (1,3 - 2,4 state) A-B) 2DIR, and C) FTIR, K^+ binding spectra for different isotope label sequences in the selectivity filter. Isotope labeling shifts the spectral signatures of ion binding states away from the proteins background (around 1650 cm^{-1}) to a background free region (dotted box). Figure adapted from [123].

combination for discrimination of 1,3 and 2,4 states, difference spectra of the states were calculated for each labeling combination. The best sensitivity to discriminate K^+ ion states compared to the unlabeled case (00000) was found with labeling combinations Thr75-Val76-Gly77 (01110) and Val76-Tyr78 (00101) (figure 2.6 and [123]). As a conclusion, isotope labeling of i.e. Val76 and Tyr78 can in theory lead to unambiguous assignment of the spectroscopic signatures to the respective K^+ binding states in the selectivity filter. Furthermore, it could provide the necessary SNR and spectral separation required to detect cross-peaks between these states.

Experimental approach of isotope labeling and transient 2DIR spectroscopy

As demonstrated in 2.1.4 $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled amino acids Val76 and Tyr78 could maximize the spectroscopic difference between the 1,3 and 2,4 binding states. In order to achieve the highest signal to noise ratio in the absorption range of the isotope labeled amino acids ideally only amino acids in the filter should be isotope labeled, while all other amino acids of the same kind should remain unlabeled. A way of introducing an arbitrary sequence of isotope labels into the filter is via semi-synthesis of the channel

FIGURE 2.7: Schematics of combined site directed and uniform isotope labeling of KcsA. KcsA with an amber stop codon at position 78 is transcribed to mRNA by the T7 RNA Polymerase and translated to the protein KcsA in the ribosome. The CFE contains all 20 native tRNA synthetases, tRNAs and 19 non-labeled amino acids except valine (green). $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labeled Valine (pink circles) is recognized by the natural tRNA^{Val} and $\text{TyrRS}^{\text{Val}}$ and uniformly labels KcsA. $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Tyr- $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ (blue tRNA) supplied to the reaction competes with translation termination factors once the amber stop codon (blue UAG) is read by the ribosome. It inserts the labeled amino acid at this position while all other tyrosines remain not isotope labeled.

[128]. Here, the filter sequence is synthesized as a peptide with isotope labels at the desired positions and later fused with two expressed halves of the protein to yield the full length protein. This method has been applied to answer several questions about KcsA which require site specific labels [129–131] and the method was proposed as suitable tools also for site directed isotope labeling [132]. Recently, this methodology was used to introduce site directed labels into KcsA for 2DIR studies with great success [124]. However, at the time of the design of the experiments in 2013 only one laboratory was able to accomplish this highly complex methodology. As a result we sought out for alternative labeling strategies that might provide a similar effect with less elaborate experimental methods.

A site specific isotope label can be introduced at an arbitrary position of a protein by reassigning one of the chain-terminating triplet codons to be translated as an isotope labeled amino acid in a process called amber suppression [133]. For this, the least naturally prevalent codon called the "amber" stop-codon is recognized by a synthetic amber-tRNA (tRNA_{CUA}) designed to recognize the stop-codons DNA sequence ATG. This suppresses the amber stop codons original function: Instead of terminating translation, the amber suppression delivers the amino acid attached to the amber-tRNA by acylation to this specific point of the growing protein chain [133]. By charging the amber-tRNA with the isotope labeled amino acid (see figure 2.8) and introducing an amber stop codon to the DNA sequence coding the selectivity filter of KcsA this protocol allows for the precise delivery of the infrared label at the desired position (see figure 2.7).

To deliver Val76 and Tyr78 via this method requires *double* site specific labeling, which is highly sophisticated [134, 135]. However, *single* site specific isotope labeling of one amino acid coupled with uniform labeling of a second amino acid is possible with reasonable effort [136]. As a trade-off, the uniform label introduces additional background due to isotope labeled carbonyl groups in the protein which do not interact with potassium ions in the filter. Since KcsA contains 16 valines and 5 tyrosines

FIGURE 2.8: Aminoacylation of tRNA. The T7 RNA polymerase transcribes tRNA of a plasmid and is folded in the correct three dimensional shape. For chemical acylation (bottom) a shortened tRNA is ligated by T4 DNA ligase to the missing nucleotides chemically linked to an amino acid. Enzymatic acylation (top) uses the native tRNA synthetases (TyrRS) to bind an amino acid to its cognate full length tRNA.

it would be more desirable to site directly deliver valine, as it avoids 15 unwanted isotope labels outside of the filter instead of 4 in the case of uniformly labeled tyrosine. However, site directed delivery of valine has proven notoriously ineffective due to the large changes in the structure of the tRNA^{Val} necessary to create the amber version $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Val}}$ of it [137]. However, tRNA^{Tyr} were changed easily to recognize the amber codon [133] and shown to site specifically introduce an isotope labeled tyrosine with reasonable efficiency [136, 137]. As a trade-off between experimental feasibility and the required high amount of isotope labeled material for 2DIR spectroscopy uniform labeling of Val76 and site specific labeling of Tyr78 seemed most promising.

Steps of this process are shown figure 2.7 and require the *in vitro* transcription of $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Val}}$ [138], aminoacylated with $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labeled Tyrosine with the cognate enzyme Tyrosine Synthetase (TyrRS) [139–141] (see figure 2.8). The charged $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Tyr- $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ in a cell free expression system (CFE) can lead to the site specific incorporation of the labeled amino acid via amber suppression of an amber stop codon at position 78 of KcsA during the translation process. To achieve uniform labeling, $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled valine is supplemented to the CFE mix (see figure 2.7) [136, 142].

2.1.5 Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport

During the course of gathering evidence for this thesis it was shown that a direct-knock on S4 facilitates the ion transport [101, 124]. Analyzing 1300 permeation events in MD simulation showed, that direct coulombic repulsion of neighbouring K^+ ions within the filter leads to the almost diffusion limited throughput. The potential landscape and electromagnetic barriers between individual binding sites S1-4 faced by ions during permeation was not found to be as static as predicted from crystallography experiments but instead strongly modulated by the strong coulombic force of the ions knocking on the selectivity filter-bound ions [101].

In response, a hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport was developed to combine the existing hypothesis of snug-fit and direct coulombic knock-on with vibrationally modulated flexibility and structural plasticity of the filter:

1. Size and charge selectivity

FIGURE 2.9: Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport of KcsA. A) Selectivity filter shown with selected residues on the pore helix shown. The pore backbone amides are connected to the pore helix via a network of hydrogen bonds (adapted from [143]). B) The hypothesis assumes, that flexibility of the filters backbone carbonyl groups is modulated by direct coulombic knock-on of a K^+ ion entering at S4. Furthermore, the hydrogen bonds connections of the pore-helix to the filter allow small ion-induced differences in pore helix positioning to further modulate the flexibility of the backbone carbonyl groups. In the exemplified S1-3 state, "softness" of the Val76 and Y78 backbone carbonyl modulates the energy barriers between the 1-3 states ions and the next binding site towards the extracellular side of the pore. Concerted movement occurs when both energy barriers are low enough to allow transmission of the ions from 1-3 to 2-4 states. C) Hypothetical mode of action of vibrational ratchet across time. Snapshots of the overall potential across the filter pore faced by an ion in S3 site with ion knocking on S4 (see schematic below) are shown over the time of concerted movement (<10 ps) alongside the pore axis (x-axis). At 0ps the K^+ ion in S3 faces a steep potential wall. However, S2 fluctuations induced by a flexible V76 carbonyl modulate translate the potential wall alongside the pore (see 1ps and 2ps steps). At 3ps the ion has reached the binding site S2 and a more rigid V76 increases the potential barrier from moving backwards to S3 as indicated by a potential well at 6 Anstrom. thus, an interplay of knock-on, induce flexibility and structural rigidity after the movement could explain the ions movements.

2. Diffusion limited throughput

3. Flexibility and structural plasticity of the filter

Flexibility of the backbone carbonyl groups along side the pore seems to be of importance if electromagnetic barriers between binding sites are drastically modulated during conduction [101]. The literature points to many examples of flexibility within the selectivity filter: previous experiments have shown, that Val76 separating S2 and S3 exhibits significant flexibility. The Val76 residues pore-facing backbone carbonyl rotates regularly away from the filter ("Val76-kick") by rapidly changing the carbonyl dihedral angle. The frequency of kicks can be modulated by mutating the pore helix residue E71 [106]. Mutations of the pore helices E71 can modulate Val76 behaviour as the pore helix is bound via an intricate network of hydrogen bonds to the selectivity filters backbone amides (see figure 2.9 A) [106].

FIGURE 2.10: Vibrationally assisted ion transport hypothesis for ion binding to S4. The figure shows the proposed sequence of events during an ion hopping event and its link to flexibility modulation via the ions. The green line shows the cavity ions trajectory alongside the pore axis (y-axis) until binding to the filters site S4 via an intermediate "pre-S4" (dotted lines). The trajectory is plotted over the time of 20-60 ns (x-axis) until binding of the cavity ion to the S4-site is completed. The sequence of binding has been separated into four sections separated by vertical lines (ABCD). Each section shows a schematic inset of the hypothesized selectivity filter configuration and carbonyl flexibility (schematic with 1,2,3,4 denoting the individual binding sites and green circles denoting K^+ ions to respective sites, waters not shown). The secondary y-axis shows a measure of flexibility of the channel as indicated by the combined root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) of the K^+ ions, waters and channel carbonyl groups. A similar measure of flexibility following the same trajectory is the Val76 kick frequency. A Val76 kick is defined as a 180 degree rotation of the filters Val76 residue located between the binding sites 2 and 3. CM denotes the event of concerted movement from 1-3 to 2-4 configuration with the relevant time-scale being 10 ps. The hypothesized transitions are as follows: A) The selectivity filter is in the 1-3 state with K^+ (green circles) bound in the S1 and S3 positions, respectively. S2 and S4 are filled with water molecules (not shown). A third K^+ ion approaches the filter from the cavity. A K^+ ion from the cavity (A) comes close to S4 (B) and initiates concerted movement (CM). The RMSD of the channel is high due to the knock-on and V76 kicks frequently indicating a flexible boundary between S3 and S2. The outermost ion binds to presite 4 (green line on bottom dotted line) which increases the coulombic force on the ion bound in S3. (C) Concerted movement occurs as flexible carbonyls allow a smooth transition between individual binding sites while releasing the previously bound ion in S1 to the exterior of the channel. The cavity ion reached binding site S4 (top dotted line) After concerted movement the RMSD of the channel drops as knock-on subsides. The channel is more rigid which rectifies the movement.

FIGURE 2.11: Hypothesis of vibrationally assisted transport of KcsA. Ion conduction in KcsA is thought to require concerted movement (CM) from 1,3 to 2,4 states. Binding of K^+ to S4 softens the carbonyl groups between S3 & S2 as well as S1 and the outside of the filter, respectively as indicated movement of extracellular facing carbonyl groups adjacent to ion in schematic of selectivity filter (green). In plane binding Na^+ (yellow) or twice the charge in the same configuration of by K^+ rigidifies the filter (solid black lines carbonyls of schematic selectivity filter). As fluctuations are missing in a too rigid filter, transport is not possible compared to the more flexible filter in the presence of K^+ .

Compared to K^+ , the selectivity filter selects against both the 0.4 Å smaller Na^+ (size selectivity) as well as the double charged Ba^{2+} which has the same atomic radius as K^+ (charge selectivity) [144]. However, all three ions can bind to the selectivity filter with Barium and Sodium being found in 2,4 position as demonstrated with x-ray crystallography [84, 145]. This shows, that the binding sites need to be flexible, as otherwise the different ion sizes and charges would not be found in the selectivity filter experimentally. The original "snug-fit" model is seemingly contradicted by the relative spatial positions of the carbonyl oxygens that vary up to 1.0 Å due to thermal fluctuations [95, 98]. Thus, this hypothesis proposes that changes in the flexibility and structural plasticity of the filter are essential to both the size and charge selectivity as well as the diffusion limited throughput.

It assumes, that the knock-on of a K^+ from the internal cavity of KcsA to S4 "softens" the carbonyl groups towards the extracellular side of KcsA for the ions in the 1,3 configuration (see figure 2.11 K^+). The interplay of the carbonyls rigidity on one side and flexibility on the extracellular side of the coordinated K^+ could provide a natural directionality to the transport. Site fluctuations could temporarily lower the potential of the barrier between the two sites to allow for simple diffusion to the next site in one concerted movement (CM). The in-plane binding configuration of Na^+ (see figure 2.11 Na^+) abolishes the flexibility of the carbonyl groups as the binding force is too strong to allow further movement. In the case of Ba^{2+} the coordination is eightfold similarly to K^+ however the double charge within the same spatial arrangement attracts the negatively charged carbonyl groups much stronger. As a result, much lower flexibility of extracellular facing carbonyl groups is expected which could explain the experimentally confirmed blockage of KcsA by Ba^{2+} (see figure 2.11 Ba^{2+}). In both cases, the lack of fluctuations in the position of carbonyl groups does not provide the possibility for temporal reduction of the potential energy between sites. As a result, the transport of these ions is far from the diffusion limited rate of K^+ .

Together, this "vibrational ratchet" type movement combines all three aspects of size and charge selectivity, diffusion limited throughput and the flexibility and structural plasticity of the filter.

2.1.6 Potential signatures of vibrationally assisted ion transport

Mutants of KcsA to sample signatures of vibrationally assisted ion transport

A literature search of mutants of KcsA shows they display a wide range of functional behavior summarized in table 2.12. The mutants cover different ion-binding states, throughput and selectivity rates paired with existing high resolution crystallography structures. Thus, mutants are ideal tools to apply the same methods of 1DIR, 2DIR and doorway mode analysis: instead of "inert" spectral probes, mutants introduce local perturbations of the selectivity filter or the surrounding pore helices by exchanging amino acids. They change amongst others the electrostatic environment of the filters surrounding, break or form hydrogen network between the filter and the pore helices and sometimes completely abolish binding sites. The spectral readout can thus be used to link the changes in spectral characteristic to the change in functional behavior (e.g. selectivity) as determined by highly sensitive methods (e.g. electrophysiology). Up to date very little data is available of the characterization of mutant KcsA with 1DIR spectroscopy posing it a high potential avenue for elucidating the structural plasticity of the filter with regards to functionally relevant mutations.

The mutants included in the literature search display a wide range of behavior that might be interesting with regards to the hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport (see table 2.12): **Binding sites:** Mutants can modulate the amount of binding sites within the filter between 4 and 2 sites. Furthermore, some lock 1-3 or 2-4 binding sites further locking in functionally relevant conductive states. What are the changes in spectral signatures of individual binding sites if they are abolish via a mutant? **Selectivity:** Mutants can render the filter completely nonselective. What spectral characteristics change if a filter is nonselective and is there a unifying pattern hinting to changes in vibrationally induced plasticity/rigidity in line with the hypothesis of vibrationally assisted ion transport? **Collapse of filter:** Low K^+ concentrations usually collapse the filter (wt) but many mutants actually keep the filter open hinting to an increase of rigidity of the filter. Is this lack of flexibility apparent in spectral signatures of the filter or its surrounding helices? **Conductance:** Mutants show both strongly reduced and even accelerated conductance. Can equilibrium IR show what spectral characteristics might be linked to high or low conducting channels? **Conductance of Na^+ in low K^+ :** The wild type does not transport Na^+ in the absence of K^+ as the filter is collapsed. Can spectroscopy show the spectral signatures of Na^+ conductance in mutants that have an open configuration in low K^+ ?

The characterization of these mutants using IR spectroscopy might yield interesting insights in many hallmark-features of selectivity, conductance and rigidity of the filter.

The structural properties of some of these channels are shown in 2.13. The structures show how the important factors of conductance, selectivity, gating modes (temporal dynamics of closed-to-open transition) or rectification (meaning uni-directionality of ion current) might be impacted by the changes in amino acids underlying these mutants. The changes are mostly located within the vicinity of the selectivity filter e.g. on the pore helix or in the case of T75C directly at the selectivity filter. Changes include removing a binding site, electrostatic (e.g. H-bond) or VDW-interaction with the backbone carbonyl groups of the filter. Altogether, these mutants are perfectly suitable for introducing localized perturbations in the relevant structural elements that enables testing hypothesis on spectral signatures of binding sites. They might

Binding Sites	Name	Selectivity	Sel filter collapse in low (3mM) K+	P(Na/K)	Conductance	Na+ conductance in 0mM K+	Remarks
4	KcsA	K+ selective in ≥20mM K+	collapsed	≈0.0001	50-108ps K ⁺	No	Highest selectivity
	KcsA D- Ala77		open	n.d.	≥100ps K ⁺	Yes	Anomalous mole fraction effect
	MthK		open	0.017	220ps K ⁺	Yes (5ps)	Anomalous mole fraction effect
	NaK2K		open	0.04	120ps K ⁺	Yes (10ps)	Anomalous mole fraction effect
2 (E71Q) - 4(E71A/I)	KcsA_ M96V	nonselective	n.d.	≈1	29-31ps Na ⁺ /K ⁺ [9]	No	Quickly collapsing selectivity filter
	KcsA E71 A/Q/I	K+ selective in ≥20mM K ⁺	open	E71A:0.03 to 0.14 [6]	variable	n.d.	E71A: Unordered selectivity filter [10]
3	KcsA_ T75C	Reduced selectivity	collapsed	n.d.	25ps K ⁺	No	Only binding sites 1-3
	NaK2K _T63A		open	≈1	100ps Na ⁺ /K ⁺	n.d.	Only binding sites 1-3
	MthK_ T59A		open	≈1	150ps Na ⁺ /K ⁺	n.d.	Only binding sites 1-3
	NaK2C NG-D		open	≈1	110ps Na ⁺ /K ⁺	n.d.	Only binding sites 2-4
2	NaK	Non-selective	open	≈1	35ps Na ⁺ /K ⁺	n.d.	Only binding sites 3-4

FIGURE 2.12: Characteristics of Mutant KcsA channels. This table shows the properties of different KcsA channel mutants with respect to experimentally confirmed ion binding sites in the selectivity filter, selectivity, whether the selectivity filter collapses in low-ion conditions and the level of selectivity as indicated by the probability of transmitting a Na⁺ over a K⁺ denoted P(Na/K). Furthermore, the Conductance in pS is given and if Na⁺ is conducted in the absence of K⁺. The literature review shows, that mutants display a high variability in binding site occupation with different types of binding sites occupied and different levels of selectivity and throughput associated. References: [130, 146] (KcsA D-Ala77), [97] (MthK, NaK2K, NaK2K_T63A, MthK_T59A, NaK2CNG-D, NaK), [87] (KcsA_M96V), [106, 147] (KcsA_E71A/Q/I), [148] (KcsA_T75C).

FIGURE 2.13: Structural properties of selected mutant channels. *KcsA_T75C* does not possess a carbonyl at binding site S4 which abolishes knock-on to the channel [148]. *KcsA_E71A/Q/I* mutants are located on the pore helix. The side-chain and the backbone carbonyl form hydrogen bonds to the filters residues Y78 and V76, respectively. Mutations were shown to display different gating modes in electrophysiology which hint to modulations in flexibility of the channel with inversed rectification of channel current. Furthermore, the V76 was shown to rotate very frequently in MD simulations [106, 147]. *KcsA_M96V* is in direct contact with the selectivity filters V76. Mutations lock the channel similar to the collapsed state of the wild type [87].

prove useful models to investigate the changes in structural plasticity of the filter and its surrounding.

2.2 Materials and Methods

2.2.1 Isotope labeling of Amino acids

The $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling of Amino acids followed methods outlined by Maracek *et al.* [149]. The protocol was adapted to the specific needs of amino acids without Fluorenylmethyloxycarbonyl chloride (Fmoc) protection group. The main difference to Fmoc-amino acids was, that much less Dioxane was needed to bring unprotected amino acids into solution. An overview of the process is shown in figure 2.14.

$^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling of L-Tyrosine

L-Tyrosine-1- ^{13}C (1 g, 5.49 mmol, Cambridge Isotope) was dried for 3 h in an evacuated glass setup prior to dissolving in 26 mL Dioxane (Sigma) and 2.5 mL H_2^{18}O (97%, Shanghai Engineering Research Center of Stable Isotope). The solution was slowly brought to 100 mM HCl 500 μL of dry Acetylchloride (Sigma) which lead to a clear solution with pH of ≈ 1 . After boiling with reflux under N_2 for 16 h the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* in a microdistille and the solid dried for a further 6 h. Analysis by mass spectroscopy showed an ^{18}O content of about 52%. The crude material was dissolved in 26 ml Dioxane and 2.4 mL H_2^{18}O . Only 160 μL Acetylchloride was needed to acidify the solution and bring Tyrosine in solution since the aminoacid was already protonated from the first step. After 16 h of boiling the solvent was evaporated until a white powder was obtained. The Aminoacid was neutralized by sonication in 30 mL of 3 M Citric Acid (pH 5.7, KOH) at 0 °C, recovered by filtering through a WhatmanTM filter and finally recrystallized and washed with icecold 10 mM Citric Acid (pH 5.7, KOH). The yield of the dry product was 81% (0.81 g) and the ^{18}O enrichment was approximately 92.5% as determined by FTIR and ESI-MS (see below).

$^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling of L-Valine

L-Valine-1- ^{13}C (1 g, 8.46 mM, Cambridge Isotope) was dissolved in 24 mL Dioxane, 2.4 mL of recovered H_2^{18}O from the labeling of L-Tyrosine and acidified with 750 μL Acetylchloride until soluble. The solution was boiled for 20 h, dried for several hours and boiled again in 24 ml solution with 2.5 mL fresh H_2^{18}O (without adding Acetylchloride) for 20 h. ^{18}O enrichments were 72.5% and 80.5% for the first and second round, respectively. Valine was neutralized with NaHCO_3 in 8 mL H_2O and recrystallized by adding 40 times the volume of EtOH. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ice cold 90% EtOH and dried. The yield was 73% of the starting material.

FTIR of Aminoacids

Aminoacids were resuspended in D_2O and 10 M NaOD was added until the amino acids went to solution at high concentrations ($>10 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, pH >10). The spectra were acquired on a NicoletTMiSTM10 FT-IR Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) by integrating 32 scans from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Background scans of buffer were subtracted to yield the final spectrum. Results are presented in figure 2.17.

FIGURE 2.14: Isotope labeling of amino acids by acid hydrolysis. a) First, the ^{13}C -labeled amino acid is filled in to a pear shaped flask. To remove any atmospheric water, the setup is first evacuated and then dried by heating with a Bunsenburner and hot water in the Liebig condenser. Afterwards, the setup is flushed and evacuated three times with N_2 and a slow flow of N_2 via a bubbler filled with mineral oil is allowed to stabilize for at least 30 min to create a stable overpressure in the system. Via a glass syringe with teflon piston water free 1,4-Dioxan and H_2^{18}O is added to the amino acid. The mixture is heated to boiling temperature and water-free Acetylchloride is added until the amino acid solubilizes and the pH drops to approx. 1. The mixture is boiled and stirred for many hours under reflux via the now cold Liebig condenser and slight N_2 overpressure. c) After cooling down the reaction mixture the Liebig condenser is quickly switched with a microdistill and immediately evacuated. The acidic Dioxan- H_2^{18}O -mixture is evaporated *in vacuo* and captured in a coldtrap. The process is repeated once more with fresh H_2^{18}O to increase the enrichment of ^{18}O in the carbonyl group of the amino acid. d) After the second distillation step, the dry $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled amino acid is neutralized in a flask under N_2 atmosphere. e) after washing the amino acid with ice cold buffer the product is dried and f) the yield determined by weighing the resulting powder.

TABLE 2.1: DH medium stock ^{a, b}

Chemical	Concentration	Chemical	Concentration
(NH ₄)SO ₄	1 g L ⁻¹	Glutamic acid	40 mg L ⁻¹
KH ₂ PO ₄	4.5 g L ⁻¹	Glutamine	40 mg L ⁻¹
K ₂ HPO ₄	10.5 g L ⁻¹	Histidine	40 mg L ⁻¹
NaCitrate-2H ₂ O	0.5 g L ⁻¹	Isoleucine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Glycerol	5 g L ⁻¹	Leucine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Adenine	0.5 g L ⁻¹	Lysine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Guanosine	0.5 g L ⁻¹	Phenylalanine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Thymine	0.5 g L ⁻¹	Proline	40 mg L ⁻¹
Uracil	0.5 g L ⁻¹	Serine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Alanine	40 mg L ⁻¹	Threonine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Arginine	40 mg L ⁻¹	Tryptophan	40 mg L ⁻¹
Asparagine	40 mg L ⁻¹	Methionine	40 mg L ⁻¹
Aspartatic Acid	40 mg L ⁻¹	<i>Tyrosine</i> ^c	40 mg L ⁻¹
Cysteine	40 mg L ⁻¹	<i>Valine</i> ^c	40 mg L ⁻¹

^aAutoclave after all supplements are added. ^bAll Aminoacids used should be L-enantiomers. ^cOmit Aminoacids in case they are to be isotope labeled.

Mass spectrometry of Aminoacids and KcsA

Samples of dried Aminoacids were dissolved in 30 % 2,2,2-Trifluorethanol (Sigma), 20 % Acetonitrile (Sigma) und 5 % formic acid (Sigma) and measured by Electron Ionization - Mass spectrometry on an LTQ Orbitrap Velos Pro (Thermo Scientific). Results are presented in figure 2.16 and 2.19.

2.2.2 Heterologous expression and purification of KcsA

Expression of KcsA

Full length KcsA was tagged by six histidine and added after Met1. The expression vector pRSF1 (Merck) (for sequence see 5.1.2) was used for cloning and expression. The fully translated protein contained 116 amino acids in each monomer and a calculated MW of 18,637.6 Da. The plasmid was transformed into E.coli BL21(DE3) by incubating 100 μ L freshly thawed competent cells for 10 min on ice with 100 ng of plasmid. The cells were heat shocked for 45 s at 42 °C, cooled on ice for 2 min and resuspended in 1 mL of prewarmed LB medium. The bacteria were grown for at least 1 h at 37 °C while shaking at 200 RPM, shortly spun down in a tabletop microcentrifuge for 3 min at 3000 G, the supernatant discarded to 100 μ L and all cells plated on LB-plate which contained the appropriate antibiotic. The plates were incubated over night at 37 °C and a single colony from it used to grow to high densities in 5 mL LB medium. 1 mL of this starter culture was used to inoculate 1 L prewarmed LB medium supplied with the antibiotic Kanamycin at 50 μ g mL⁻¹. Upon reaching an o.D. of 0.8 the transcription was induced with 0.8 mM IPTG for 6 h at 37 °C in baffled flasks while shaking at 130 RPM. Bacteria were harvested by centrifugation at 4000 G, weighed and frozen at -20 °C. To analyze the success of the expression 1 mL samples were taken just before induction and harvest, brought to an o.D. of 10 and diluted with 2x SDS sample buffer to a final concentration of 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 6.8, 2 % SDS, 10 % glycerol, 1 % β -mercaptoethanol, 12.5 mM EDTA and 0.02 % bromphenol blue. The samples were cooked for 10 min at 95 °C and stored until use at 4 °C no longer than 24 h.

Single amino acid point mutations were introduced to the above wildtype construct following the QuickChange protocol for site-directed mutagenesis (Quiagen). In short, primers were designed to contain the desired sequence for replacing amino acids (e.g. E71A) and melting temperature according to the QuickChange user manual (www.Agilent.com). After plating of the cells, single colonies were sequenced to confirm successful amino acid exchange and positive colonies were kept for future use as Glycerol stocks at -80°C . Expression of mutant constructs followed the expression protocol for wild type KcsA detailed above.

Expression of uniformly L-Valine-1- $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ and L-Tyrosine-1- $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled KcsA

A single over night colony of E.coli BL21(DE3) transformed with wildtype KcsA was used to grow an overnight culture in LB medium. 980 mL of LB were inoculated with 20 ml preculture and grown at 37°C to an o.D. of 1.2. The cells were spun down at RT at 4000 G and resuspended in 1 L prewarmed (37°C) defined DH medium (see table 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3) supplied with all, except the isotope labeled amino acids (see table 2.1). Cells were allowed to grow in the new medium for 10 min at 37°C until 40 mg of the isotope labeled amino acids (i.e. L-Valine-1- $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ and L-Tyrosine-1- $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$) were added per litre of expression medium. After another 20 min of growth, the culture was induced with 1 mM IPTG for 6 h at 37°C . Cells were harvested at 6000 g for 15 min at 4°C and the pellet was weighed and frozen at -20°C .

TABLE 2.2: Trace metal mix

Chemical	Stock	Volume	MW	Concentration
$\text{FeCl}_3-6\text{H}_3\text{O}^{\text{a}}$	0.1 M	50 mL	270.30	50 μM
CaCl_2	1 M	2 mL	93.0	20 μM
$\text{MnCl}_3-4\text{H}_3\text{O}$	1 M	1 mL	197.91	10 μM
$\text{ZnSO}_4-7\text{H}_3\text{O}$	1 M	1 mL	287.56	10 μM
$\text{CoCl}_2-6\text{H}_3\text{O}$	0.2 M	1 mL	237.95	2 μM
$\text{CuCl}_2-2\text{H}_3\text{O}$	0.1 M	2 mL	170.486	2 μM
$\text{NiCl}_2-6\text{H}_3\text{O}$	0.2 M	1 mL	237.72	2 μM
$\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4-5\text{H}_3\text{O}$	0.1 M	2 mL	241.98	2 μM
$\text{Na}_2\text{SeO}_3-5\text{H}_3\text{O}$	0.1 M	2 mL	263.03	2 μM
H_3BO_3	0.1 M	2 mL	61.83	2 μM

^adissolved in 0.1 M HCl, 100 fold dilution of conc. HCl

Purification and characterization of His-tagged KcsA

The bacterial pellet was re-suspended in 30 mL buffer A (50 mM sodium phosphate, pH 8.0, 100 mM NaCl, 50 mM KCl) per gram of cells in the presence of 0.2 mM protease inhibitor PMSF. The solution was enzymatically lysed by 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ Lysozyme (Sigma) for 30 min at 4°C . Then, the cells were lysed by sonication at 4°C until the

TABLE 2.3: DH growth medium

Chemical	final amount
DH medium stock	1 L
Thiamine	2 mg L^{-1}
Kanamycin	50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
1 M $\text{MgSO}_4-7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1 mL L^{-1}
Trace element mix	1.7 mL L^{-1}
each $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ Aminoacid	40 mg L^{-1}

solution appeared darker and much less viscous, which indicated the success of the lysis. The protein was solubilized with 20 mM DDM (Avanti) by slowly stirring the solution at 4 °C for 1 h. After centrifugation at 4 °C for 20 min at 30 000 G the supernatant contained the solubilized protein. KcsA was bound to Co²⁺ affinity resin (Thermo) while slowly stirring for 1 h at 4 °C in 20 mM imidazole. The slurry was loaded on a column (Econo-Pack Chromatography column, Biorad) and washed with 20 mM imidazole and 1 mM DDM in buffer A until the optical absorbance at 280 nm dropped to below 0.01. The protein was eluted in 1 mL fraction with 400 mM imidazole and 1 mM DDM in buffer A.

During the purification, samples of individual steps were taken, brought to 1xSDS-sample buffer and boiled for 10 min at 95 °C and stored until use at 4 °C no longer than 24 h. The sample amount taken at each step was adjusted to the volume used for resuspending the bacteria, to allow for quantitative comparison between the individual steps. To test proper folding of KcsA, samples were diluted in 2x native SDS-page sample buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 6.8, 10 % glycerol and 0.02 % bromophenol blue) and loaded to the gel without boiling. Samples of the expression and purification were loaded on a 16 % SDS-Page (40 µg per lane) and run for 50 min at 200 V in 1x SDS-running buffer (25 mM Tris base, 192 mM glycine, 0.1 % SDS). The SDS of the gel was removed by shortly boiling and subsequently agitating it for 10 min in 50 % ethanol and 10 % acetic acid. The gel was transferred to 5 % ethanol and 7.5 % acetic acid and 200 µL of a 0.25 % Coomassie brilliant blue R250 in 95 % stock in ethanol was added. The gel was shortly brought to boiling in a microwave and was agitated until bands started to appear. For documentation, the gels were left over night in the staining solution and excess stain was removed by boiling in dH₂O.

By comparing boiled and native samples on SDS gel the correct folding of KcsA in buffer B was quantified by densitometry. The amount of protein in the 75 and 18 kDa band of tetrameric and monomeric KcsA, respectively, allowed to determine the fraction of correctly folded KcsA since tetrameric KcsA is stable on SDS-gels. In addition, KcsA samples were diluted in buffer B and the circular dichroism determined on a Chirascan Plus CD spectrometer (Applied Photophysics). Size-exclusion chromatography was run on an Äkta Fast protein liquid chromatography system (GE) using a Superdex 200 10/300 GL column (GE) in buffer B supplied with 0.3 mM DDM.

To measure protein samples of KcsA in MALDI-TOF all lipids were removed by precipitating and washing the protein twice in MeOH. Dried protein samples were then measured on an ABI 4800 MALDI TOF/TOF (ABSCIEX). The deconvolution was performed in the Thermo Scientific™ Protein Deconvolution software. Results are presented in figure 2.18.

2.2.3 FTIR of KcsA

Desalting and deuteration of KcsA for FTIR

Purified KcsA was dialysed extensively against buffer B (150 mM NaCl, 1 mM DDM, 10 mM HEPES, pH 7.5) to remove potassium ions from the solution. Due to the high CMC of DDM is only very slowly lost during the dialysis and does not have to be supplemented to the buffer. The desalted KcsA was less stable at higher temperatures and thus kept at 4 °C as much as possible. H₂O absorption in the infrared regime overlaps with the amide-I vibration of proteins. Thus, the water was exchanged to D₂O by multiple concentration-dilution cycles with buffer B prepared in D₂O. For this purpose the buffer was first prepared as a 50x stock solution in H₂O, dried in a Speedvac vacuum concentrator (Eppendorf) and resuspended in D₂O. KcsA was concentrated to approx. 1 mg mL⁻¹ by centrifugation at 4 °C in a Microsep™ Advance

Centrifugal Device (Pall) with a modified polyethersulfone and MWCO of 10 kDa. Smaller volumes were concentrated with Amicon centrifugal devices (Millipore). The concentration device was sealed when possible with Parafilm to avoid contamination with atmospheric H₂O. The concentrated protein was diluted 5-fold with deuterated buffer B (150 mM NaCl, 1 mM DDM, 10 mM HEPES, pD 7.9) and the cycle repeated until the flow through was transparent at 3400 cm⁻¹ as determined by FTIR. To achieve high deuteration (>99%), the freshly diluted protein was incubated at 37 °C for up to 30 min to allow for proper deuteration of buried parts of the protein. The final concentration of KcsA was 7-8 mg mL⁻¹, frozen in liquid N₂ and stored at -80 °C after precipitates were removed by centrifugation for 20 min at 13 000 G from the concentrated protein. Potassium salts, were added to the sample by dialysing against a modified deuterated buffer B (150 mM KCl, 1 mM DDM, 10 mM HEPES, pD 7.9).

FTIR spectroscopy of KcsA

2.5 µL of concentrated, desalted and deuterated KcsA at 8 mg mL⁻¹ was sandwiched between CaF₂ windows (CeNing Optics) which were separated by a PTFE spacer with a thickness of 50 µm. Spectra were acquired on a Nicolet 380 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) at room temperature by averaging 2048 times at 1 cm⁻¹ resolution. The spectrometer was flushed with dried air prior and during the experiment. Spectra of the buffer allowed to subtract the background and the contribution of remaining H₂O and impurities from the spectrum of KcsA. The differences in ion binding were extracted by subtracting background corrected spectra of high and low K⁺ conditions.

2DIR spectroscopy of KcsA

Absolute value 2D IR spectra of fully deuterated samples at concentrations of 8 mg mL⁻¹ were acquired using a 2D IR spectrometer, as described in [150]. Briefly, ultrashort pulses of 800 nm light from a regenerative amplifier (Spitfire, Spectra Physics) were used to generate light at 6 µm. This was then split into 4 pulses, which could be delayed independently. The first three pulses were used to generate the nonlinear 2D IR signal, which was overlapped with the fourth, reference pulse, and dispersed onto a detector to generate the detection frequency axis, while the delay between the first two pulses was scanned in 4fs steps, and subsequently Fourier-transformed to generate the excitation frequency axis. The delay between the second and third pulses was kept constant at 150 fs.

2.2.4 tRNA transcription and aminoacylation

T7RNA polymerase expression and purification

N-terminal His-tagged T7 RNA polymerase from pAR1219 [151] was expressed from plasmid pPROEX HT-b (InVitrogen) in BL21(DE3) cells. 5 mL of saturated o.N. preculture were diluted to each liter of LB Medium (2 x 1 L total), grown to an o.D. of 0.5 and induced with 1 mM IPTG for 4 h at 37 °C. Cells were harvested at 6000 G for 15 min at 4 °C and the pellet was weighed and frozen at -20 °C. The pellet was resuspended in 10 mL Lysis buffer (20 mM Tris/Cl pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 5 mM Imidazole, 1 mM β-MeSH) per litre culture, lysed by sonication and the cleared lysate was applied to a 2 x 5 mL Ni-NTA columns (GE). After washing with washing buffer (20 mM Na-Phosphate pH 7.7, 500 mM NaCl, 5 mM Imidazole, 1 mM β-MeSH) the column the protein was eluted with 20 mM Na-Phosphate pH 7.7, 300 mM NaCl,

250 mM Imidazole, 1 mM β -MeSH) and the fractions checked on an SDS-Gel. Fractions containing T7-Polymerase were pooled, extensively dialysed to storage buffer (20 mM Na-Phosphate pH 7.7, 100 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM DTT) and stored in at -20°C after dialysing against storage buffer with 55 % Glycerol.

Preparation of the template DNA

The template DNA of the amber-tRNA coding plasmid PSP64-tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr} was a generous gift by M. Gerrits. Directly following the T7 promotor the tRNA-tTyr (su+3) gene is located and terminated with a BstNI cleavage site (see DNA sequence section 5.1.1). The RNA sequence of the transcribed suppressor tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr} contains an anticodon AUC matching the amber stop codon UAG on the transcribed mRNA (see RNA sequence section 5.1.1). Large amounts of high quality template DNA had to be generated routinely by anion exchange columns using Maxiprep kits (Quiagen). The plasmid was linearized by digestion with 0.1 U of BstNI (NEB) per μg of plasmid at 60°C for 16 h. Enzymes were removed by Phenol/Chloroform/Isoamylalkohol (PCI, Sigma) extraction and the DNA precipitated and stored at -20°C in water.

In vitro transcription of Tyrosine suppressor tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr}

In vitro transcription reactions contained 42 mM MgCl_2 , 10 mM GMP, 8 mM ATP, GTP, CTP and TTP (Sigma), respectively, 0.01 % Triton X-100 (Sigma), $0.02 \text{ U } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ RNase Inhibitor (Thermo), 0.002 U mL^{-1} RNase free Phosphatase, $0.04 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ acetylated BSA (Thermo), 150 nM template DNA and $10 \text{ U } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ T7 RNA polymerase and were incubated for 3 h at 41°C . Then, template DNA was digested with 0.5 U mL^{-1} RNase free DNase (Roche) for an additional 30 min. The reaction was stopped by adding 0.5 M EDTA pH 8.0 to 50 mM until the solution went clear. Then the polymerase and residual DNA was removed by PCI, the mixture desalted with a PD-10 column (GE), the tRNA precipitated over night at -20°C in EtOH and stored as a pellet or in H_2O . The resulting tRNA was analyzed on by denaturing gel electrophoresis.

Analysis of tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr} integrity by denaturing gel electrophoresis

For single nucleotide resolution gel electrophoresis denaturing acidic gels were poured and run at high temperature to keep the tRNA from folding. Typically, 15 mL gel solution consisted of 12 % Acrylamide (from 40 % Acrylamide/Bis Solution, 19:1, Biorad), 1 x TBE, 8 M Urea and after degassing the solution polymerization was started with 10 μL TEMED and 100 μL of 10 % APS and poured between two glass plates with a 1 mm spacer. Samples were dissolved in 1 x RNA sample buffer (1 x TBE, 8 M Urea, 0.01 % Bromphenolblue, 0.01 % Xylencyanol), boiled for 5 min at 95°C . The samples had to be carefully loaded on the gel with a thin pipette tip because a focusing gel analogous to protein gels is not possible in this method. The samples were run in 1 x TBE at 35 W for 8 min to quickly heat up the gel and then at 22 W for 4.3 h to ensure a high temperature ($>60^{\circ}\text{C}$) during the gel run. The gel was carefully transferred to a plastic vessel and stained in 1 x TBE and 1 x SYBR Safe stain (Invitrogen) and bands imaged under blue light.

Folding and repair of tRNAs

For folding the transcribed tRNA it was resuspended in folding buffer (15 mM HEPES pH 7.8, 10 mM MgCl_2), heated to 75°C for 4 min, quickly transferred to 65°C and

cooled to RT over the course of 20 min. The acceptor arm of the folded tRNA was repaired if necessary by incubation of 20 μ M tRNA in TI-Buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 7.6, 70 mM KCH₃COO, 30 mM NH₄Cl, 0.1 mM EDTA pH 8.0, 10 mM DTT, 12 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM nucleotide mix (ATP, CTP, GTP, TTP), 30 mM PEP (Sigma), 10 mM ACP (Sigma), 0.02 % NaN₃ (Sigma), 25 μ g mL⁻¹ Pyruvatkinase (Roche), 25 U mL⁻¹) for 1 h at 41 °C. The tRNA was purified by PCI and precipitated in EtOH, analysed by gel electrophoresis and stored at -20 °C.

Purification of tRNA synthetases

The plasmids coding for His-tagged glycyl-tRNA synthetase GlyRS, TyrRS, ValRS and ThrRS were a gracious gift of T. Ueda and purification for all synthetases followed a protocol described in by Shimizu *et al.* [152]. In short BL21(DE3) cells were transformed with each vector and grown to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.8 in 2L LB medium. Induction was carried out for 4 h at 37 °C in the presence of 0.1 mM IPTG. Cells were harvested by centrifugation at 6000 g for 15 min at 4 °C and the pellet weighed and frozen at -20 °C. The cells were resuspended in buffer A (50 mM (HEPES)-KOH, pH 7.6, 1 M NH₄Cl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 0.3 mg mL⁻¹ lysozyme (Sigma), 0.1 % Triton X-100, 0.2 mM PMSF, and 7 mM mM β -MeSH) and lysed by sonication. Centrifugation for 20 min at 16,000 g at 4 °C removed cell debris and the supernatant was loaded on 2 x 5 mL Ni²⁺ HisTrap FF Crude chelating columns (GE). The column was washed with buffer A with additional 25 mM Imidazole and the protein was eluted with buffer B (Buffer A + 400 mM) Imidazole. The fractions were analyzed on an SDS-PAGE, fractions containing the synthetase pooled and dialysed for 3h at 4 °C twice against buffer HT (50 mM (HEPES)-KOH, pH 7.6, 100 mM KCl, 10 mM MgCl₂ and 7 mM mM β -MeSH) and once against storage buffer (50 mM (HEPES)-KOH, pH 7.6, 100 mM KCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 30 % glycerol and 7 mM mM β -MeSH frozen in small aliquots at -80 °C.

Preparation of Tyr-tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr}

The acetylation reaction was adapted from [141] and consisted of 20 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM KCl, 5 mM ATP, 5 mM DTT, 30 μ M tRNA_{CUA}^{Tyr}, 5 μ M TyrRS and 1 mM of L-Tyrosine with or without the 1-¹³C¹⁸O label. Reactions were carried out for 30 min at 37 °C and stopped by adding 1/50 volume of 12.4 M acetic acid and 3 M ammonium acetate.

Analysis of acetylated tRNA by acid gel electrophoresis

The pellet of acetylated tRNA was dissolved in 10 mM Na-Acetate pH 4.5 and mixed with equal volume of 2 x loading buffer (0.1 M NaAc pH 4.5, 8 M Urea, 0.01 % Bromphenolblue, 0.01 % Xylencyanol) and kept on 4 °C before loading. The gel consisted of a 6.5 % Acrylamide (from 40 % Acrylamide/Bis Solution, 19:1, Biorad), 8 M Urea, 0.1 M NaAc pH 4.5, 8 M Urea, 0.8 % APS (10 %) and 0.04 % TEMED. The gel was placed at 4 °C and run at 170 V over night for 14 h. The gel was carefully transferred to a plastic vessel, stained in 0.1 M NaAc pH 4.5 and 1 x SYBR Safe stain (Invitrogen) and bands imaged under blue light.

2.2.5 Cell free expression of KcsA

Cell free expression (CFE) followed a detailed protocol by Schwarz *et al.* [142]. The expression itself takes place in a reaction mix (RM) where all components for transcription and translation are localized. The feed mix (FM) is separated from the RM by a dialysis membrane which allows only metabolic educts of the reaction to diffuse to the RM. As recommended, the expression of wildtype KcsA was first optimized by screening K^+ concentration in analytical scale and precipitate-based cell-free expression (P-CF). In the absence of supplied detergents the expressed membrane proteins (MP) precipitates and was purified and quantified by centrifugation. Next, analytical scale screens of different detergents were used to optimize the detergent-based cell-free expression (D-CF), where MPs are directly inserted into detergent micelles in the solution. The volume of one analytical reaction consisted of 500 μL FM and 65 μL RM and were carried out in a custom made Plexiglas reaction container. The RM was placed into a plexiglas tube sealed at the bottom by a dialysis membrane with a 10 kDa molecular weight cutoff (MWCO, Spectrum) which was washed extensively by boiling it twice in distilled water. This device was then placed in the cavity of a 24 well plate which held the FM, incubated at 20 °C and stirred at 250 RPM for 16 h. Preparative scale CFE consisted of 17 mL FM and 1 mL RM and were carried out in a partially self made slide-A-lyzer setup. The RM was filled into a extensively washed commercially available Slide-A-lyzer dialysis cassettes (Pierce) which was placed in a custom made plexiglas container holding the FM. The reaction was incubated for 16 h at 20 °C while stirring at 200 RPM.

The optimized reaction consisted of a final concentration of 230 mM K^+ and 16 mM Mg_2^+ summed over all chemicals in the mix. Note, that i.e. Nucleotides are supplied as K^+ salts and thus contribute to the overall K^+ concentration. The final concentration for P-CF of all chemicals was 0.05 % NaN_3 , 2 % PEG 8000, 70 mM KOAc, 11 mM $\text{Mg}(\text{OAc})_2$, 100 mM HEPES buffer, 1x Complete mix (Roche), 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ Folinic acid (Roche), 2 mM DTT, 1 mM NTP mix, 20 mM PEP, 20 mM AcP, 4 mM amino acid mix, 1 mM RCWMDE and 35 % S30 Buffer for the feeding and Reaction mix (see [142] for details on amino acid mix, RCWMDE and S30 Buffer). The RM consisted of additionally 40 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ PK (Roche), 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ tRNA, 6 U μL^{-1} T7RNAP, 0.3 U μL^{-1} RNAGuard (GE), 15 ng μL^{-1} DNA and 35 % S30 extract (Gift by K. Djinovic).

For D-CF the detergent DDM was added to 0.1 mM. To test for amber suppression instead of wildtype KcsA a plasmid carrying an amber stop mutation at the desired position in the selectivity filter was supplied to the RM. In addition aminoacylated tRNA was added to the mix to a concentration of up to 10 mM depending on the aminoacylation efficiency as determined previously by acid gel electrophoresis.

After the reaction the RM was centrifuged for 20 min at 16.000 g and 4 °C to separate the soluble fraction of MPs from the insoluble (precipitated) MPs. The protein content in each fraction was analyzed on an SDS-Page and the yield quantified photometrically by comparison to weight standards (Lysozyme and BSA).

Quantification of amber suppression in CFE of KcsA by ^{14}C -Tyrosine and ^3H labeling

The protocol for quantification of the correct suppression product was adapted from Yabuki *et al.* [136]. CFE and aminoacylation were carried out as described above with some modifications: Only the RM of the CFE was prepared in this experiment, since continuous feeding was not possible due to experiment design (see section 2.4.1). Furthermore, ^{14}C -Tyrosine with 1707 CPM pmol^{-1} was acetylated to $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ in a

separate reaction as described above. The tube with the precipitated ^{14}C -Tyrosine-tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ was used to as the reaction vessel and the pellet resuspended directly in the prepared RM. The total protein amount of the CFE was measured by supplementing ^3H -alanine to the reaction with plasmid pRsF1-KcsAFL. During the preparation of 60 μL RM as described above, 0.548 mM unlabeled alanine was added to a special amino acid mixture lacking only alanine of all 20 amino acids. Then 1.85 μM of ^3H -alanine from a 13.4 μM stock solution with 1 mCi mL^{-1} (Perkin Elmer) was added to yield a detectable amount of ^3H signal. This reaction was incubated at 37°C for 60 min and 3.5 μL samples were taken at 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, 45, and 60 min. The samples were pipetted on small discs of Whatman paper, precipitated with 5% trichloric acid (TCA) and used for scintillation counting (Quantalus, Perkin Elmer). At the same time 3.5 μL sample from the RM was mixed with 6 μL of 0.1 M NaOH to deacetylate the tRNAs before the samples were precipitated as before with 5% TCA before liquid scintillation counting of the TCA insoluble material. The experiment was run in triplicate, protein amount calculated following Yabuki *et al.* [136] and averaged. Results are presented in figure 2.20

2.2.6 Structure-based spectral modeling

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Molecular dynamics simulations were carried out using the GROMACS software package with the CHARMM36 force field. The crystal structure of full-length tetrameric KcsA (PDB accession code 3EFF) was embedded in a lipid membrane composed of DMPC molecules, by utilizing GROMACS.27 `gembed` function. TIP3P water model was added to the protein-lipid system for solvation. After an equilibration time of 2 ns (1 ns NVT, 1 ns NPT equilibration, respectively) a 7 ns long production run was carried out and used for the spectral calculations in order to have consistent trajectory times as found in literature protocols for KcsA simulations. The time step of the simulation was 2 fs and used the LINCS constraint algorithm, a Nose-Hoover thermostat and (where appropriate) semi-isotropic pressure coupling by Parrinello-Rahman. The impact of salt ions on the spectrum of the selectivity filter was investigated by placing Na^+ and K^+ prior to equilibration. Two K^+ were placed either in S1, S3 or S2, S4 with two water molecules occupying the remaining sites. For Na^+ , two ions and two waters were placed at positions published by Thompson *et al.* [104]. To fix the ion-binding configuration, the ions were held in place by harmonic position restraints during the production run.

Amide I Spectral Modeling

A schematic of the spectral modeling of amide I frequencies from molecular dynamics simulations is shown in figure 2.15. The process is described in detail in ref [121, 153]. In short, the configurations of 668 backbone peptide units was frozen and used as a starting point for building and parametrizing the local mode Hamiltonian. The structure of the current MD snapshot determines the localization and direction of each carbonyl group along the peptide. For each unit, the transition dipole moment is located in the peptide plane between the carbon and oxygen. Site energies are constructed from the Hamiltonians diagonal parts. To calculate the underlying vibrational transition energies, an empirical spectral map by Reppert *et al.* [154] was used which captures the influence of the environment on the carbonyl oxygen and gives the frequency of each oscillator and its correlation with the electric field.

FIGURE 2.15: Schematics of IR-spectral modeling from structural ensembles. In order to interpret an experimental spectrum on a structural level, an ensemble of KcsA structures is generated by MD-simulation. From this, each peptide groups position is extracted, to calculate the associated amide-I transition dipole. The direct electronic environment influences each sites frequency and couples sites with similar frequencies. This can be calculated by using the structure to parameterize a local mode Hamiltonian. Many coupled sites lead to delocalized eigenstates, which can be used to calculate the IR spectrum via the corresponding transition dipole moments. Doorway modes visualize the amino acids contributing the most to prominent vibrations.

Off-diagonal elements of the Hamiltonian are called couplings, which are dependent on the spatial configuration and orientation of the carbonyl groups. Transition dipole coupling estimated by through-space interaction between them depends on the angle and distance between amide I oscillators [155]. Through-bond coupling of bonded peptide units was determined using a nearest-neighbor model [156] which takes the peptides ϕ and ψ angles into account to map them onto a coupling. By diagonalizing the Hamiltonian, eigenstates and eigenvalues were calculated which served to model the FTIR spectrum of each configuration of the protein and water drawn from snapshots of 1 ps intervals of the MD simulations. Spectra of K^+ binding states 1,3 and 2,4 were averaged to best reproduce experimental conditions. Quantitative descriptions of absolute frequencies, intensities or line widths of peaks is not reproduced, but qualitative and relative shifts are determined reliably. Another limitation is that the spectral map used here neglects side-chain frequencies absorbing in the amide I band such as glutamine, asparagine and arginine. Nevertheless, their intensities are small compared to backbone absorption and their frequencies are well-known making them feasible to consider in interpreting the experimental results.

Doorway Mode Analysis

Doorway mode analysis allows to find the peptide units contributing most to a specific spectral window in the IR spectrum analogous to how PCA reduces a complex data set to reveal the most relevant subset of datapoints that explains the most about a certain investigated feature. This is possible, since in this case over 30000 eigenstates of the vibrational modes are known from the diagonalization of the local mode Hamiltonian. Typically, a $\pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ window around a center frequency is used for the analysis in order to pick up strong IR-active states from the set of eigenvectors [157]. The matrix transformations and visualizations used for this thesis are described in detail in [158].

2.2.7 Electrophysiology of KcsA

The patch-clamp setup consisted of a commercially available Port-a-Patch (Nanion) system where NPC-chips (Nanion) were used in so called black-lipid membrane experiments (see 5.1). Currents were amplified on an EPC-10 amplifier (HEKA) and channel currents analyzed on the computer. RF signals were applied by a SMB100a signal generator (Rhode und Schwartz). Reflectance curves were measured with a FieldFox N9918A (Keysight) RF analyzer. All components were controlled by a custom Labview script. Giant unilamellar vesicles (GUVs) with reconstituted KcsA were generated by electroformation on a Vesicle-prep Pro (Nanion). After drying 5 mM DPhPC (Avanti) with 10 % Cholesterol in chloroform on the conductive side of an Indium Tin Oxide slide (ITO-slide, Nanion) an O-ring was placed around the dried lipid and 1 M sorbitol rehydrated the lipid film. After another ITO-slide sealed the liquid, GUVs were formed by applying an alternating voltage of 3 V at 5 Hz to the system for 2 h at 36 °C. KcsA was added to the solution and incubated for up to >2h before excess lipids were removed with BioBeads (Biorad) for 2h at RT. After removal of the beads the GUVs were used directly for experimentation or stored at 4 °C until further use. Bilayers were formed on NPC-chips (Nanion) which contain a small aperture of 2 μm and a typical resistance with bilayer of 5 G Ω . The bilayer was formed by pipetting a 2 μL of GUV solution to 20 μL of recording buffer solution (10 mM Tris, pH 4, 150 mM KCl) while applying small suction of -10 to -40 mBar. The internal solution consisted of 10 mM Hepes, pH 7, 150 mM KCl and currents

were recorded at 20 kHz sampling with a 3 kHz Bessel filter with voltages between -200 and 200 mV. Single channel currents and their kinetics were analyzed in the software QUB (www.qub.buffalo.edu and references [117, 159]).

Reflectance and transmission measurements consisted of frequency scans from 0.2 to 26.5 GHz carried out at a resolution of 32.5 MHz at the highest available power at each frequency. Frequency was delivered via a coaxial cable with 2 mm diameter which was manually unshielded at the last 5 mm length. A HP Agilent 8449B RF Preamplifier with battery source power (to avoid 50 Hz noise) provided additional gain of 23.5 dB to the antenna. The receiving antenna in transmission experiments was a coaxial cable with 1.5 mm diameter and replaced the inner Ag/Cl electrode.

Simulations of AC-voltages across the membrane were carried out by Ferry Kienberger (Linz) in EMPro 3D EM Simulation Software (Agilent) using spatial parameters as denoted in figure 5.1 and permittivity of $\epsilon_{r(Glass)} = 4$ & $\epsilon_{r(Buffer)} = 80$.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Isotope labeling of amino acids

Organic chemistry of ^{18}O exchange

Exchange of the carbonyl oxygen of amino acids was achieved at high temperatures under highly acidic conditions. The carbonyl oxygens are hydrolyzed by the isotope labeled oxygen of H_2^{18}O with which it exchanges. In order to achieve high enrichment of ^{18}O in the carbonyl group the compounds and glassware had to be devoid of H_2^{16}O during all steps involving high temperatures and low pH. Thus, the glassware was designed to contain only small volumes of air and remaining water vapor was removed from inside the setup by two cycles of heating, flushing with N_2 and evacuating the glassware. A slight overpressure of N_2 avoided contamination from atmospheric water during the acid hydrolysis (see figure 2.14a). Compounds added to the system were water free and injected via air tight syringes through a rubber stopper. H_2^{18}O was of highest available enrichment of ^{18}O to allow for full exchange of isotopes. The amino acid was then hydrolyzed by boiling via a heating mantle under reflux for extended periods in a N_2 atmosphere (see figure 2.14b). The solvent was evaporated, distilled and stored for reuse under nitrogen N_2 (see figure 2.14c). The ^{18}O enrichment of the recovered solvents was high enough to allow to be reused in the first labeling step of another amino acid. In the second acid hydrolysis step only fresh chemicals were used, in order to achieve a high final enrichment of up to >95 %. The carbonyl groups were deprotonated by mixing with an equimolar amount of buffer. After neutralization of the amino acid the carbonyl group is unlikely to exchange its oxygen making it possible to work without N_2 atmosphere. To remove impurities and buffer, the amino acids were recrystallized by precipitating them from the solution and then washed with ice-cold buffer. For this purpose the pH of the buffer was adjusted to the isoelectric point (pI) of the respective amino acid at 0 °C because zwitterionic amino acids are least soluble [160]. L-Tyrosine is almost insoluble in water (0.02 g per 100 g H_2O at 0 °C) which rendered it efficient to crystallize and wash with aqueous buffer solutions and recover 81 % of the starting material. However, L-Valine is fairly well soluble in aqueous solution (8.34 g per 100 g H_2O at 0 °C) which would reduce the yield drastically if washed with aqueous buffer. Thus, the solubility was decreased by mixing with EtOH [161] which allowed for crystallization and washing to achieve fairly high recovery (73 %).

FIGURE 2.16: Mass spectrum of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ amino acids A) L-Tyrosine and B) L-Valine. A shift in mass-charge ratios of 1.003355 or 2.00424638 corresponds to a ^{12}C - ^{13}C or ^{16}O - ^{18}O exchange, respectively. A) For L-Tyrosine mass-charge ratios of approx. 183, 185 and 187 correspond to 0, 1 or 2 ^{18}O atoms in the carbonyl group, respectively (see also chemical structures of the amino acids carbonyl group). 186 and 188 m/z were Tyrosine molecules with 1 or 2 ^{18}O atoms in the carbonyl group and an additional naturally occurring ^{13}C atom in a random position of the rest (R) of the amino acid. B) Correspondingly, for L-Valine mass-charge ratios of 119, 121 and 123 correspond to 0, 1 or 2 ^{18}O atoms while 122 and 124 stemmed from 1 or 2 ^{18}O atoms in Valine molecules carrying an additional ^{13}C atom. The peak at 118 m/z stemmed from L-Valine lacking the ^{13}C at the carbonyl group.

Characterization of isotope labeling efficiency

After the neutralization and washing of the amino acids, the ^{18}O enrichment was determined by ESI-MS by comparing relative abundances of the labeled with unlabeled fractions. 92.5% of all carbonyl oxygen atoms in L-Tyrosine were replaced with ^{18}O after two enrichment cycles (see figure 2.16A). The enrichment in L-Valine was much lower and reached only 74.3% despite two cycles of enrichment with 20 h of hydrolysis each. For both amino acids species with more than one ^{13}C atom were found due to the natural abundance of 1.1% of this isotope. Surprisingly, 3.5% of L-Valine was lacking an ^{13}C atom, although the ^{13}C -enrichment of the supplier was declared as 99%.

Additionally, amino acids were analyzed by FTIR-spectroscopy in order to determine the spectroscopic shift introduced by the isotope labels. The results are shown in figure 2.17. An ^{18}O label introduced a redshift of the amide-I carbonyl group vibration by about 20 cm^{-1} , ^{13}C red-shifted by more than 40 cm^{-1} . The $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labeled products of the acid hydrolysis provided a shift of over 60 cm^{-1} and had almost no overlap to $^{12}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}$ amide-I vibrations. Notably, the amide-I peak of tyrosine overlapped exactly with the peak of its side chain [162] after $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling (see figure 2.17A).

Deconvolution of FTIR-spectra quantified how much the overlapping contribution of all isotopomers contributed to the final spectrum of the $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labeled Valine, in order to confirm ESI-MS results. First, Voigt-profiles (a convolution of characteristics from both Gaussian and Lorentzian lineshapes) were fixed at peak frequencies corresponding to each isotopomer species. Then, an iterative algorithm optimized the peak height and shape to reproduce the original spectrum as good as possible. As a result, the area of each peak quantified the amount of the corresponding isotopomer in the mixture [163]. L-Tyrosine this analysis yielded 95.1% $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ and

FIGURE 2.17: FTIR of isotopomers of Valine and Tyrosine. FTIR absorption of isotopomers normalized to absorption at 1500 cm^{-1} of A) Tyrosine and B) Valine (spectra of amino acids with isotope ^{12}C or ^{13}C are green and purple; dotted and solid lines represent amino acids containing ^{16}O or ^{18}O labels, respectively). Differences in amide-I peak absorption frequency of isotopomers compared to $^{12}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}$ -Tyrosine are shown above the spectra. The legend shows the structure of an α -amino acid with the labeled carbonyl group atoms in red. The carbonyl frequency of the double labeled $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Tyrosine overlaps with the Tyrosine side-chain mode at 1500 cm^{-1} . As an effect, this peaks absolute intensity almost doubles (1.8 times compared to other labeling combinations, not shown).

4.9% $^{13}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}$ for the final product (figure 2.17A, solid purple line). For L-Valine the spectrum of the final hydrolysis product (see figure 2.17B, solid purple line) was comprised of 87.2% $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ and 12.8% $^{13}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}$ contribution from peaks at 1526 and 1507 cm^{-1} , respectively.

As a conclusion, the enrichment of ^{18}O in Valine as determined by FTIR (87.2%) was considerably higher than by ESI-MS (74.3%, see above). The discrepancy in enrichment between ESI-MS and FTIR results could have arisen due to the preparation of ESI-MS samples. The strong change in pH in aqueous environment necessary for both methods likely provided conditions for hydrolysis of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ carbonyls to $^{13}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}$ and thus could have led to lower enrichment as present under neutral pH conditions. Nonetheless, FTIR samples in high pH retained a higher ^{18}O content compared to ESI-MS samples in low pH. Ultimately, maximal spectral separation of isotopes in FTIR was necessary and thus enrichment determined by FTIR was used for calculations the probability of placing two labeled amino acids in the filter, which is $(0.951 \times 0.872 = 82.9\%)$.

2.3.2 Expression and characterization of KcsA

Mutation, expression and characterization of KcsA without isotope labels

From the full length construct of KcsA the following mutants were produced in the wild type full length pRsf1-KcsA construct: pRsf1-KcsAM96V, pRsf1-KcsAE71V, pRsf1-KcsAE71Q, pRsf1-KcsAE71I, pRsf1-KcsAE71H, pRsf1-KcsAE71A, pRsf1-KcsAT75C, pRsf1-KcsAP55Q, pRsf1-KcsAR117Q. In addition, amber constructs were derived for site-directed amber suppression (see below) yielding the constructs pRsf1-KcsAV76am, pRsf1-KcsAG77am, pRsf1-KcsAY78am with "am" denoting mutation to an amber stop codon.

KcsA and mutant strains were expressed in fairly high amounts ($>1.5\text{ mg}$ purified KcsA per litre of culture). Membrane protein optimized bacterial expression strains

FIGURE 2.18: Biochemical characterization of KcsA in low K^+ conditions. A) SDS-PAGE of purified and desalted KcsA. Tetrameric and monomeric KcsA run at 75 and 18 kDa, respectively. B) The overall shape and the two characteristic dips of the CD-spectrum at 208 and 220 nm indicate a high fraction of α -helical features in desalted KcsA.

(i.e. C21, BL21(DE3)-star) did not notably increase the expression yield. The purified and desalted protein displayed a high fraction ($>95\%$) of tetrameric and correctly folded protein (see figure 2.18). However, in the course of deuteration the repeated concentration and dilution cycles precipitated a significant fraction of KcsA. Interestingly, the precipitate not only consisted of monomers, but also a significant fraction of multimeres (6, 8, 10, 12 monomers) of KcsA.

Expression of uniformly $^{13}C^{18}O$ labeled KcsA

To demonstrate the biocompatibility of isotope labeled amino acids, KcsA was expressed in a defined medium in the presence of $^{13}C^{18}O$ -Tyrosine and $^{13}C^{18}O$ -Valine. The efficiency of isotope labeling was calculated based on 16 Valines and 5 Tyrosines (total of 21) in each subunit of KcsA (see figure 2.19 A and 5.1.2) with one Valine and Tyrosine each located in the selectivity filter. The raw mass spectrum in figure 2.19 B showed distinct peaks which corresponded to KcsA charged with different amounts of electrons. Peaks of double labeled KcsA appeared shifted towards higher m/z ratios indicating the extra mass added by isotopes. The difference in peak height between samples can be attributed to different amount of protein used in both samples.

Deconvolution of the mass spectrum extracted the distribution of molecular masses found in the preparation and is shown in Figure 2.19 C. The unlabeled protein was found to be evenly distributed around 18,648 Da, corresponding to the molecular weight of full length KcsA of 18,637.6 Da (see 5.1.2). The difference of 10.4 Da was attributed to the amount of naturally occurring ^{13}C and ^{15}N , which appear at a rates of 1.1% and 0.3%, respectively. KcsA contained 837 carbon and 250 nitrogen atoms. Thus, on average 9.2 and 0.8 u are contributed from natural isotopes ^{13}C and ^{15}N , respectively. Thus, KcsA corrected for natural isotopes was calculated as 18,647.6 Da which almost precisely matched the center of the measured deconvoluted mass peak. The distribution with a FWHM (full width half maximum) of approx 4 u reflected

most likely the measurement imprecision and heterogeneity of the amount of naturally occurring isotope labels in the protein as well as naturally occurring mutational errors during translation.¹

The Mass peak of double labeled protein revealed at least two overlapping Gaussian peaks centered at 18,708 and 18,701 Da. The mass difference of the two peaks compared to the unlabeled protein was 60 and 55 u, respectively. Each artificially introduced isotope label adds 3 u to the proteins mass. Thus, both peaks correspond to 20 and 18.3 incorporated $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled amino acids, respectively. Taking into account, that a in total 21 positions can be labeled by valine and tyrosine, the peaks correspond to an overall labeling efficiency of 95.2 and 87.1 %, respectively. The largest peak at 18,708 Da approximately contains twice the amount of molecules compared to the peak at 18,701 Da as determined by fitting Gaussian curves centered at the peak positions. Thus, the overall labeling efficiency was calculated to be $(2 \times (0.952) + 0.871)/3 = 92.5$ %. The small peaks between 18,648 and 18,690 Da were not significantly higher than the baseline over the whole deconvoluted mass range (not shown) and were omitted from the calculation.

Site-directed isotope labeling by amber suppression in CFE

One prerequisite of amber suppression are high amounts of folded and functional aminoacylated tRNA. For this purpose, T7RNA polymerase was purified in high amounts (see figure 2.20 A) which was able to transcribe high amounts of amber tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ ($>5 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ IVT-mixture). The acceptor arm of the tRNAs (see figure 2.20 B) was often too short which impacted the aminoacylation efficiency. Repair of the acceptor arm restored the canonical CCA-sequence (see figure 2.20 C) by adding the previously lacking nucleotides to the 3' end of the tRNA. For the aminoacylation of tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ the tyrosine synthetase TyrRS was purified in high amounts (see figure 2.20 D). The aminoacylation yielded tyr-tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ which displayed a shift in a acid polyacrylamide-PAGE as seen in figure 2.20 E. The deaminoacylation completely removed the tyrosine from the tRNA and restored the original weight of the tRNA. The efficiency of the aminoacylation reaction was estimated by densitometry of the heavier band compared to the light band. In general up to > 80 % of the tRNA preparation were aminoacylated after the reaction was completed.

A CFE reaction of wt-KcsA from pRsf1-KcsA produced full length monomeric proteins with a molecular weight of 18 kDa. Mutation of Y78 inside the selectivity filter of KcsA to an amber stop codon completely abolished the production of full length product. The product of the corresponding pRsf1-KcsAY78am plasmid was only 9 kDa (see figure 2.20 F and 5.1.2). Upon supplementing tyr-tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ to the plasmid pRsf1-KcsAY78am the amber stop codon was successfully suppressed in approx. 40 % of the cases, rescuing the full length protein by introducing a tyrosine site-specifically at this position.

To quantify the time course of such a reaction radioactive isotopes ^{14}C -tyrosine and ^3H -alanine were used to estimate the amount of suppression and total protein production, respectively. First, ^{14}C -tyr was aminoacylated to tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ to produce ^{14}C -tyr-tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ which was then supplied to a CFE reaction. The suppression efficiency over time was measured by precipitating nucleic acids and proteins with and without previously deacetylation of ^{14}C -tyrs-tRNA $_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$. Measuring the untreated

¹It is generally assumed, that about every 1000th amino acid is placed erroneously by the Ribosome. This means, that from the approximately 10^{12} amino acids constituting the KcsA sample used for this ESI-MS analysis 10^9 were randomly changed amino acids. They deviate from the theoretically calculated amount of atoms and increase the mass-peaks FWHM.

FIGURE 2.19: Mass spectrum of wt and uniformly isotope labeled KcsA. A) Schematic of full length KcsA with 16 Valines and 5 Tyrosines colored in green and orange, respectively. B) ESI-mass spectrum of full length KcsA without (green) and uniformly labeled with $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Tyrosine and $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Valine (purple). The individual peaks correspond to KcsA carrying different amount of positive charges from the ionization process (numbers above peaks). Note, that peaks of double-labeled KcsA have slightly higher m/z ratios. C) Deconvoluted mass spectrum for wt (green) and double labeled KcsA (purple). The mass peak for wt-KcsA is centered around 18,648 Da. For every $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labeled amino acid the protein gets heavier by 3 u. The double labeled KcsA showed a split peak with most KcsA at 18,708 Da and a significant fraction at 18,701 Da which indicated a fraction of partially labeled KcsA.

precipitate determined the amount of acetylated tRNA and labeled protein; deacetylation and washing previous to precipitation determined only the amount of labeled protein. Subtraction of both yields the sum of residual aminoacylated tRNA in the reaction.

The result is shown in figure 2.20 G and H. The flattening of the purple curve in figure 2.20 G indicated, that after 30 min all ^{14}C -tyr was removed from $\text{tRNA}_{\text{CUA}}^{\text{Tyr}}$ either by deacetylation in the solvent or by biosynthesis during amber suppression. Similarly, the amount of ^{14}C -tyr in the protein fraction increased until 30 min (see figure 2.20 H) but does not increase thereafter. The total amount of protein translated in the CFE was determined by measuring the incorporation of ^3H -alanine in both labeled and unlabeled protein. Production of WT KcsA was up to two times the amount of total protein produced from pRsf1-KcsAY78am (green and blue lines in figure 2.20 H). After 30 min, the amount of full length protein in the amber suppression reaction was 65 % which amounts to $(13.0 \pm 1.3) \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of site specifically ^{14}C -Tyr labeled KcsA of the total protein yield $(23.3 \pm 1.7) \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

2.3.3 IR spectroscopy of KcsA

The results in this section are partly published in [153].

FTIR spectroscopy of wt KcsA in KCl and NaCl

Figure 2.21 shows the absolute FTIR spectrum of KcsA in either NaCl or KCl buffer which both show a very similar broad peak with a center frequency of 1659 cm^{-1} indicating high α -helical content. The peak is asymmetric with side chain absorptions of Trp, Tyr, Arg, Asp and Gln residues [162] contributing to a shoulder in the low frequency region. To untangle solely the contribution of ions binding to the filter the difference spectrum is calculated by subtracting the spectra of KcsA in KCl from KcsA in NaCl. The largest change in intensity of the difference spectrum is only $\approx 4\%$ of the intensity of the absolute spectra, since only 16 of 668 amino acids of KcsA directly interact with K^+ or Na^+ inside the filter. The difference spectrum reveals several distinct features (labeled 1, 2 and 3, see figure 2.21) which showed the most difference in amplitude, were not from the region of side chain region absorption and could be simulated qualitatively by the spectral modeling approach described below. Namely, peak 1 at 1625 cm^{-1} is a broad negative peak, peak 2 at 1660 cm^{-1} is a strong positive peak whereas peak 3 is a narrower positive peak with less absorption at 1680 cm^{-1} .

Without computational modeling it is difficult to interpret such spectra. To decipher what structural regions of KcsA might contribute to the difference spectra at these peaks we can rely on what typical types of structures give rise to these spectral components. α -helical and random coil structures are observed in the range of $1650\text{-}1660 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas β -sheets have two peaks with a weak and strong mode at $1670\text{-}1690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1620\text{-}1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. This might hint towards peak 2 originating from the α -helical region close to the selectivity filter, whereas Peak 1 and 3 might be unlikely to stem from β -sheets in KcsA thus hinting towards a series of coupled oscillators potentially from the selectivity filter.

The absolute and difference spectra are consistent with spectra reported by [122, 125] although a shift of peak position $< 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is apparent. The differences in hydrophobic environment (detergent micelles vs. asolectin membranes) are known to induce slight structural changes [164] that can influence FTIR spectra.

FIGURE 2.20: Site-specific isotope labeling by amber suppression in CFE. A) SDS-PAGE of purified T7RNAP (MW = 99 kDa). B) Schematic drawing of a tRNA with the Anticodon complementary to the amber stop codon in green. The aminoacid is acylated to the acceptorarm on the 3' end ending in the sequence CCA. C) Single nucleotide resolution gel of tRNA^{Tyr}_{CUA} before and after repair of the CCA end. In this case up to two nucleotides were added during the repair to create a majority of correct CCA 3' ends. D) SDS-PAGE of purified his-tagged Tyrosyl tRNA synthetase (TyrRS, MW = 42 kDa). E) tRNA^{Tyr}_{CUA} before (left column) and after (middle column) aminoacylation with Tyrosine. The aminoacylated tRNA is heavier and runs slower in the gel. The aminoacylation can be reversed by deacetylation in basic conditions (right column). F) Amber suppression with tRNA^{Tyr}_{CUA} in a CFE. The full length protein produced by pRsf1-KcsA (left column) is completely abolished by an amber mutation in pRsf1-KcsAY78am (middle column). Supplementing tRNA^{Tyr}_{CUA} rescues the full length protein partially by amber suppression (right column). G) Timecourse of ¹⁴C-Tyr-tRNA_{CUA} depletion during CFE. The amount of aminoacylated tRNA in the CFE reaction drops exponentially (purple) releasing more deacylated tRNA (green) which can become aminoacylated by not isotope labeled amino acids in the reaction mixture. H) Timecourse and quantification of amber suppression reaction. As ¹⁴C-Tyr-tRNA_{CUA} was depleted (dotted purple line), site-directed isotope labeled KcsA was produced from plasmid pRsf1-KcsAY78am (purple) by amber suppression. The labeled protein was 60% of all protein produced (blue, quantified via ³H-Ala) which contained abortive and unlabeled KcsA. Production of wt KcsA from plasmid pRsf1-KcsA was twice as effective (green).

FIGURE 2.21: Absolute and difference FTIR spectrum of KcsA in KCl and NaCl. The subtraction KCl - NaCl (red line) reveals the underlying key features in the difference spectrum. Three distinct spectral regions that show high amplitude in the difference spectrum and correspond to spectral regions of interest (see text) are denoted 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Adapted from [153].

FTIR spectroscopy of mutant KcsA in KCl

Only the mutants KcsA E71Q and T75C were possible to be expressed, purified and deuterated to a high-enough concentration to be investigated via FTIR. The mutants often showed either much lower expression rates or were much more sensitive to precipitation during the many cycles of concentration and dilution needed for deuteriation of the samples. The absolute spectra were acquired similar to wt KcsA and displayed stark changes in the region between 1600 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} (see figure 2.22 A). Compared to the subtle changes in ion concentration (see figure 2.21) the absolute changes between wt and mutant are much more pronounced. Contaminants can be excluded, as the deuteriation process exchanges the buffer also to a highly pure ion concentration that was kept the same between WT and mutants. Aggregation peaks are mostly seen out of the 1600 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} range which means that the changes can be attributed to the identity of the mutation.

The difference spectra were normalized to the area between 1600 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} before subtraction. The result is shown in figure 2.22 B. The changes for both mutants display the same tendency: The most notable change is in peak 1 around $1620\text{--}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with T75C displaying a much bigger change compared to the WT construct. The strong positive peak 2 at 1660 cm^{-1} for WT is reduced for E71Q and strongly reduced for T75C. The narrow positive peak 3 of WT KcsA at 1680 cm^{-1} is almost unchanged for the E71Q mutant while T75C displays a slight reduction in optical density.

Modeling of FTIR Spectra

In order to elucidate the structural origin underlying the experimental difference spectrum we applied spectral modeling of KcsA. The maximum difference in intensity of 4% between the different ion binding states in the experiment indicated, that more than the filters carbonyl groups (2.4% of all peptide groups in KcsA) contributed to the ion binding. Thus, the difference FTIR was calculated for different regions of KcsA in order to determine the contribution of each regions peptide units to the

FIGURE 2.22: FTIR of mutants compared to WT KcsA. A) absolute spectra of E71Q (blue line) and T75C (green line) when compared to WT KcsA (red line). B) The difference spectrum E71Q - WT (blue line) and T75C - WT (green line) show stark changes in spectral regions of interest denoted 1 and 2 (see section 2.3.3 for details on peak denotation). The tendency of change is the same for both E71Q and T75C. However, T75C displays the biggest change in regions 1 and 2. Peak 3 is unchanged for the E71Q mutant while T75C shows reduced optical density.

spectral features. These tetrameric subdomains were comprised of (I) the filters TVGY sequence, (II) an extended filter formed by the filter and the four pore helices and (III) the whole membrane embedded region of KcsA. The summary in figure 2.23 A shows that the calculation for filter-only residues greatly differs from the experimental spectrum. Especially the 1660 cm^{-1} peak was captured only once the pore helices are included in the simulation, which suggested that coupling between the monomer units of this larger protein part is responsible for this signature of the experimental spectra. Adding the whole membrane spanning region of KcsA does not notably improve the match of the calculated ion difference spectrum with the experiment. Thus it can be concluded, that changes upon ion exchange are mostly confined to the extended filter region.

The simulation results of the absolute and difference FTIR spectrum of the extended filter region qualitatively resembled the experimental features (see figure 2.23 B). The shape, peak frequencies and line width were in qualitatively in good agreement, although quantitative accuracy was not possible with this type of calculation. The calculated difference spectrum reproduced the relative intensity and peak frequency of the most pronounced spectral features 1, 2 and 3 with a precision of a few wavenumbers (see figure 2.23 C). This indicated, that the delocalized vibrational modes calculated in the model captured the relevant underlying molecular details of KcsA in the experiment.

The experimental spectrum deviates strongly from the simulation in a shoulder between 1620 and 1650 cm^{-1} (orange region in 2.23 B). While this could be a general limitation of the underlying model, it is more likely to reflect the neglect of side chains of Tyr (1615 cm^{-1}), Arg (1605 cm^{-1}), Trp (1618 cm^{-1}) and Gln (1640 cm^{-1}) [162] due to the lack of realistic coupling modes, whose contributions are not captured in simulations (see also page 49). This is illustrated by the Y78F mutation of the filter which showed normal channel currents [165] but altered absorption compared to the WT especially in the side chain region (1620 - 1650 cm^{-1}) [122]. Thus, the analysis focused on the delocalized amide I vibrations of peaks 1-3 which were reproducible solely by modeling of backbone carbonyl groups.

FIGURE 2.23: Simulation and experimental results of difference spectra for different subregions of KcsA. A) The features 1, 2, and 3 of the experimental spectrum are qualitatively reproduced by the full transmembrane region and the extended filter region, whereas the filter-only simulation differs significantly. The comparison of simulated and experimental spectra of high K^+ KcsA three distinct features (1, 2 and 3) shown in red, green and blue, respectively, appear in both absolute B) and difference spectra C). Side chains absorb in the region highlighted in orange. Adapted from [153].

FIGURE 2.24: Contribution of ion binding states to the simulated difference spectrum of the extended filter region. The subtraction of potassium from sodium binding states yields the gray difference spectrum. Spectral regions of interest 1, 2 and 3 are highlighted in red, green and purple, respectively. Adapted from [153].

To deconvolute the molecular origins of the spectral features 1-3, the contribution of each ion type and binding state to the extended filters FTIR difference spectrum is shown in figure 2.24. In agreement with previous studies [122], peak 1 and 3 arose from frequency shifts between distinct peaks of K^+ and Na^+ . At 1630 cm^{-1} (peak 1) the Na^+ bound filter had a high absorption leading to a narrow negative feature in the $K^+ - Na^+$ FTIR difference spectrum. Analogously, peak 3 of the difference spectrum was due to two peaks of K^+ in the 1,3 and 2,4 state at 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} , respectively, while the Na^+ bound KcsA does not show a clear feature in this region. However, peak 2 arose from changes in line shape and intensity of a peak shared by simulations of K^+ and Na^+ binding states. As substantiated by calculations of subsets of KcsA, this suggested that the 1660 cm^{-1} peak did not reflect a direct interaction of filter carbonyl groups with ions, but ion type induced changes in the filters adjacent α -helices.

Most significantly for the detection of quantum coherence in KcsA, this analysis showed that signatures of 1,3 and 2,4 state were identified. However, their most strongly absorbing features have a rather small spectral separation of $\Delta\omega \approx 6\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is unsurprising due to their structural similarity. As a consequence, in 1DIR these spectral features are inseparably convolved to one peak (peak 3).

Doorway mode analysis and Visualization

Spectral deconvolution described which peaks originate from which ion state (S1,S3 etc.). However, it did not provide the contributing carbonyl groups whose vibrations contributed to each states deconvoluted spectrum. Doorway mode analysis (figure 2.25) revealed with molecular detail the peptide units which most significantly contributed to the delocalized amide I vibrations of a spectral feature. The analysis of eigenstates within four narrow ($\pm 3\text{ cm}^{-1}$) spectral windows was centered around 1630 cm^{-1} (peak 1), 1660 cm^{-1} (peak 2) and K^+ binding states S1,S3 and S2,S4 at 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} , respectively (peak 3).

FIGURE 2.25: The expanded filter region's doorway modes, represented as a side view (left) and peering down the pore from the top (right). Color intensity indicates the amplitude of the carbonyl vibration, while the color indicates its relative phase. Green arrows indicate the transition dipole moments direction (μ) for the respective mode. Na⁺ and K⁺ are shown as blue and purple spheres, respectively. The general displacement of the filters carbonyl groups and the backbone is shown as colored circles on the right. Adapted from [153].

The resulting calculation assigned distinct vibrational motions of the extended filters amide units to the four modes. The 1630 cm^{-1} was designated B-site mode due to the contributions from carbonyls of T75 complexing Na^+ in an in-plane coordination [104]. Furthermore, the mode showed significant contribution from the pore helices carbonyls with opposite monomers vibrating out-of-phase, as indicated by the direction of their transition dipoles (outlined arrows and different colors in top panel figure 2.25). Carbonyls on one monomer extended, while they contracted on the opposing monomer effectively adding up to a strong net transition dipole moment μ (shown as a green arrow in figure 2.25) perpendicular to the filters pore. The 1660 cm^{-1} mode of peak 2 showed almost exclusively contribution from the pores adjacent α -helices and is thus labeled "Helix-mode". All monomers carbonyls moved in-phase leading to a total transition dipole moment μ along the pore (second panel figure 2.25). Analysis of the 1674 cm^{-1} mode revealed strong involvement of the carbonyls of T75 and V76 which comprise binding site S3. The 1680 cm^{-1} mode displayed mostly contributions from V76 and G77 residues of ion binding site S2 (bottom panels figure 2.25). Interestingly, both modes are almost completely uncoupled from the pore helices and show out-of-phase carbonyl movements between the monomers with the total transition dipole moment μ orthogonal to the pores tunnel.

The difference in extent of delocalization provided additional information on the specificity of the mode to particular interactions of the involved protein sites [166, 167]. The finding of confined and highly delocalized amide I vibrations (i.e. $1674/1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ versus 1660 cm^{-1} mode) reflects the differences in couplings and site frequencies determined by the positioning of the underlying structural elements. Two competing factors determined the amount of delocalization of a vibration: The more similar the site frequencies ($\Delta\omega$) are and the stronger the individual oscillators couple (J) to each other, the easier it is for an excitation to spread its energy over many oscillators. The "Helix" mode (peak 2) nicely illustrates this case, because the α -helices of the pore helix provided an almost uniform electrostatic environment which reduced the variation in individual site frequencies ($\Delta\omega$). In addition, the helical structure forced all carbonyls to point in the same direction effectively aligning their transition dipole moments. This significantly increased coupling between all oscillators of the helix which also share similar site frequencies (small $\Delta\omega$). As an effect, the vibration was spread out across the whole α -helix because the structural prerequisites allowed it to be highly delocalized.

Slight disruptions of the helical structure like twisting or bending were shown to change the line width and intensity of associated IR peaks [168, 169]. Since in the IR difference spectrum of peak 2 originated solely from helix modes, the strong change in intensity upon ion exchange could stem from a distortion of the pore α -helices. The drop in intensity from K^+ to Na^+ -bound state suggested that the α -helices deviated more from an ideal geometry with K^+ bound to the filter. With Na^+ bound, α -helices were significantly less fluctuating as quantified by their summed RMSD over the course of the MD simulation. The modes line shape is broader and less intense, since the vibrational energy is shared more effectively in an optimal helix configuration across many carbonyl groups.

The opposite was true for the three remaining, more localized modes: the involved carbonyl groups frequencies were selectively and strongly influenced by the electrostatic forces of the ions coordinated by them. The close proximity of Na^+ to the carbonyl group of T75 in the B-site mode changed the carbonyl groups frequency by over 25 cm^{-1} . This was considerably larger than the coupling to the adjacent V76 carbonyl groups ($J < 8\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which effectively decoupled the ion coordinating carbonyl groups from the rest of the filter. Thus, the 1630 cm^{-1} -mode is a site-specific infrared

mode for in plane coordination of Na^+ ions by the four carbonyls of T75. In contrast, K^+ is caged by eight carbonyl groups, which is reflected in the localization of the S3 and S2 modes. The S3 site binds K^+ to the carbonyls of V76 and G77 which induces similar frequencies ($\Delta\omega \approx 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and strong coupling amongst them ($J < 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This results in a largely localized IR transition of only the carbonyls involved in ion coordination which includes Y78. The S2-mode behaves very similar with almost the same molecular constituents. Slight differences in site energies involve V76 and G77 which are slightly stronger supposedly due to direct contact with the bound K^+ . Furthermore, Y78 is less involved in this delocalized vibration which might stem from the lack of direct interaction to an ion in this binding state.

Similar how PCA projects highly dimensional data to few dimensions, the doorway mode analysis considered only the most pronounced modes. However, all vibrational motions contribute to varying degrees to the overall vibrational landscape of a protein. The interactions of the subset of doorway modes presented above was not considered in this analysis but it would be necessary to describe how these characteristic modes influenced each other. Because the analysis was insensitive to these couplings or anharmonicities, FTIR cannot provide a definitive characterization of the vibrational modes of proteins which would be necessary to describe the full dynamical picture of the ions interactions with the protein.

In conclusion, the molecular constituents contributing to S1,3 and S2,4 mode are very similar both in amino acid identity, site frequency and contribution strength to the resulting spectral feature. Nonetheless, this underpinned the choice of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -labels at V76 and Y78, which might indeed be able to discern experimentally the subtle differences between the states as found in the simulations above.

Equilibrium 2DIR of isotope labeled KcsA

$^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels have to be detectable in complex molecules like KcsA to allow the discrimination between K^+ states and ultimately allow for transient 2DIR measurements on coherences between the states. The detection of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels in 2DIR measurements of uniformly labeled KcsA was used to evaluate the detectability of site-directed labels in KcsA. Figure 2.26 shows the experimental results of 2DIR spectroscopy in equilibrium. As predicted by [123] (figure 2.26 A&B), the results (2.26 C&D) revealed that $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels indeed provide detectable signatures in the low frequency regions. Changes after ion exchange (figure 2.26 E&F) show an increase in signal strength and decreased ellipticity which indicates a more rigid environment of all or some of the isotope labeled carbonyl groups in the presence of K^+ compared to Na^+ . This is in line with IR-experiments on model compounds mimicking the interaction of carbonyl groups and K^+ in KcsAs selectivity filter (see figure 2.5 and ref [123]). However, overall signal strength of the isotope labeled fraction was close to the noise levels of residual water in the sample (likely trapped inside the detergent micelles) and overlapped with side-chain absorptions (see also figure 2.17 and 2.21). The additional background hindered the detection of proposed cross-peaks between IR signatures of carbonyls in the filter.

The difference spectra are shown in figure 2.27. Subtraction within isotope labeled KcsA revealed that in the region between 1600 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} differences between K^+ and Na^+ can be resolved (see figure 2.27 A). To confirm, non isotope labeled KcsA was subtracted (see figure 2.27 B) which revealed small resolvable changes between ion content even without isotope labels. The peaks of the difference spectra are both at 1630 cm^{-1} , 1660 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} which is in line with 1D FTIR experiments (see section 2.3.3).

FIGURE 2.26: Theoretical and experimental 2DIR spectra of KcsA with isotope labels in different ion environments. Predicted difference spectra between 1,3 and 2,4 states for A) unlabeled and B) T75, V76 and Y78 of KcsA site-specifically labeled, respectively. Without isotope labels, The difference is convoluted with all other carbonyl groups of KcsA at 1650 cm^{-1} . Isotope labels introduce a redshift and resolve the differences (green box, A&B adapted from [123]). Experimental spectrum of C) unlabeled and D) uniformly $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ -Tyrosine and Valine labeled KcsA. Compared to the unlabeled protein C) the low frequency region (green box) intensified in the labeled protein D) due to the red shift of labeled amino acids. The difference spectrum of labeled from unlabeled protein in E) low (0 mM) and F) high (150 mM) K^+ salt concentration revealed that the signal in the low frequency region is increased in high potassium environment. Furthermore, the line shapes of the unlabeled amino acids ($>1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are broader in low K^+ compared to high K^+ environment. This indicated more variable carbonyl group environments if the channel is devoid of K^+ .

FIGURE 2.27: Experimental 2DIR difference spectrum between K^+ and Na^+ with and without isotope label. All difference spectra show the difference of WT KcsA between high and low K^+ concentrations. The difference spectrum of KcsA is shown A) with isotope and B) without uniform isotope labels. Both difference spectra show peaks signal strength at around 1630 cm^{-1} , 1660 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} .

Initiation of transport for transient 2DIR of KcsA

Measurement that could characterize possible quantum and vibrational effects in KcsA requires to follow the coupling of 1,3 and 2,4 states with ps time resolution while initiating ion transport from one specific state to another synchronously in the majority of channels. Precise initiation of ion transport is necessary since unsynchronized events across channels would average out the expected beatings in off-diagonal cross peak intensity during scanning of waiting times. However, diffusion times of ions are long compared to the short observational window of 2DIR and thus this presents a limiting factor for synchronizing ion transport events with 2DIR readout. After excitation, the vibrational lifetime of a carbonyl vibration in which it is sensitive to changes in the environment is on the order of ps². Identical transport events and interactions with K^+ have to occur during this time window in most channels to obtain meaningful data at good signal strength. Thus, the necessary SNR to detect amplitude fluctuations in the off-diagonal peaks depends on the efficiency of synchronization multiplied with fraction of isotope labeled KcsA in the sample.

Another option to circumvent synchronization of many channels would be to record single-molecule 2DIR. High sensitivity of the measurement would be required to detect the difference spectrum of a single ion-induced event. Surface-enhanced Infrared spectroscopy (SEIRAS) [170] might be an experimental methodology that could provide the necessary amplification of signal required for such an experimental approach.

One way to induce ion flow in KcsA is to open its pH sensitive gate via a pH jump. Photoacids such as pyranine (HPTS) can lower the pH from 8 to 4 within 0.2 ns [171–173], enough to open the pH gate of KcsA [84]. However, the conformational transitions triggered by protonating KcsAs gate are on the order of microseconds [85]. Preliminary experiments showed, that the His-tag of KcsA absorbed most of

²Electronic coherences found in the Photosystem usually last $\approx 1\text{ ps}$ [22, 27] while the much higher mass of K^+ suggests an even smaller coherence time

FIGURE 2.28: Optical control of unblocking of KcsA. Overlay of K^+ channel structures side views (Shaker channel gray, KcsA purple, filter yellow, K^+ green). Homology modeling revealed a similar position for functionalization of KcsA (red) in a conserved external loop. Here, MAQ-azobenzene (black) was linked to shaker via a cysteine introduced by mutation. MAQ (blue) blocks S4 in the dark state and arrests the channel in the 2,4 state (right side). Photoisomerization of azobenzene could allow unidirectional transport of K^+ to the 2,4 state (left). PDB struct: 1k4c and 2r9r

the protons released which led to a low fraction of open channels. Cleavage of the His-tag [174] in a specially designed plasmid was possible but introduced additional loss in purifiable protein amount by approximately 15 % (data not shown). As a consequence, it is rather preferred to keep most channels open at all time by buffering in low pH and induce ion transport in a different manner. Sequestering and subsequent photo-release of K^+ could rapidly increase its concentration in the vicinity of KcsA and thus initiate transport in channels devoid of K^+ . Many different light-switchable metal-organic cages are available [175] that could be tuned to the optimal conditions of high affinity to K^+ in the dark state and rapid release upon photo triggering while avoiding spectral overlap with the 2DIR acquisition window. The time scale for release of K^+ was comparable to previously published calcium cages [176] and expected to be on the order of μs .

After photorelease, K^+ would need to diffuse to KcsA and initiate transport. The diffusion time of K^+ to the channel after photorelease can be calculated³ as $t = \langle x \rangle^2 / 2D \approx 2.5 ns$ with the average distance $\langle x \rangle = 3 nm$ of crown ethers ($MW \approx 300 Da$) at a concentration of 50 mM in the solution and the diffusion coefficient $D = 2 \times 10^5 cm^2 s^{-1}$ of potassium in water. The probability distribution of distances to the channel is adding more variability to the expected diffusion time of K^+ to the channel. Furthermore, K^+ can enter KcsA via two sides with largely different diffusion lengths to the filters first binding site (see figure 2.1 and 2.19A). In addition, the ions would induce 1,3 or 2,4 state coming from the extracellular and intracellular side, respectively, and ultimately average their signatures. Finally, KcsA devoid of K^+ is arrested in the non-conductive or C-type inactivated conformation [88] and slowly switches to the conductive conformation on timescales reaching up to seconds upon ion titration [82, 87, 102].

Directionality of ion transport could be assured by locking the channel in one of the two configurations by reversibly blocking one side of the channel. KcsA arrested in the 2,4 state may be achieved by blocking the extracellular side with the channel blocker MAQ. Photoinducible unblocking was pioneered in the related Shaker K^+ channel by

³The average distance between molecules $\langle x \rangle$ is calculated as $\langle x \rangle \sim 1/n^{1/3}$ with $n = N/V$ [177].

linking MAQ to azobenzene. Light isomerizes azobenzene and removes the channel blocker from the pore opening [178–182]. The isomerization of Azobenzene occurs on ps timescale, close to what is needed for the transient 2DIR measurements but a lack of concentration gradient or electrical potential across the channel does not actively drive the ion transport after unblocking. Gradients could be applied by reconstituting isotope labeled and photoinducibly unblockable samples unidirectionally into stacked bilayers [183] to obtain sufficiently high sample concentration on a gold coated ATR-FTIR crystal surface in surface-enhanced Infrared spectroscopy (SEIRAS) [170]. The gold surface would serve as an electrode to drive the ion transport.

Nonetheless, even in the presence of an external field ensuring maximal conductance and photo induced unblocking of channels, ion transport is inherently stochastic process which is on average three orders of magnitude slower than the measurement window of excitations in transient 2DIR. Thus, even with all the highly sophisticated methodologies incorporated to the sample design, only a marginal fraction of channels will release a K^+ ion from its local minimum in a defined state in the desired synchronous behavior. This fraction is multiplied by the inefficiencies of each additional protein modification step which further reduces the fraction of homogeneous and functional sample and ultimately the SNR of the measurements. Nonetheless, single-molecule spectroscopy overcomes the limitation of high concentration and inefficient production of molecules and might be a highly rewarding future path for exploration.

2.3.4 Electrophysiology of KcsA

Quantum coherences

In order to induce quantum resonances in the filter, impedance matching is necessary to maximize the power transfer to and minimize signal reflection from the patch. Since the modulation of DC current by the predicted quantum coherences depends strongly on the AC power applied across the membrane, it is necessary to know the exact AC potential across the patch. To characterize the stability of impedance matching across a broad frequency range during normal use of the setup, the reflectance of the setup was measured with a Microwave analyzer as RF reflected from the patch does not contribute to the membranes AC field.

The results in figure 2.29 A-C show measurements of reflectance under different experimental circumstances. The RF emitter was placed at approx 50 μm distance from the patch without the RF receiver (see figure 2.29 D). Variations of up to 40 dB in reflectance appeared after usual manipulations such as changing the inner or outer buffer solution, exchanging the NPC-chip or touching the AgCl-electrode. The amplitude and frequency of the peaks changed drastically after slight manipulations of the setups geometry. This showed, that the setups normal use introduced unpredictable variability of RF-strength at the patch especially in the >10 GHz range.

The transmission of the setup measures the actually applied RF-strength across the patch. It was not possible to test reflectance in the complete measurement setting with the inner DC electrode in place, due to spatial constraints (see 5.1). Trying to

TABLE 2.4: Simulation results of AC-voltage across bilayer in millivolt as a function of distance and RF-Frequency

Freq [GHz]	Distance [μm]			
	1	200	1	200
1	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.04
10	0.36	0.93	0.21	0.50
26	0.05	0.12	0.03	0.07

FIGURE 2.29: Reflectance of RF-frequencies in Nanion setup. Green and purple traces represent reflectance measurements before and after A) exchanging the buffer solution B) exchanging the chip or C) touching the AgCl grounding wire. Differences of pre and post-manipulation are shown in gray. Distance dependency of transmission in D) air and E) Buffer. F) Schematic Nanion setup. The RF emitter dips in the outer buffer together with the ground electrode. The DC voltage usually drives K^+ ions across the patch (orange inset) via the inner electrode. Due to spatial constraints, the electrode was removed and replaced with the RF-antenna/receiver during these measurements.

FIGURE 2.30: Electrophysiology of isotope labeled single channel KcsA. Representative single channel currents of A) wildtype and C) uniformly Val/Tyr isotope labeled channels (Top: Overview, Bottom: Magnification of burst underlined with grey dots). Analysis of gating dynamics of B) wildtype and C) uniformly Val/Tyr isotope labeled channels show comparable kinetic behavior. In both cases three populations of closed states correspond to High P_O , Low P_O and Flicker mode with a mean open time τ_0 of 100, 10 and <1 ms, respectively.

Figure B adapted from [106].

circumvent this limitation by measuring RF transmission at the output of the DC-electrode was not successful. No transmission was measured, either due to lacking RF transmission across the patch or improper impedance matching of the inner Ag/Cl electrode and the wiring inside the Nanion. Thus, RF-Transmission measurements were possible only by replacing the internal AgCl electrode with the RF-receiver in the fully assembled and shielded Nanion (figure 2.29 F or purple electrode in figure 5.1 Top).

The distance dependency of the transmission was investigated by repeating frequency scans while moving the RF-antenna away from the receiver in steps of 25 μm using a translation stage. Transmission loss quantifies the decrease in RF-intensity after propagation through some medium with lower values indicating smaller attenuation of the signal strength. As expected, in air (figure 2.29 D) transmission loss increased with increased distance of the RF-emitter from the patch. In recording buffer (figure 2.29 E) distance dependency was less pronounced. However, especially low frequencies <10 GHz were heavily attenuated with transmission losses of up to -25 dB at close distances. This behavior got more pronounced with smaller drop sizes (data not shown).

Simulations of the RF strength across the membrane provided the magnitude of expected voltage differences in the above setup. As shown in table 2.4 induced AC potential differences across the membrane are highest at intermediate frequencies (10 GHz) and close to the patch. According to [108] a membrane potential change of 315 mV has to be induced by the AC field across the membrane to observe quantum resonances. AC strengths found by simulations reach 0,01 and 0.30 % of this value at 1 and 10 GHz, respectively. Highest AC potential was found at frequencies sensitive to experimental variations (see figure 2.29).

TABLE 2.5: Comparison of single channel parameters. The differences in conductance and opening probability are not significantly different between the Wildtype and isotope labeled channels.

Type	Conductance	Opening prob.
Wildtype	(89 ± 8) pS	(14 ± 2) %
$^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ Val/Tyr	(85 ± 7) pS	(16 ± 2) %

Single channel behavior of isotope labeled channels

To investigate if isotope labels are non-invasive probes, single channels of uniformly Val/Tyr labeled KcsA were recorded at a constant holding potential of 200 mV.

Results in figure 2.30 show examples of representative currents and the channels kinetic behavior. In both cases short bursts are interspersed with long silent periods (figure 2.30 A&C). A quantitative description is shown in figure 2.30 B&D. Isotope labeled KcsA is similar to recorded and published WT data [106]. Table 2.5 shows, that conductances and opening probabilities P_O of WT and labeled channel are not significantly different and resemble published data (≈ 100 pS in ref [79], $P_O \approx 15$ % in ref [184]).

2.4 Discussion

2.4.1 Discussion of hypothesis of quantum assisted ion transport in potassium channels

Search for signatures of quantum resonances by electrophysiology

The pitch and strength in suppression of DC current by quantum resonances (as introduced on page 22) is strongly dependent on the strength of the applied AC field (see figure 2.2 left). Stability of AC-strength and the channels conductance properties across many measurements is crucial to discern small variations in DC current with statistical significance. However, securing a stable and strong enough AC-field as well as compensating drift in channel properties to test the hypothesis of quantum coherent ion transport was hindered in this study by significant experimental hurdles. The setups for detection of quantum resonances by Electrophysiology demonstrated that maximizing the power transfer between the RF-source and the patch (impedance matching) cannot be implemented reproducibly in the setups investigated in this thesis. Several parameters had to be adjusted manually for each experiment which impacted the impedance matching: First, the patch clamp setups AgCl-electrodes shape and position, second, amounts and shape of the dielectric electrolyte solution, and third, the lateral position and distance of the RF-Antenna respective to the patch as well as the variation of the patch chip itself. The variations in the geometry and electrical properties of the setup did not allow for reproducible field strength at the patch especially above 8 GHz (see figure 2.29 A-C). Below 10 GHz AC-strength at the patch dropped significantly (see table 2.4) leaving no frequency window to reliably apply the desired AC-strength across the membrane. Increasing the AC-strength by increasing the power of the RF source may lead to heating of the lipid membrane which is known to influence conductance and gating [164, 185].

Nonetheless, Nanions' black lipid setup provided more reliability of the patch geometry itself compared to the setup originally proposed by Vaziri and Plenio. There, the patch pipettes' shape and size would introduce additional spatial variables. As a possible solution, a custom lab on a chip setup [186, 187] with fixed geometries of all

antennas and electrodes as well as defined electrolyte amounts inside the system could provide the reproducibility necessary for detecting presumably weak quantum resonances. The setup should be optimized for optimal impedance matching and small variations in geometry, to increase stability by reducing nonlinear and unpredictable changes in field strength across individual experiments. Since no commercial system was available at the time of the thesis and major engineering hurdles would have to be overcome, the project was discontinued at this point.

Search for signatures of quantum resonances using 2DIR of KcsA

The prerequisites of successful measurement of quantum resonances outlined in section 2.1.4 are discussed below in the light of the findings of this thesis:

Site directed $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels were introduced *in vitro* by amber suppression to unambiguously assign spectral signature of 1,3 and 2,4 states. This method proved to be successful, but also came with several technical limitations.

First, the amount of full length protein produced by amber suppression is limited due competition with release factor 1 (RF-1) present in the CFE leading to a significant fraction of abortive products. The use of RF-1 depleted S30 extract [188] could help increasing the amount of correct product by removing the competing reaction for abortive products.

Second, the native tRNA synthetases present in the CFE can recharge deacylated amber tRNA with amino acids that are not isotope labeled. This leads to an undetermined fraction of unlabeled full length KcsA which will increase the background during FTIR measurements. A workaround would be to acetylate the amino acid to an orthogonal tRNA [189] not recognized by the native E.Coli tRNA synthetases. Since tRNA synthetases do not distinguish isotopomers of amino acids it is so far impossible to develop an orthogonal tRNA synthetase which would specifically recharge amber tRNA with normal isotope labeled amino acids while rejecting unlabeled amino acids. As an alternative, an orthogonal tRNA/tRNA synthetase pair developed for unnatural amino acids [190] could be used to allow for *in vivo* amber suppression without the risk of recharging. For this a unnatural amino acid has to be identified which (i) does not disrupt filter function and (ii) can be $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled and (iii) can be attached to an orthogonal tRNA. The unnatural amino acid however is likely to introduce artifacts due to the tight packing and functionally crucial interactions of side chains of amino acids lining the pore [106].

Third, high yield of membrane proteins by CFE can be achieved when replacing reaction products in a continuous manner [142]. However, in this case continuous feeding is not possible due to the "single-use" charged amber tRNAs that need to be supplemented at the beginning to the reaction. The reaction has to be stopped when most of the charged amber tRNA is depleted. Otherwise recycling of amber tRNAs by native tRNA synthetases in the CFE with nonlabeled amino acids increases the amount of unlabeled full length protein as discussed above. The limited reaction time reduces protein yield drastically compared to continuous feed methods described in [142] and adds unwanted background in the FTIR experiment due to unlabeled full length protein. The protein amount needed for one 2DIR experiment would require 5 mL of optimized CFE reaction (see figure 2.20 H) supplemented with 5.4 mg of charged amber tRNA which comes at high cost and effort for production and purification. Deuteration and all other manipulations added lossy steps to the preparation which further reduced the yield but IR-experiments would demand reasonably large amounts of highly concentrated sample. Thus, streamlining and optimization of the methodology is needed to make it practically feasible for 2DIR experiments.

Fourth, the presence of side-chain absorption in the frequency region of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels (see figure 2.17, 2.26 B-D and [162]) adds a significant amount of background and diminishes the signal to noise ratio of the labeled amino acids. Deprotonation of side chains is not possible because KcsA precipitates at high pH. Thus, careful subtraction of labeled and unlabeled samples, averaging of independent batches and further increase in deuteration could further improve the SNR.

Lastly, uniform isotope labeling is quick, easy and provides large amounts of labeled protein for FTIR and 2DIR studies. However, isotope labels outside the selectivity filter increase the background absorption and unspecific interactions with K^+ . The applied uniform labeling of Val/Tyr adds over 90% of the isotope labels outside the filter which drastically decreased the SNR of the filter labels. Thus, spectral changes observed by ion exchange (see figure 2.26 B-D) might stem mostly from non-filter groups interacting with ions, or ion-binding induced structural changes in remote parts of the protein [77]. Nonetheless, this method could be used to provide a single isotope label inside the filter if all four Tyrosines outside the filter are changed to functionally and structurally immune mutations. Uniform $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeling as pioneered in this thesis proved to be a successful technique in FTIR studies to improve common amide I frequency maps [191]. Furthermore, $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels were demonstrated to be non-invasive for several functional key parameters of the channels function.

As demonstrated recently [124], semi-synthesis is able to label KcsAs filter in a site-directed manner without introducing $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ carbonyls outside the filter. In their study, the signal of the filters isotope labels increases the 2DIR signal strength in the same red shifted region as observed with uniform labeled KcsA in this thesis. Careful subtraction removed side chain contributions and allowed modeling of filter states. This showed that a more sophisticated experimental approach unambiguously assigns filter residues spectrally. Uniform labeling contains the same information within the background of labeled non-filter residues and maybe careful subtraction might be able to extract spectral changes specific to the filter without the need for sophisticated labeling techniques. Furthermore, uniform labeling could be applied to include structural rearrangements of non-filter residues upon ion exchange in the filter into the analysis. This could elucidate important details on channel activation [77] or the functional importance of structural elements surrounding the filter [106].

The detection of off-diagonal features between 1,3 and 2,4 states is another requirement for the proposed experiments. Vibrational modeling as demonstrated in section 2.3.3 assigned spectral features without the need for laborious labeling strategies. Furthermore, this approach demonstrated how ion type binding to the filter influences the delocalized vibrations of the whole extended filter region. Most interestingly, doorway mode analysis deconvoluted the differences between S1,S3 and S2,S4 site frequencies ($\Delta\omega$) and their strength which were small when compared to KcsA in Na^+ 2.24. The biggest apparent difference at 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} shows changes of $\Delta\omega \approx 6\text{ cm}^{-1}$ between K^+ binding states in the filter. Detection of quantum coherence depends on cross-peaks between these signatures, however due to their small spectral resolution, crosspeaks will lie close to the diagonal. Line-broadening in big proteins like KcsA is a significant factor, due to the multitude of different environments and couplings carbonyl groups encounter in a complex and flexible protein. Thus, cross peaks close to the diagonal will overlap with the originating spectral features decreasing SNR. Nonetheless, off-diagonal features might be detectable in labeled samples with high SNR.

As demonstrated in the electronic 2D spectroscopy of the photosynthetic complex, coherence manifests itself as beatings in the amplitude of the cross peaks for different

inter-pulse delay times [22]. Given that experiments are typically done on ensembles of molecules, a necessary requirement to experimentally observe the beating of the cross peaks is that the initialization of the excited state needs to be fast compared to the decoherence time. The approaches demonstrated in section 2.3.3 revealed that it might be possible to arrest the channels in the S1,S3 state and allow ion movement with ps precision due to optical control of Azobenzene. However, even with sophisticated protein modifications and externally forcing the ions along a gradient, the randomness inherent to an ion leaving their local minimum inside the binding site will wash out any effort to synchronize ion transport on a ps scale. We were not able to identify a method to actively push an ion out of their respective binding site after photoinducible unblocking within the desired experimental observation window of coherences. As a result, the inherently asynchronous ion transport would strongly reduce the SNR of potential off-diagonal beatings if not abolish them completely. In addition, isotope editing of KcsA is already a laborious process with low protein yield and achieved $\approx 83\%$ double labels in the filter (see section 2.3.1). Adding two more sophisticated protein modifications (i.e. Azobenzene-MAQ, reconstitution to membranes) further reduces the chance to obtain double labeled and photoswitchable KcsA.⁴ In combination with unsynchronizable ion transport, the remaining small fraction of randomly synchronous ion channels is likely to be drowned in averaged background and high scattering as found in 2DIR in the spectral region of uniformly $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled samples.

The best alternative to avoid problems with synchronizing the transport is if one could achieve 2DIR spectroscopy in single channels. Single-channel 2DIR recordings would simply detect whenever an ion-crossing occurs and would completely eliminate the need for synchronization. This could be for example explored utilizing near-field techniques which were shown to increase the signal strength by orders of magnitude [192]. Membrane proteins have been investigated using 2DIR near-field methodology while a current was applied across the membrane [193] and novel methods utilizing plasmonic nano-antennas were shown to exhibit $h10^6 - 10^8$ raw enhancement factors [194]. Both methodologies combined could drive an ion current across single-channels in the membrane while the enhancement factors of novel antennas could be sensitive enough to resolve the ions interaction with the selectivity filters carbonyl groups.

To summarize, the possibility of quantum coherent ion transfer in KcsA cannot be investigated with the currently available methodological toolset due lack of synchronous excitation of ion transport. However, spectroscopic modeling showed even without isotope labeling [153] how flexibility and rigidity of the filter are balanced by an interplay of the filter and its surrounding pore helices. Together with the finding, that ions do not follow the previously proposed hard knock-on [101] but indeed occupy two degenerate states inside the filter and [124] this leaves the possibility for quantum coherent ion transport in KcsA. For future investigation the methodological improvements as outlined above should be implemented to facilitate detection of quantum resonances.

2.4.2 Discussion of vibrationally assisted ion transport

Single-channel behavior of isotope labeled channels

Conductance and opening rate of isotope labeled and non isotope labeled KcsA were compared using electrophysiology. Considering the differences in experimental setup

⁴If we assume efficiencies of 90% for each additional step the originally $\approx 83\%$ double labeled channels would be further reduced to 67% of double labeled and photoswitchable reconstituted KcsA.

compared to comparable literature (lipid composition and preparation, patch clamp technique etc.) and the analyzed variables, $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labeled KcsA is indistinguishable from WT KcsA without isotope labels (see table 2.5). This is in agreement with previous isotope labeling studies which found that KcsA's function was unimpaired by uniform ^{15}N labeling [195]. The experiments do not provide evidence for a detectable impact of $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ on the conductance and channel dynamics of single channels. The difference in three atomic units and the resulting 50 cm^{-1} shift of isotope labels do not change vibrational behavior of the channel which can be linked to physiological properties. As such, these measurements present a lower experimentally determined level for vibrational changes that do not influence channel function. As isotopes were used as probes for all further experiments in determining influence of vibrational characteristics on potential functional states we can assume the labels to be physiologically "inert". Isotope labels are thus a non-perturbative probe for investigating ion or mutant induced changes in channel behavior via spectroscopic methods as used in this thesis.

Characterization of ion binding related vibrational modes using 1DIR and 2DIR of KcsA

The discussion of the doorway mode analysis was partially published in [153]. The doorway mode analysis showed spectral signatures which can be attributed to different ion binding states and to the alpha-helical region surrounding the selectivity filter. In addition it was shown, that the pore helices carbonyl groups are coupled to the filter's carbonyl groups (see figure 2.31).

Figure 2.31 summarizes distinct spectral signatures that correspond to functionally relevant states within the filter. Na^+ strongly couples the carbonyls of T75 which is in line to an in-plane binding of the ion at this site (figure 2.31 a). K^+ binding largely involves the carbonyl groups of binding site 3 which was shown to strongly exhibit flexibility ("Val76 kicks", figure 2.31 c and d). In addition, the spectral signature for the S3 state (figure 2.31 c) displays strong involvement of E71 on the pore helix. The strongest spectral signature of the pore-helix was shown to be linked to changes in position of the helix with respect to the filter's ion binding state and ion type (figure 2.31 b).

The computational results are strengthened by experimental results of 2DIR of isotope labeled KcsA. The difference spectrum in figure 2.26 A shows that $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}$ labels are detectable in low-frequency regions allowing the more targeted investigation of carbonyl groups of the selectivity filter. The increase in signal strength and decreased ellipticity of the filter point towards increased rigidity of the isotope labeled residues in the presence of K^+ . Although, Na^+ strongly binds to T75 which should rather increase rigidity, the residue was not amongst the isotope labeled carbonyls. Figure 2.26 B shows that even without isotope labels differences in ion type can be detected via 2DIR spectroscopy. All together, the methodologies established in this thesis are an excellent starting point for investigating the behavior of the filter and its surrounding helices.

Mutant KcsA as a proxy for investigating vibrational landscape related to channel function with FTIR spectroscopy

The mutations presented in table 2.12 all impact the direct vicinity of the selectivity filter or the filter itself. Together with the previously established spectral signatures of the filter and pore helices we can now investigate the impact of these mutations. The

FIGURE 2.31: Overview of spectral signatures and potential functional significance of mode analysis. Left: the experimental (dotted) and calculated (black) difference spectra between Na⁺ and K⁺ are shown with spectral signatures denoted a-d. Below the individual states for 1,3/2,4 and Na⁺ are shown in blue, green and red, respectively. a-d shows the doorway mode analysis of the filter and pore helix region alongside the filters ion configuration with involved residues color coded according to their strength of involvement in the spectral signature.

only experimentally observable mutations were E71Q and T75C. T75C removes direct knock-on as binding site S4 has been removed which has been shown to drastically reducing the conductivity. As no ion can bind to S4, no direct coulombic knock-on can occur [148]. The results in figure 2.22 show that this mutant greatly changes the strength of 1620 cm^{-1} mode which was linked to sodium binding to S4. Thus, these results confirm the doorway mode results of 1620 cm^{-1} mode which was mostly attributed to S4 which is missing in T75C. In addition, T75C reduces the intensity of the pore helix mode at 1660 cm^{-1} . This hints to large changes in the pore helix structure by this mutant [148].

E71Q is characterized by showing flickering behavior in electrophysiology behavior, meaning the selectivity filter opens and closes for transduction mediated by increased fluctuations of V76. While these gating modes are on microsecond timescale, the increased flexibility of V76 could be assumed [106, 147]. The results in figure 2.22 show, that the same spectral modes are changed compared to T75C although to a lesser degree. Surprisingly the modes 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} which strongly involve V76 are almost unchanged. This contradicts the assumption, that there is a large change in coupling of the residues involving S3 and as such V76. Nonetheless, the absolute changes of the mutant to wt are much larger compared to changes in wt with different ion concentrations which means, that the pore-helix and S4 site are strongly altered by this mutant.

The experimental investigation by FTIR of mutants seems to yield strong spectral response that can be linked to the characteristic modes identified by doorway mode analysis. As crystal structures are available future studies could prepare doorway mode analysis of these mutants to further decipher the untypically strong changes that were experimentally observed. As the filter modes 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} are not the strongest contributor to the mutants spectra mostly the pore helix and S4 seems to be involved in the mode of action of these mutants. Thus, the following updated hypothesis with a proposed mode of action was derived with testable hypothesis for future experiments.

The M96V mutant is a rapidly inactivating mutant which has lost selectivity. Its crystal structure shows a fixed non-conductive conformation also with high K^+ . Structurally it resembles the collapsed wildtype except for the environment of the pore helix and V76. This mutant might be a suitable candidate to detect K^+ binding in the 1,4 state in the collapsed state [87].

The assumption is that K^+ cannot bind to 2,3 but probably only partially to 1,4. This would test the 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} mode which should not appear this mutant. 1662 cm^{-1} should show lower intensity since 1662 cm^{-1} of 1,3 and 2,4 state is more intense compared to Na^+ bound collapsed state. 1635 cm^{-1} and crosspeak 1635 cm^{-1} , 1662 cm^{-1} should not appear in M96V K^+ wildtype K^+ spectrum as its in a collapsed conformation. Another interesting question would be if V76 is still flexible in vicinity of M96. Furthermore, some features from red modes with involvement of T75 might change due to 1,4 binding of K^+ . The proposed experiment would be to record the difference FTIR of 150mM KCl M96V subtracted from 150mM NaCl wildtype: Is the 1,4 signature comparable to K^+ of wildtype KcsA? Does 1,4 K^+ binding to collapsed channel promote opening and easier access to S2,S3 compared to Na^+ bound collapsed channel?

All 19 substitutions at E71 are very well characterized electrophysiologically and crystal structures of E71I, E71Q, E71A are available [106, 147]. All mutants are K^+ selective and different gating modes can be found in electrophysiology. The transition from and to different modes probably depends on filter flexibility mediated via V76 kicking of the filters backbone carbonyl. E71Q forms a hydrogen bond from the pore

helix to the backbone carbonyls of the filter thus linking the selectivity filter to the surrounding area that was shown to correlate with the spectral signatures determined by doorway mode analysis.

The E71 mutants might thus give vibrational signatures of different conductive states of KcsA that are linked to different time-scales of opening and closing (e.g. flicker modes). Thus, they are a model to study how H-bond coupling to the pore helix might modulate the selectivity filters flexibility related to gating modes. Based on the experimental results of E71Q the modulation of the 1662 cm^{-1} helix mode poses interesting questions: How does the mutations abolishing the H-bond coupling the pore helix to the filter influence pore helix position and overall H-bond probabilities to the selectivity filter in each state? And how does coupling of modes to the pore helix change? Last could be investigated by analyzing cross peaks between the 1662 cm^{-1} mode and the filter modes. Furthermore, how does the delocalization of high frequency modes change with respect to the type of mutation? Why are 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} changing only minutely although very large changes in the helix modes are apparent? Are 1674 cm^{-1} and 1680 cm^{-1} "washed out" in E71Q and other mutants that show high flexibility of V76 as there are higher fluctuations in site energy? A line-shape analysis of the mutants in 2DIR might elucidate the dynamics of the V76 residue.

Wildtype KcsA is usually outward rectified (meaning less and noisier currents exist at a voltage $U < 0\text{mV}$). E71 sidechains H-bond to Y78 coordinates the Y78 main chain carbonyl which might stabilize the pores outer binding site 1. Together with flexible V76 and T75 carbonyls the transport might be easier to towards the exterior of the pore as no such coordination exists at the inside of the pore. E71 mutations exhibit mild inward rectification (E71A) or pronounced inward rectification (E71V). As all mutants abolish the E71-Y78 connection this might be indicative of a functional involvement of this connection. Do changes in the selectivity filters flexibility and coupling upon E71 mutation promote reversal of rectification by modulation of the filters flexibility? The spectral probes determined within this thesis and targeted spectral isotopes probes at E71 or Y78 might help elucidate these problems.

Table 2.32 connects the changes observed in crystal structure with proposed changes in spectral signatures. As the signatures are derived mostly from specific residues, the changes in crystal structures can be used as a proxy of predicting expected changes. The observed spectral changes in T75C and E71Q inform on the magnitude and direction of the change of similar mutants.

cm ⁻¹	1630	1635	1645	1662	1674	1680	Comment
States	Na	1,3	2,4	All	1,3	2,4	
sites involved	T75 E71 W8	E71 W68	T75 E71 W68	Pore helix	T75 E71 V76	G77 V76	
M96V	?	?	?	↓	↓	↓	Always collapsed
E71A				?	↓	↓	Always open but flipped V76 conf in X-Ray
E71I					Like Q but weaker		Less flickery
E71H		↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	Mostly inactive/closed
A73E					?	?	80% open channel

FIGURE 2.32: Hypothesis of spectral signatures of mutants. The table outlines the spectroscopic signature of ion binding states and the sites that are involved based on the doorway mode analysis. It then links these to several mutants that were shown to impact the sites detectable via the spectroscopic signatures. The expected reduction in spectroscopic absorption per signature is given as down-arrows while question marks denote regions that might be impacted or where the direction of change cannot be predicted.

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Chapter 3

Neuronal readout of isotope effects on *C. elegans* oxygen sensing

3.1 Introduction

3.1.1 Sensitivity of allosteric transitions to isotopomers

Control of protein activity on the molecular scale is essential to relay signals effectively which gives rise to cellular function. An intriguing question is if long range delocalized vibrations on the molecular scale contribute to the incredible efficiency with which animals relay minute changes of the environment to make behavioral decisions. The basic principle underlying this directed information dissipation is termed allosteric control and describes how the interaction of a ligand at some site of the protein changes the functionality of a spatially separated site. The concept was introduced in the 60s by Monod, Wyman and Changeux (MWC model) and focused on how the allosteric effect induces conformational changes between two distinct states that resemble the ON and OFF state of a protein. In this way the substrate affinity or catalytic activity of an enzymes substrate binding site is modulated. Hereby, it was thought, that a deterministic, cascading transfer of structural strain dissipated the information from one allosteric site to another [63].

This rather static view was inspired by the static structural snapshots from X-ray crystallography of the highly ordered Hemoglobin molecules. However, as methodological advancements allowed the study of allostery in dynamic or even intrinsically disordered proteins the paradigm shifted towards a more dynamic and stochastic understanding of allosteric action [64, 65]. Instead of being limited to changes between two distinct states it is now thought, that all dynamic proteins are potentially allosteric [67] and act via the full array of known conformational changes [62].

Conformational changes induced by selection of structural vibrations or oscillatory modes of the protein are one example of such dynamic allosteric actions. They act on long-range structural vibrations modes of the protein which originate from the respective forces retaining the structure of individual parts of the protein [196]. Depending on the size and mass of the parts involved, the frequencies of those normal modes can vary from picoseconds for amino acid side-chains to microseconds for inter-domain movements or even seconds for large scale protein rearrangements [65]. Ligands selectively enhance or damp certain modes which changes the pool of conformations the protein can access. This modulates the probability a certain functional conformation (i.e. high affinity substrate binding site) can be accessed by the population of proteins. According to transition-state theory, all conformational states form an energy landscape. The depth of each energy well is directly correlated with the

fraction of the proteins population adopting this state. Interconversion rates between states are dependent on the height of an energy barrier separating two conformations. Population shift occurs if a ligand binding to a protein changes the shape of the energy landscape. Thereby, previously highly occupied conformations are rendered less favorable. If i.e. the proportion of an enzymes active state is reduced in this way also its biochemical activity will be reduced [196].

3.1.2 Hypothesis of sensitivity of allosteric transitions to isotopomers

Vibrational modes proposed to direct biochemical reactions are, amongst others, collective low-frequency, phonon like vibrational modes in the terahertz regime (<3 THz, <100 cm^{-1}) [10]. Their impact on biological systems was first pioneered in the small soluble enzyme lysozyme. Its enzymatic activity was proposed to depend on the ligand-dependent modulation of a highly delocalized hinge-bending mode of the substrate binding cleft [9]. Although, those vibrations were thought to be heavily overdamped in aqueous solutions, recently first experimental evidence of the existence of delocalized vibrational modes in proteins was found in Lysozyme at <100 cm^{-1} . Importantly, the frequency of the concerted conformational fluctuations changed upon ligand binding which establishing the coupling between low-frequency delocalized modes and the reaction coordinate of the protein [66]. Taking into account, that all proteins are thought to be allosteric and use many ways to modulate their function [67] it is valid to ask how general such a mechanism is. Are small changes in the vibrational landscape of a sensory protein sufficient to change the activity of a sensory neuron? Can this mechanism be responsible for some animals extremely sensitive responses to minute changes of the environment? If yes, what are the smallest vibrational energies that can shift the population of a protein towards a different functional state by tuning the shape of its energy surface?

As a top-down qualitative approach to these questions, the experiments below aimed to determine the following: Can small changes in the low-frequency modes of a sensory protein evoke strong enough change in its biochemical activity to evoke a neuronal response that could be perceived as a sensory stimulus in a living animal? For this, isotope labeled ligands of sensory proteins are used to interfere selectively with the vibrational landscape of the protein without changing the chemistry of the interaction. If the output of the sensory system changes notably between isotopomers, this would indicate the possibility of an impact of vibrational effects on perception.

3.1.3 Experimental approach of *C. elegans* as a model organism for studying the influence of isotopomers in chemotaxis

A suitable system to test this vibrational hypothesis on the neuronal level needs to be sensitive to minute changes in the environment. Furthermore, the sensory systems function should depend on a proteins allosteric transitions that could be interpreted by changes in the vibrational landscape of the protein analogous to established models of phonon like modulation of protein function. Hereby, the soil nematode *C. elegans* is an ideal model to study this question, since it exhibits complex behavior and is able to integrate many sensory inputs with astonishing precision despite of only 302 Neurons and 8000 synaptic connections in the whole nervous system. The worms sensory system is able to detect minute temperature gradients [197], mechanosensory stimuli [198], light [199], magnetic fields [56] and a broad range of chemicals. The worms transparency and genetic accessibility allows to record the whole neuronal activity non-invasively by genetically encoded calcium reporters while responding

to changes in the environment [200]. Oxygen sensing is of vital importance for *C. elegans* and thus, the worms respond to minute changes in oxygen concentration of the environment. This reaction routinely serves as a well established paradigm for which behavioral, neuronal as well as molecular details are intensely studied. Due to the worms sensitivity, available literature and methodology, oxygen sensing in *C. elegans* was chosen as a suitable system to answer the above question. For this the difference in neuronal response to $^{16}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}_2$ isotopes was tested in chemosensory neurons of *C. elegans*.

Behavioral and neuronal basis of oxygen sensing in *C. elegans*

FIGURE 3.1: Overview of oxygen sensory neurons in *C. elegans*. (A) Overview of *C. elegans* and location of subset of oxygen sensing neurons with guanylat cyclase genes expressed in the corresponding neurons. Schematic morphology of (B) URX and (C) BAG neurons (pink) close to the pharynx (green) in the head of *C. elegans*. (D) Typical calcium imaging of URX and BAG at 20% O₂. URX is currently active, BAG shows background fluorescence. (A) adapted from [201]. (B-C) adapted from [202]

Oxygen serves as a chemosensory cue for *C. elegans*. Chemosensory cues are important for survival which is underlined by the fact that 5% of all genes and most of its nervous system are used to detect volatile (olfactory) and water-soluble (gustatory) cues from the environment [202]. Based on their association with food, danger, predators or mating partners behavioral responses to chemosensory cues include positive and negative chemotaxis, changes in speed of motility and turning behavior. *C. elegans* senses oxygen in order to find its preferred food *E.coli* bacteria. These prokaryotes deplete oxygen of the soil due to respiration. Thus, the preferred natural habitat of *C. elegans* is at low oxygen concentration (5 to 12% oxygen, optimal 8%). Exposed to very high or very low oxygen environment the worm exhibits an increase in motility in order to escape the unfavorable conditions.

While the worm is in the soil, oxygen permeates its cuticula rendering the inside of the worm in equilibrium with its surrounding oxygen concentration. The oxygen binds then to chemoreceptor molecules which in turn activate the sensory neurons where they are being expressed. Each class of sensory neurons comes in bilaterally symmetric pairs which are similar in cilium, axon and synapse morphology [203] and

express a unique subset of genes for perception and transduction of environmental cues. The neuron classes dedicated to oxygen sensing are most importantly URX, BAG, AQR, and PQR (Gray et al., 2004; Cheung et al., 2005; Chang et al., 2006). URX and BAG are located in the anterior (head) ganglia with the cell bodies located around a nerve ring around the pharynx (see fig.3.1 A). Originating from the pharynx, URX and BAG have cilia projecting to the head of the worm (see fig.3.1 B-C), whereas AQR and PQR cilia endings are exposed to the coelomic body fluid. Together they are thought to measure external and internal oxygen levels, respectively (see fig.3.1 A). Chemoreceptor molecules are concentrated at the tip of these cilia and thus provide a localized measurement. This allows to coordinate affective and aversive behavior to gradual changes in environmental oxygen conditions.

Soluble guanylat cyclase serve as oxygen sensors

Chemosensory proteins translate the concentration of a chemical into a level of biochemical activity which in turn evokes a neuronal response. Usually, chemicals are recognized by proteins that are exposed to the outside of the cell and also in *C. elegans* most chemoreceptors are integral membrane proteins from the family of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs). However, oxygen sensing proteins are special as they are from an unusual protein family of soluble guanylat cyclases (sGC) which resides inside the cell [201]. sGCs are membrane bound proteins which bind gases and send cellular signals by producing second messenger molecules which trigger a signal transduction cascade. In detail, one subunit of sGCs from the H-NOX family binds gases like O₂, CO₂ or NO via a hemoglobin. The binding event triggers allosteric transitions which modulate the activity of an enzymatic subunit synthesizing the second messenger 3',5'-cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) from GTP [204, 205]. The signal is then amplified and transduced by mainly two signal transduction cascades which use either TRPV ion channels or cGMP binding to cGMP-gated ion channels Tax4/Tax2. The resulting increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ levels ultimately leads to a neuronal signal [206]. By modifying the sensitivity of the signal transduction cascade via kinases, phosphatases and globins the response characteristics of the sensory neuron are changed to convey sensory adaption and associative learning [207].

In *C. elegans* several isoforms of sCGs exist whose slight variations in protein sequence allow a differentiated response in second messenger production to the same stimulus. Sensory cell types with unique expression profiles of sCG isoforms thus secure highest sensitivity to small changes across a large concentration range. sCG isoform GCY-33 is expressed solely in BAG whereas most GCY-35 is expressed in URX [208]. URX is activated by an oxygen upshift to aversive hyperoxic environment >15% whereas BAG is activated by oxygen downshifts towards favorable anoxic levels (4-10%) (see fig.3.1 D). Together, both neurons allow the animal to find and tonically stay in preferred oxygen environments.

The changes in sGC activity conveying these changes in neuronal activity are unknown, since no biochemical data is available on the regulation of activity upon O₂ binding for GCY-35 and GCY-33. However, we can get an idea from similar atypical sGCs in *Drosophila* which are activated under anoxic conditions [209]. Anoxic conditions are sensed by *C. elegans* BAG neuron where sCG isoform GCY-33 is expressed. The tonic action of URX and BAG neurons in response to anoxic conditions suggests that GCY-35 and GCY-33 are also reversely activated when exposed to anoxic conditions. In this case in oxygen upshift sensing neuron URX the activity of GCY-35 isoform would decrease in anoxic conditions whereas in the oxygen downshift

sensing neuron BAG GCY-33 activity would increase and behave like the drosophila analogues [209].

C. elegans strains vary highly in their preferred oxygen levels although expressing the same GCY-35 isoforms. The natural variation is conveyed by differences in expression level of the oxygen-binding globin GLB-5 [207]. Globin-5 is a heme like protein that can bind oxygen with high affinity and is expressed in oxygen sensing neurons. Together with GCY-35 and GCY-36 it tunes the dynamic range of oxygen sensitivity and increases O₂-evoked calcium signals [210].

In conclusion, changes in neuronal activity are a complex and convoluted result of multiple dynamically modulated entities along the whole signal transduction cascade. The lack of knowledge and complexity outlined above prevents quantitative statements about how exactly a change in oxygen concentration is conveyed into a neuronal signal. Nonetheless, during steady state changes in neuronal activity have to originate from changes in sCG activity. Neuronal signals induced by exchanging only the isotope content of a compound would thus be a qualitative measures of some change in sCG activity.

Structure and allostery of soluble guanylat cyclases

In order to evoke a neuronal response, an isotope molecule of oxygen has to evoke a change in the output signal of the sCGs big enough to overcome the noise of the transduction pathway and amplification cascade. Isotopomers of oxygen could induce changes in the energy landscape of the oxygen sensing protein and thus induce changes in its activity. Vibrational spectroscopy could hereby provide information on the differences in shape of the energy landscape between isotopes. Furthermore, structural data is used to identify conformers that relate to relevant functional states of the protein.

Unfortunately, the crystalstructure of the *C. elegans* sCGs has not been solved yet. Spectroscopic data is limited to UV/Vis which does not give information on low-frequency modes. In general, sCGs are multidomain proteins which are comprised of a heme NO/oxygen-binding (H-NOX), Per/Arnt/Sim (PAS) and the C-terminal catalytic domain. Oxygen binds to the Heme in the H-NOX domain which triggers an allosteric response mediated by direct inhibitory contacts between the H-NOX and the catalytic domain as well as long range allosteric changes mediated from H-NOX via PAS to the catalytic domains. As an effect, the catalytic domains cGMP conversion rate changes upon oxygen binding which ultimately mediates the neuronal response (see above).

The initial steps triggered by oxygen happen within the gas binding domain, however *C. elegans* sCGs H-NOX domain is not well characterized. In related H-NOX proteins including vibrational spectroscopy and crystallography shows, H-NOX proteins are composed of two subdomains. Oxygen binds the Heme molecule of the oxygen binding subdomain and triggers allosteric changes that translate to the C-terminal subdomain (see figure 3.2) which then relays the signal via long range allosteric changes to the catalytic domain as explained above. The information likely dissipates from the oxygen binding domain via a hinge region (yellow in figure 3.2) to the C-terminal domain.

It was shown, that oxygen activated inter-subdomain displacements relayed via the hinge-region are associated with activation of signaling effector domains. This suggests a link between structural dynamics and protein function [211]. Since hinge-bending modes in Lysozyme [9] were found to be of functional relevance for regulating

enzymatic activity [66] it is intriguing to ask, if the hinge-region in H-NOX proteins could confer allosteric regulation in a similar dynamic manner.

Vibrational Raman spectroscopy of H-NOX proteins

Changes in protein low-frequency dynamics induced by oxygen ligands can be probed by vibrational spectroscopy but no such data of *C. elegans* sCGs H-NOX domains is available. Nonetheless, Raman spectra of bacterial H-NOX domains provide evidence of vibrational changes induced by $^{16}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}_2$. In general, the isotope exchange revealed no major changes in the vibrational landscape of H-NOX domains above $>200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [212]. In the lower frequency region (200 to 1000 cm^{-1}) isotope substitution induces only one pronounced shift at 567 cm^{-1} in the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{O}_2$ stretching mode. A shift of 26 cm^{-1} is measured upon exchange of $^{16}\text{O}_2$ to $^{18}\text{O}_2$. This is in accordance with a downshift of 21 cm^{-1} as predicted for a simple harmonic oscillator model of $\nu(\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{O}_2)$. A downshift of this vibration corresponds to an isotope induced weakening of the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{O}_2$ bond strength [212] which is in accordance with classical isotope effects [213, 214].

No $^{18}\text{O}_2$ spectrum is available for skeletal modes in the range of 1000 to 1800 cm^{-1} which are sensitive to differences in the heme macrocycle core size and conformation of the protein. It is thus unknown if isotope substitution induces novel conformations or changes hemes planarity and its coupling to surrounding residues. These measurements would be indicators of allosteric transitions triggered by $^{18}\text{O}_2$. However, even if spectral changes could be found in biochemical essays, the functional significance for perception could not be answered. We thus took a top-down approach to see to what degree minute changes on the biochemical level can propagate to the organismic level.

3.2 Material & Methods

3.2.1 Gaussian network model analysis of dynamics in H-NOX proteins

Domain separation by dynamics was calculated using the the Gaussian network model database for biomolecular structural dynamics (iGNM 2.0) [215]. The PDB structure of an H-NOX protein from *S. oneidensis* in the $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ ligation state (PDB accession code: 4U99) with high (35%) similarity to *C. elegans* sGC GCY-33 and GCY-35 was analyzed on the online platform <http://gnmdb.csb.pitt.edu/>. Slow eigenvectors of all chains were calculated and results visualized in PYMOL.

FIGURE 3.2: Structure and oxygen binding in H-NOX proteins. Crystal structure of an H-NOX protein with the Heme molecule (blue) complexed by a Histidin residue (white). Oxygen (red) is directly binding to the Hemes iron (brown). The dynamic flexibility of the proposed hinge region (yellow) is supported by domain separation according to the signs of the eigenvectors of the lowest normal mode (colored green and purple, respectively). PDB accession code: 4U99

3.2.2 Crossing of imaging wormline

In order to have a *C. elegans* wormline expressing a GECI in a Glb-5 background, N2 males of the imaging line ZIM226 expressing GCaMP5K in URX and BAG neurons were crossed with glb5 hermaphrodites. The Glb-5 background was chosen to optimize the sensitivity range of the worm to low oxygen concentrations [207]. The offspring was identified by culturing worms exhibiting both fluorescence in URX and BAG neurons, as well as glb-5 positive band on PCR analysis. The PCR primers and genotyping protocol was adapted from [207].

3.2.3 Oxygen delivery setup

$^{18}\text{O}_2$ was bought from CK-Isotopes in the highest available purity and an enrichment of 98%. The oxygen was delivered to a custom-fabricated two-layer PDMS microfluidic device [201]. A LABVIEW script regulating Red-Y (Voegtlin) mass flow controller and miniature piloting solenoid valves (The Lee Company) was used to change Oxygen flow or to switch between different oxygen gas channels, respectively. The oxygen was mixed with N_2 to keep the overall flow at constant 50 mL min^{-1} and directly delivered to the setup. By changing the bottle leading to the mass flow controller the oxygen species was changed. To differentiate between oxygen species in a single continuous measurement each oxygen species was attached to a calibrated mass flow controller of similar type.

Only one oxygen species was delivered to the imaging setup at any time, with the other species flowing to a similar dummy setup (see figure 3.4) to keep pressures between the two channels as comparable as possible. For this purpose each oxygen mass controller was attached to the input of one of two separate controllable three-way solenoid valve. Without applied voltage on the solenoid $^{16}\text{O}_2$ flow was directed to the normally open output of the solenoid which in turn was connected to a T-connector to mix oxygen with N_2 to yield a constant flow rate. This mixture was led to the gas inlet of the imaging device via another T-connector. $^{18}\text{O}_2$ flow was channeled in similar manner through the other solenoid valve but was mixed with CO_2 and delivered to the dummy setup. The normally closed outlets of both solenoids were connected to the inlet of the respective other imaging or dummy setup thus pressurizing the normally closed outlet. By applying a constant voltage of 12 V to both solenoids $^{18}\text{O}_2$ was now exiting the normally closed outlet, mixed with N_2 and directed to the imaging setup while $^{16}\text{O}_2$ was led to the dummy setup. The tubing connecting all components was polyethylene (0.066 in ID, 0.005 in OD; Intramedic) or Tygon tubing (0.02 in ID, 0.06 in OD; Norton) joined by 23G Luer-stub adapters (Intramedic) and low-pressure T-connectors and fittings (BioRad). Glb-5 Background, oxygen concentrations and downshift protocols were designed to take place at low oxygen concentrations in order to save expensive $^{18}\text{O}_2$ while simultaneously ensuring high neuronal sensitivity to small changes in concentration.

3.2.4 Imaging setup

Animals were maintained under standard conditions (on food, 20 degree Celsius) before and during the experiment. Young adult worms with 1- to 4-eggs were fixated in a narrow S-shaped bottleneck in the microfluidic chamber to align the worms laterally facilitating reproducible neuronal recordings from the same perspective [200, 201]. A constant flow of buffer S-basal supplemented with bacteria at an OD_{600} of 0.6 and 5 mM of the mildly paralyzing acetylcholine receptor-specific agonist tetramisole was applied to reduce motion-artifacts. The microscope used was upright Axio imager

microscope (Zeiss) with a standard GFP filter set and EMCCD camera (C9100-13, Hamamatsu). To avoid scattering, the focus of the microscope was chosen to record fluorescence only from neurons closest to the objective. Fluorescence traces were analyzed with a custom MATLAB script.

O₂ levels inside the worm chamber were determined by using a Ruthenium dye (SIGMA) at 120 mM. Fluorescence was acquired on a upright Fluorescence microscope with a standard mCherry filter cube. Analysis of the fluorescence traces was carried out in FIJI and Matlab.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Structural dynamics of H-NOX proteins by normal mode analysis

In order to verify the choice of sGCs as a suitable model system to test for allosteric changes based on delocalized modes a normal mode analysis using a gaussian network model was applied [215]. Specifically, we sought out to determine if hinge-bending modes previously found to be of functional relevance for regulating enzymatic activity [9, 66] could exist in sCGs. Thus, the lowest normal mode of a H-NOX protein was calculated and subdomains were separated based on the direction of the vibrations eigenvector. The results in figure 3.2 show a clear separation of the domain at the previously identified hinge-region. This means, that considerable flexibility exists across this hinge and the two subdomains dynamically translate with respect to each other. As outlined above, the hinge region was linked to allosteric control of enzymatic activity based on static crystallographic evidence [211]. In line with allosteric control by low-frequency vibrations [9, 66] this analysis showed, that the enzymatic ON/OFF states identified by crystallography [211] are likely in a dynamic equilibrium coupled by a low-frequency vibration across the hinge-region.

3.3.2 Experimental measurement of neuronal responses to isotope substitution

To resolve differences in neuronal activity between the isotope species ¹⁶O₂ and ¹⁸O₂ mainly two different experimental approaches schemes were applied. The *direct* approach measured the absolute neuronal response to shifts in oxygen concentration within each isotope species. Subsequent subtraction of activation levels revealed changes in neuronal activation between the two species. In this case, the absolute output of the activation of sCGs by oxygen shifts was measured for each oxygen species and was later compared. The *differential* approach kept the oxygen concentration constant and switched the isotope species only while measuring the neuronal activity. If all other parameters would stay constant this method would be the most sensitive to isotope induced changes in neuronal activation.

3.3.3 Direct determination of isotope effect of oxygen isotopomers

In the direct method the effect of isotopes is determined by measuring the change in peak fluorescence encoding neuronal activity between different oxygen species after a shift in the respective oxygen concentration. For this purpose, worms are equilibrated in a certain concentration of oxygen and the fluorescent response to a small oxygen shift is compared to a similar response with another oxygen species. The responses to isotopes are recorded consecutively by switching the supply oxygen bottle while leaving the rest of the setup unaltered. No valves and only two mass flow controllers are

FIGURE 3.3: PMDS flow chamber design and imaging results of consecutive isotope stimuli. (A) a) Scheme of the microfluidic chamber. The worm is loaded and immobilized in the red channel and gas delivered via the blue channel. a') Cross-section of a) indicating gas delivery via the poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) layer. a'') phase-contrast image of an immobilized worm with the head fixed at a defined location at the bottom of the S-curve. The worm's ventral side is indicated by the blue arrow. Adapted from [200]. (B) Calcium imaging of BAG neurons in response to oxygen downshifts with different oxygen isotopes. Measurements of neuronal activity as percent change of gCaMP5 fluorescence ($\Delta F/F_0$) averaged over multiple animals. Oxygen downshifts were applied from 10–80 s as indicated in the inset and afterwards switched off, allowing for atmospheric oxygen to diffuse in. (C) Integrated change in fluorescence of stimulus period 10–80 s with same color code as in (B). The number of recorded animals is indicated. (Error bars = SEM. ns = not significant. **p = 0.001–0.01, ***p < 0.001, one-way ANOVA test). (D) Typical URX neuron from recordings of (B) shows no response to small downshift but to oxygen upshift after the experiment.

used which reduces the size and complexity and increases reliability of the setup. After the animals were equilibrated 300 s at 9% oxygen concentration small downshifts of 0.5%, 1% and 1.5% were applied to individual animals. The resulting averaged neuronal responses of BAG neurons are shown in fig. 3.3 B. The integrated fluorescence (fig. 3.3 C) shows that downshifts of 1% of both oxygen isotopes elicit similar responses in *C. elegans* and cannot be discriminated from 0.5% downshifts. Only 1.5% downshifts can be discriminated from smaller downshifts. Fig. 3.3 D shows that URX neurons behave normally to an increase of oxygen concentration in the range investigated. This showed, that the setup cannot discriminate changes below 0.5% change in oxygen concentration. Isotopes do not induce changes that are above this detection threshold.

3.3.4 Differential determination of isotope effect of oxygen isotopomers

In this setup oxygen flow of both isotope species was kept at constant flow and concentration with only one of the isotopes reaching the immobilized worm. Then, electromechanically operated solenoid valves switched between the species (see scheme in fig. 3.4 A). The stimulus protocol (see fig. 3.4 B) was optimized to allow for equilibrated $^{18}\text{O}_2$ flow before switching the solenoids to record only the differential response to the new oxygen species. Changes in fluorescence should be attributable to isotope effects only in case all other parameters stayed constant. To quantitatively determine the degree of change in fluorescence upon isotope exchange the response to known oxygen concentration shifts were acquired. For this, the isotope experiments were followed by controlled up- and downshifts in $^{16}\text{O}_2$. With this the percentage of oxygen shift corresponding to an amount of fluorescence change during the $^{18}\text{O}_2$ experiment was determined.

In order to carry out this experiment, constant conditions upon switching of isotope species had to be ensured. Thus, extensive characterization of the setup was carried out to determine the systematic errors of the setup. To increase precision of the measurement, two constant streams of $^{16}\text{O}_2$ from the same gas bottle were switched during characterization and oxygen concentration was measured by a oxygen sensitive fluorescent Ruthenium dye. The three-port valves switched upon application of 12 V within approx. 4 ms the outflow between two outlet ports of oxygen species. The valves are designed to provide reliable switching behavior only against a constant pressure on each outlet channel. Connecting the outlet valve directly to air lead did not provide a pressure at the outlet matching the pressure fed in and thus led to malfunction of the valves. This became apparent due to drastic neuronal responses of the worm. The artifact was ameliorated by providing backpressure on the currently closed outlet valves via a dummy setup (see asterisks in 3.4 A). Flow of CO_2 was used to create backpressure and as expected its flowrate strongly influenced the degree of systematic artifacts while switching the valves (see figure 3.4 C). At a flow of 3.75 mL CO_2 switching between the same oxygen concentration and species produced the minimal possible artifact, corresponding to a downshift of 0.53% (see fig. 3.4 C). All further experiments were carried out with this systemic limitation in place.

After the worm was equilibrated for 300 s at a constant flow of $^{16}\text{O}_2$ the other mass flow controller was set to the same flow of $^{18}\text{O}_2$ (or $^{16}\text{O}_2$ for controls) up to 20 s before the experiment to stabilize the flow. 10 s after the optical readout was started the valves were switched for 50 s. After switching back to $^{16}\text{O}_2$, flow of $^{18}\text{O}_2$ was shut down and recording of neuronal activity was continued for control experiments with

$^{16}\text{O}_2$ (see schematic example fig. 3.4 A). Afterwards the animal was replaced and the procedure repeated.

The resulting traces of neuronal activity averaged over multiple animals while switching from $^{16}\text{O}_2$ to $^{18}\text{O}_2$ or $^{16}\text{O}_2$ are depicted in fig. 3.4 D as purple and green lines, respectively. During the experiment (grey background) a short transient peaks between 10 and 20 s is followed by a large slowly decaying peak in neuronal activity until 60 s. The first peak can be attributed most likely to short pressure fluctuation due to the rapid movement of the pistons inside the solenoid valves. The overall average response to changes in oxygen species is shown in Fig3.4 E. By integrating the fluorescent signal from 20 to 60 s the absolute strength in neuronal response between isotope species was quantified. No significant difference was found between the different oxygen species.

FIGURE 3.4: Transient switching between oxygen species. (A) $^{16}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}_2$ flows via two three-way switches at 0V to the imaging setup and dummy setup, respectively (top) or vice versa with 12V applied (bottom). The closed channel of the switches (*) are pressurized at all times (grey lines) to ensure reproducible switching behavior. (B) Recording of flow rates of mass controllers during shortened experimental delivery protocol. During equilibration (-20 to 0 s), setpoints of $^{16}\text{O}_2$ -valve (lightgreen) are matched with corresponding $^{16}\text{O}_2$ -flow. Setting the $^{18}\text{O}_2$ -valve to the same value at -5 s leads to temporary peaks in flow-rate during startup (purple trace). After equilibration of $^{18}\text{O}_2$ flow the solenoids are switched at $t=0$ s and the response recorded between 0-5 s. Afterwards, $^{18}\text{O}_2$ flow is shut down and control experiments of small up and downshifts are recorded with $^{16}\text{O}_2$. (C) Measurement of artifacts introduced by switching between two $^{16}\text{O}_2$ channels as a function of backpressure on closed valves in ml/min flow of CO_2 . The smallest systematic error found is indicated as a red dot. (D) Calcium imaging of BAG neurons at constant oxygen level in response to switching within or between oxygen species ($^{16}\text{O}_2$ to $^{16}\text{O}_2$: green, $^{16}\text{O}_2$ to $^{18}\text{O}_2$: purple). Measurements of neuronal activity as percent change of gCaMP5 fluorescence ($\Delta F/F_0$) averaged over multiple animals. (E) Integrated change in fluorescence from traces in (D) (same colorcode, p-value = 0.26, paired t-test).

3.4 Discussion of neuronal readout of isotope effects on *C. elegans* oxygen sensing

3.4.1 Systematic errors of experimental setups

The neuronal readout of the experiments were a measure for rate constants of sGCs in complex with $^{16}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}_2$. The two approaches applied to dissect this difference came with serious limitations. The direct method was inherently less sensitive to reveal small differences because two large values of two independent measurements had to be subtracted. The independent measurements However, the hardware and tubing of the setup is less complex and thus worked reliably without noticeable systematic artifacts which increased the precision and reproducibility of the individual stimuli.

Switching from one isotope to another while keeping all other parameters constant is the most sensitive method to discriminate small effects in neuronal activation by different isotopes. Changes in the activity of the sGCs upon binding of an oxygen isotope would directly translate to a change in neuronal activation read out by fluorescence. Although, this is the more elegant approach, it sets high requirements for stability and reproducibility to the setup. To obtain the highest sensitivity, the oxygen species have to be exchanged as quick as possible without changing any other parameters of the setup. Thus, the setup was designed as small as possible to avoid dead volumes which would delay the time of exchange between different oxygen species. Furthermore, the tubing was symmetric for both isotope species to have the same volume between the mass flow controller and experiment for both oxygen species. The easiest way to exchange isotopes would have been to increase flow of $^{18}\text{O}_2$ while decreasing $^{16}\text{O}_2$ and vice versa. The mass flow controllers used for this experiment were from the same build type and were very stable in supplying a constant flow of oxygen. However, transitions between different setpoints - especially during startup or shutdown - differed significantly between all mass flow controllers tested. Thus, it was not possible to transiently switch between oxygen species by simultaneously ramping up and/or down flowrates of mass flow controllers. Ramping in many very small, discrete steps (i.e. x-times 0.1% within a minute) increased reproducibility, however also reduced the measurable neuronal response of worms, due to their adaptation to slowly changing oxygen concentrations. These factors ruled out the easiest possibility to change between the channels by switching flow of e.g. $^{16}\text{O}_2$ off while simultaneously switching $^{18}\text{O}_2$ on.

The more complex solution used for switching between oxygen species used microfluidics three-way solenoids. They have low internal volume and fast switching times as required for this experiment. However, it has to be guaranteed that both valves switch synchronous and the switching times of both valves are the same. Asynchronous switching leads to flow of either none, or both oxygen channels to the experiment resulting in transient oxygen down- or upshifts, respectively. Switching the valves itself was found to elicit a short neuronal response in the extremely pressure sensitive worms (see spike in figure 3.3 D). This might be caused either by the mass flow controller building up pressure during the dead time of the valves or more likely due to a transient shock wave which is typically created by the rapid movement of the piston inside the valves as. To ameliorate shock waves, slower switching times could be applied by using lower voltages on the solenoids. But this would increase dead times, block oxygen flow and thus create artificial oxygen downshifts. Additionally, the switch time of the solenoids is strongly influenced by the pressure difference between the two outlet channels. Moving the piston against a low pressure is quicker compared to movement against a higher pressure. The systematic error introduced

by switching between identical gas flows changed drastically depending on the pressure difference of the outlet valves (fig 3.3 C). The resulting systematic artifacts are considerable compared to the errors in the direct method, but even extensive testing of modifications did not result in better solutions.

3.4.2 Vibrational effects compared to classical isotope effects

The sensitivity of the direct approach allowed to discriminate differences not smaller than 0.5% and showed no significant differences in neuronal activation between isotopes of oxygen within these limits. The differential setup exhibited a systematic error which elicited a neuronal response indistinguishable between the two oxygen species tested (fig 3.3 D and E). To put these results and the specificity of the setup into perspective we draw parallels to classical kinetic isotope effects (KIE) which are well established in their ability to modulate the reaction speed of enzymatic reactions. ^{18}O isotope labels directly involved in enzymatic catalysis can modulate an enzymes catalysis rate by 4% [214] and are usually determined *in vitro* due to the higher sensitivity to changes in the reaction coordinate. In sCGs however, the isotope labeled oxygen is not directly involved in the enzymatic catalysis of second messenger molecules but merely acts as a remote allosteric effector at the ligand binding site.

Thus, the change in association strength of one oxygen to the Heme molecule as shown by the Raman shift in the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}-\text{O}_2$ line gives a good estimate of the expected amount of the KIE in sGCs. The magnitude of isotope effects on the level of enzymatic activity is directly proportional to the mass difference between the isotopes.

A rule of thumb for heavy atom isotope effects is that the maximum isotopic rate ratio scales with the squareroot of the isotopes masses inverse ratio [213]. This means, the expected isotope effect for exchanging ^{16}O to ^{18}O would be $^{16}k/^{18}k = \sqrt{18/16} = 1.06$. Simply put, with the same amount of oxygen molecules present at the H-NOX 6% more ^{16}O than $^{18}\text{O}_2$ molecules will be bound to the heme.

6% better binding of ^{16}O to the Heme of the H-NOX domain. In this case, after equilibration of the worm at 9% $^{16}\text{O}_2$, a worm at the same concentration of $^{18}\text{O}_2$ would have the heme occupancy corresponding to 9.54% $^{16}\text{O}_2$. A oxygen downshift of 1% from 9 to 8% $^{18}\text{O}_2$ would correspond to an apparent shift of 9.54 to 9.48% using $^{16}\text{O}_2$. The difference of heme-occupancy would be the isotope effect $(9.54 - 8.48) - (9 - 8) = 0.06\%$. This estimation shows, that the sensitivity to changes of 0.5% is about an order of magnitude too inaccurate to discriminate classical isotope effects. Considering the convoluted and heavily integrated fluorescent readout used in this experiment, it is remarkable, that the setup with living animals is not too far away of detecting very subtle effects which usually require *in vitro* experiments. On the other hand, allosteric effects caused by changes in low-frequency, phonon-like modes need to be at least 10 times more pronounced than the discussed KIE in order to have a detectable signal with these setups. Since no significant change in the neuronal response of the worm to isotopomers was determined, isotopomer induced allosteric effects in low frequency modes are either absent or change neuronal activity by less than 0.5%.

It is assumed, that the strength of oxygen binding to the heme group translates to the degree of change in the enzymatic rate constant of cGMP production via allosteric changes in the protein. Experimental measurement of the change in dissociation constants of oxygen isotopes or the indirect change in rate of cGMP catalysis in GCY-35 or GCY-33 is difficult and involves highly artificial reconstituted systems. However, the isotope effect - if big enough - is amplified by the second messenger pathway and might become measurable via much less intrusive change in fluorescence

of a calcium sensor. Furthermore, this approach provides the information if minute isotope effects are perceptible by the organism on a neuronal level or if they are buried in the noise of the preceding biochemical pathways.

The most likely scenarios how the isotope label impacted protein function in addition to the above described KIE are as follows: a) The weight difference of isotopomers are too small to change the low frequency modes significantly. Low frequency modes involve whole domain motions. The subdomains of H-NOX proteins separated by the lowest normal mode (see fig. 3.2) weigh already more than 10 kDa. This is ~5000 times the weight introduced by the isotope label. An allosteric effect due to isotope labels would need to shift a delicate balance between two functionally relevant protein populations which is unlikely to be maintained in the presence of thermal fluctuations on the same magnitude of the low frequency mode itself (Energy of thermal noise at 300 K is approximately 25 meV while energy of 3 THz low freq modes is 12 meV). Such delicate balance would mean in practice, that the allosteric switch is very leaky and activates stochastically most of the times without detecting an oxygen binding event. The worm would have significant disadvantages in oxygen sensitivity due to many false positive detection events. b) The isotopomers chosen in the experiment modulate a subset of low frequency modes which are not allosterically tuning the enzymatic activity of sCGs. c) The change in sCG activity due to allosteric control by isotopomers is existent, but too small compared to the noise of subsequent second messenger pathways. As an effect, the isotope-induced allosteric signal did not induce a measureable change of the integrated fluorescent signal of the neuron.

In order to ameliorate the problems outlined above, future experiments should increase the mass difference during association by using bigger ligands and focusing on changes between ligated and unligated states instead of using isotopomers. This is exemplified by the fact, that Turton et al. found an impact on low frequency modes by inducing a mass changes during ligand association ~300 times bigger compared to ^{16}O to ^{18}O exchange. Once suitable ligands are identified, their impact on phonon-like modes could be characterized spectroscopically *in vitro* with purified components. Sensitive enzymatic essays should be used to demonstrate the ligands impact on activity while eliminating the ambiguity of convoluted fluorescent readouts in behaving animals. By determining the enzymatic activity levels in dependence of the ligands weight, one could map the energy wells depth separating the two allosteric populations of active and inactive state. The characterized system can then be reconstituted into living animals to investigate the noise of the signal transduction cascade and finally the relevance of low frequency modes for perception and behavior.

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Chapter 4

Brain dynamics as a readout for quantum tunneling in olfaction

4.1 Introduction

4.1.1 Missing origin of olfactory processing in vertebrates

Our senses can be described as the process of perceiving environmental cues in sensory proteins which translate the stimulus to intracellular chemical signals which are then relayed by cell signaling. In higher organisms sensory neurons transform this environmentally induced intracellular chemical signal to an electro-chemical signal which is processed by a neuronal network to create a sensation. The type of sensory protein is determines the type of environmental stimulus that can be perceived by this sense. Olfaction acquires chemical information from the external world by specialized olfactory receptor proteins (OR) expressed in olfactory sensory neurons (OSNs) of the olfactory epithelium (OE). ORs belong to the superfamily of approx. 1000 members of G-protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) which are transmembrane proteins that amplify a specific extracellular signal by activating an intracellular signaling pathways via a G-protein [216]. Each OR responds to multiple odors sharing a chemical property of odorants [217]. Since only one type of OR is expressed per OSN, these neurons activity encode the chemicals recognized by the OR. In case of a sensory input to the OR the OSN is activated and the activity of all OSNs is integrated to a sensation of smell by higher brain areas.

In this way, the olfactory system is able to distinguish many thousand odors [218], but the molecular mechanism of odorant reception in the GPCR is unknown up to date. Initially, it came naturally to mind to draw the analogy to vision and hearing, where the sensation is created by individual receptors detecting different spectral bands of a complex spectrum. The proposal, that vibrations in the infrared give a characteristic smell to a molecule was pioneered by Dyson [219, 220] and expanded by Wright [221] but the basic idea dates back to the 1870s [222]. Later, an alternative shape theory of olfaction emerged building on insights from shaped-based molecular interactions in biological systems [223] which proposed that size, shape and functional groups of the odorant molecule are responsible for its characteristic smell [224]. After the discovery of the odorant receptor proteins [225] it is now widely believed, that physicochemical attributes of distinct structural classes of odorants are recognized similar to the 'key-and-lock' mechanism leaving the vibrational theory [226, 227] largely ignored by the chemosensory community [228, 229]. Nonetheless, a crystal structure of the ORs does not exist up to date which leaves the molecular origin of the interaction, binding site and activation elusive and vividly debated.

4.1.2 Theory of vibrational molecular mechanism of olfactory receptors

The most prominent advocate of the vibrational theory of olfaction today is Luca Turin, who - while working in the perfume industry - was intrigued by the finding, that some very similar smelling odorants have very different molecular shapes, but similar spectral characteristics. He proposed a mechanism sensitive to spectral changes in the IR-frequency and compatible with the molecular nature of the ORs GPCRs based on a quantum effect called phonon-assisted electron tunneling [226, 227, 230]. The basic idea is, that activation of ORs occurs via electron transfer across a molecule with vibrational modes with energies matching an energy gap in the receptors odorant binding site (see fig.4.1). The energy gap can be formed between an electron donor like NADPH and a metallic acceptor like Zn^{2+} inside the binding site and blocks electrons from traversing to the acceptor (fig.4.1 A). After binding of an odorant molecule the electrons loses energy when exciting a vibrational mode of the odorant molecule which matches the energy gap. Then the electron tunnels to the electron acceptor, which otherwise would be insulated from the electron donor (fig.4.1 B). Finally, the electron activates a signal transduction pathway by i.e. reducing a disulfide bond of the G-protein interface of the GPCR [226].

The protein sequence of different subtypes of ORs varies slightly which results in variations in the electrostatic environment of the binding pocket. As a result, the varying size of the energy gap allows detection of molecules with different vibrational energies. Functioning at ambient or body temperature limits the minimum width of the energy gap to at least $2kT$ (with $T = 300\text{ K}$) which corresponds to a resolution of approx. 400 cm^{-1} . Analogous to the visual system where three receptors with detuned perceptive fields cover the entire visible spectrum, a series of only 10 broadly tuned receptors overlapping in their spectral range could cover the entire range of the relevant vibrational spectrum from $0\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [226]. Based on this, an experimental test of the theory was postulated by introducing a change in the vibration of an odorant. If the spectral shift is bigger than the width of the proposed receptive field this should lead to a different odor perception while keeping its shape unchanged. This is easiest accomplished by using isotopes which change the mass and thus vibrational frequency, but not size and electronic properties of a molecule (see also chapter 2). Hereby, the vibrational frequency changes proportional to the square root of the change in mass. Deuteration provides the largest change in reduced mass per modified atom and shifts the frequency of a C-H bond by approx. 600 cm^{-1} which is more than the proposed resolution of the receptors (see above). As a result, a different

FIGURE 4.1: Principle of vibrationally assisted olfaction. (A) Without a ligand electrons are unable to tunnel across an energy gap in the OR binding site. (B) An odorant molecule with the vibrational energy $\hbar\omega_0 = \Delta E$ enhances electron tunneling. (C) Schematic depiction of overlapping receptive fields of five ORs each with a characteristic frequency associated to their maximum electron tunneling rates. The subset of receptors activated by e.g. a C-H Bond (green) changes after shifting the frequency by deuteration (purple).

subset of ORs should be activated creating a different smell (see fig.4.1 C).

4.1.3 Previous experimental approaches utilizing isotope effects

This vibrational theory is heavily debated in the literature since the mode of odorant-receptor interaction is yet to be elucidated (see figure 4.2). Unlike originally proposed [226] isotope effects were not found to impact smell in humans [236]. However, later discrimination tests for isotopomers of acetophenone were found successful in fruit flies [238] and honeybees [239]. Thus Gane *et al.* [237] revisited human isotope experiments and presented evidence for perceptual differences of isotopomers of musk odorants in humans. However, the experiments in humans and animals were fundamentally criticized for using perceptual experiments alone to test fundamental subatomic mechanisms of OR ligand-receptor interactions [229, 233, 235]. In order to be closer to the molecular origin of smell, Block *et al.* recently investigated isotope effects on the OR level [233]. They identified and reconstituted a human musk receptor OR5AN1 in a heterologous OR expression system and biochemically measured its activation in response to isotopomers of its ligand muscone. The results showed no changes in OR activation by isotopomers. In addition they found chemical impurities between isotopes in the odorants of Ganes *et al.* behavioral studies. The conclusion was, that the impurities and not isotopes triggered the reported differences in perception. Furthermore, they provided theoretical evidence that Turins electron tunneling mechanism is easily suppressed in biological environments like GPCRs. Proteins exhibit dynamic fluctuations, disorder and possess significant quantum vibrational modes in the acceptor and donor site. These impact electron-transfer kinetics on the same order of magnitude as the amplification of small vibrational effects as proposed by Turin [233].

In addition, enzymatic conversions of odorants in the mucus of humans are susceptible to secondary isotope effects. This results in different mixtures of metabolites in the OR for isotopomers of the same chemical [240]. Taking into account, that the conversion of odorants in the mucus is fast enough to affect olfactory perception [232]

FIGURE 4.2: Key steps in olfaction and relevant studies. This study investigates on the neuronal level if the sensory system is sensitive enough to perceive small changes in isotopic content.

the perceived differences in smell of isotopomers of musk in humans could be solely due to perireceptor events and do not provide evidence for changes in tunneling rates in GPCRs [233]. Turin admitted to impurities but objected by pointing out that a series of negative results leaves the possibility that maybe another, yet unidentified OR might be responsible for the discrimination of isotopomers in humans. Also all OR activity measurements of Block *et al.* were taken from tissue culture cells which might have an unfavorable environment for electron transport chains as originally proposed due to lacking crucial cofactors [234]. Thus, conclusive experiments would best require the native OE and ORs.

4.1.4 Experimental approach for inducing isotopes effects in the olfactory system *in vivo*

Neuronal classification as a readout for isotope sensitivity

Repeating Blocks *et al.* *in vitro* measurement *in situ* or *in vivo* by determining OR activity directly in the OSNs of the OE would need major technical improvements. An experimental approach would be to target the state-of-the-art *in vitro* Luciferase reporter construct for ORs [241] used by Block *et al.* selectively to the OSNs of a living organism [242] which has not been accomplished yet. However, studying neuronal activation and classification are *in vivo* experiments, that have not been used as a way to test for sensitivity to isotope effects in the olfactory system (see figure 4.2). Measuring changes in the neural activity in the Zebrafish OB to infer information on odor percepts is an established methodology [243–246]. The neuronal networks in the olfactory bulb amplify small changes in OR activation by forming distinct neuronal activity patterns [245]. This highly sensitive and specialized system can amplify otherwise small changes in OR activation to experimentally *in vivo* detectable levels. The OSNs activity thereby varies only slightly between similar odorants but subtle changes of OR activity are amplified and classified *in vivo* by the pattern classification system of the higher processing center called the olfactory bulb (OB) [245].

Thus, this thesis tests if isotopomers of olfactory stimuli can be classified to distinct neuronal output patterns in the olfactory bulbs pattern recognition system. This would show, that the differences between isotopomers are big enough to be of relevance to the neuronal systems dedicated for generating stable output patterns representing different smells in Zebrafish. The inherent non-linear response of the OB output to changes in odor identity (see right figure 4.4) filters chemical changes that are non-discriminable to the system. As such, this analysis provides insight into the threshold of olfaction while it closes a gap in the currently available literature on isotope effect in the olfactory system (see figure 4.2). Results could be of relevance for the perceptual and behavioral level as they depend on the sensory systems output. However, studies on the neuronal level can not exclude potential perireceptor events in the fish's mucus [231, 232, 247], nor provide molecular evidence for GPCR activation by vibrationally assisted electron tunneling. Nonetheless, these unique experiments use the relevant neuronal populations to integrate and classify the change in OR activity due to isotopomers *in vivo* in the natural tissues and brain regions of behaving animals as proposed in previous studies [233–235].

Neuroanatomy and olfactory processing of the Zebrafish brain

The anatomy and odor processing is exemplified based on Zebrafish larvae, a genetically accessible and well understood model animal (see figure 4.3). Basic features of this system are conserved throughout higher mammals and the developing Zebrafish

FIGURE 4.3: Olfaction in Zebrafish. (A) Dorsal overview of a 5-7 dpf Zebrafish larvae. (B) Dorsal and (C) lateral view of Zebrafish larval brain anatomy (magnification of grey box in (A)). OB: olfactory bulb, TE: Telencephalon, OT: Optitectum, C: Cerebellum, MO: medulla oblongata, H: Hippocampus. gray area: anterior part of forebrain (FB). (D) Frontal view from Rostal to Caudal, showing the OE and its projections to the OB via the Cranial Nerve I (arrowhead) in a 4 dpf larvae stained with anti-acetylated tubulin antibody. Ey: eye. (E) Schematic of neuronal computation in the boxed region in (D). Each type of OSNs projects via the cranial nerve I to a separate Glomerulus (GL, dotted circles) of the OB. Here, mitral cells (MC) and inhibitory interneurons called granule cells (GC) integrate signals and amplify differences for processing in higher order brain regions [248]. D and E modified from <http://zebrafishbrain.org/>

brain: The sensory information of the OSNs is transmitted directly to the first olfactory processing centre of the brain, the olfactory bulb (OB) [249] (see fig.4.3 A-C). All information of one type of OSN converges from the OE to the first basic modules in information processing, spherical structures called the glomeruli [250] (fig.4.3 D-E). Since one odor can activate multiple ORs [218], odor information is represented as discrete glomerular response patterns, thereby forming a coarse chemotopic organization [218, 243, 251]. After the OB amplified small differences between odors as discrete network states [245] the information is sent by mitral cells to higher brain areas to construct the odor perception [244, 252, 253] (fig.4.3 E).

FIGURE 4.4: Olfactory pattern discrimination in neuronal space. The high-dimensional neuronal space is represented using three dimensions with each axis representing the factors contributing most to the variance of the system in decreasing order (Principle component, PC). (A) The network converges from the baseline to similar output patterns for similar odors (odorants X&Y). (B) If odors are dissimilar enough the system converges towards a new output state (odorants X&Z). (C) A quantifiable measure representing "dissimilarity" is the euclidean distance in PCA-space between output states of the network. Network states change non-linearly between stable output patterns depending on the dissimilarity of odors.

Modified from [245]

By measuring the neuronal signals of OB and TE neurons as in [245] it was possible to discriminate percepts of similar amino acid odors due to their classification into discrete and defined output activity patterns. Trajectories in the neuronal coding space of indistinguishable amino acids are deflected towards the same local minimum. Distinguishable, but similar odors converge via different trajectories towards different output states in the odor space. The output states are stable due to a non-linearity in the amount of separation induced by small chemical dissimilarities (see figure 4.4 and [245]). By analyzing the respective trajectories in Zebrafish coding space for isotopomers of amino acids we sought out to show, if isotopomers are distinguishable on a neuronal level. Strongly diverging trajectories of isotopomers of the same amino acid in the coding space would indicate successful odor discrimination by the OB of Zebrafish. For this analysis, we acquired full-brain Zebrafish neuronal activity data while presenting isotopomers in behaving fish.

4.2 Material & Methods

4.2.1 Odorant characterization

Amino acid odours without labels were of the highest available chemical purity (99%, Merck) and deuterated amino acids (L-Leucine-d10, L-Lysine-2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-d9 HCl, L-Phenyl-d5-alanine-2,3,3-d3 and L-Tryptophan-2,4,5,6,7-d5 (indole-d5)) had all stable Hydrogens replaced with Deuterium at an enrichment of 98% with a chemical purity of 99% (CDN Isotopes).

IR spectrum calculation

In silico IR-spectra were calculated as described in [238] using the Amsterdam Density Functional software package (www.SCM.com). In short, first the geometry of molecular models of non deuterated Amino Acid was optimized by minimizing the Hartree-Energy of the molecules. Deuterated amino acids were generated by adjusting the mass of Hydrogen atoms to 2.014101779 Dalton. The IR frequencies were calculated numerically at DZP/PBE level of theory. The differentiation of energy gradients in a sequence of single point runs for the equilibrium geometry and a series of slightly different geometries yields the energy surface of the molecule. By comparing the computed gradients the force constants and hence the frequencies are computed (in the harmonic approximation of the energy surface) with an accuracy of typically fewer than 10 wave numbers [254].

1D-NMR spectroscopy

1D-NMR spectra were acquired by the supplier of the chemicals CDN at 300 MHz in D₂O on VNMR-300 or Gemini-300 spectrometers (Varian). Assignment of the peaks was based on values deposited in the BioMagResBank [255].

4.2.2 Animals and odor delivery

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) of the *mitfa* *-/-* background [256] stably expressed the calcium sensor GCaMP6s [257] under control of the a pan-neuronal HuC promotor (HuC:GCaMP6s). Larvae used for the experiments were selected for fluorescence in the brain and kept under standard conditions until between 7 and 9 days post fertilization (dpf). To minimize movement artifacts, larvae were paralyzed with α -Bungarotoxin (Sigma) after [258]. The paralytic, α -Bungarotoxin, binds irreversibly

and competitively to the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor at the Zebrafish neuromuscular junction [259] and allows stable recordings of the Zebrafish forebrain [260]. In short, larvae in E3-Medium (5 mM NaCl, 0.17 mM KCl, 0.33 mM CaCl₂, and 0.33 mM MgSO₄, pH 6.8–6.9) were weakly paralyzed with 0.02% tricaine methanesulfonate (Sigma) for ca. 20 s. Immobile larvae were aligned in a well of an agarose gel under a stereo-microscope with their heart facing up. α -Bungarotoxin (125 μ M) in PBS is injected into the heart cavity using a patch pipette with a tip diameter of 1–3 μ m on a Femtojet micromanipulator (Eppendorf) and the fish allowed to recover in E3 buffer.

The larvae were transferred to a microfluidic recording chamber and fixed in 2% low melting agarose (Promega) with their head pointing towards the liquid inlet. A canal was cut in the agarose from the liquid inlet of the chamber to the nose of the fish for quick odor delivery and removal. In case the larvae was not paralyzed the tail was cut free from agarose to reduce rotation and translation of the head in case of spontaneous tail movements. Amino acids were dissolved at a concentration of 1 mM in E3-Medium. A stream of E3-Medium at constant flowrate driven by gravity was used to apply the odors using a pneumatically actuated HPLC injection valve controlled by MATLAB. The order of deuterated, non-deuterated and control odors was pseudorandomized and neuronal activity of the fish placed around the native focal plane of the microscope recorded over the course of up to 16.5 min. Before the next experiment the larvae were left in the dark to recover for ca. 20 min and imaging was continued in this manner until the fish deceased or neuronal activity or fluorescence levels decreased significantly.

4.2.3 Imaging, image processing and signal extraction

In order to reproducibly obtain neuronal activity traces a work-flow for was developed to obtain 3D data and reproducibly correct for computational and experimental artifacts (see figure 4.5).

Imaging setup

Images were acquired in a Lightfield microscopy setup similar to [246]. In short, on an epifluorescence microscope (Olympus / Scientifica) fluorescence was excited at a wavelength of 465 nm (300 mW, CoolLED) and collected by a 20x \0.5-NA wet objective (Olympus) through a standard GFP filter set (Excitation filter (Zeiss): 466nm, Emission filter (Semrock): 525/50 nm). The signal is imaged onto a 5.5-megapixel (2,560 x 2,160 pixels) sCMOS camera (Andor Zyla) and recorded at 5 Hz. Image acquisition and odor stimulation were synchronized by MATLAB and Micromanager via a DAQ-Board (USB-6008, Native Instruments).

Light-field deconvolution

Light-field microscopy is able to capture 3D images at high recording speed by recording both the 2D location and angle of incident light from a microlens array placed in the native image plane of the microscope. This allows to computationally reconstruct a 3D focal stack by deconvolution of the 2D image after recording with a point spread function (PSF) computed for the microscope, objective and phasemask [246]. Pixels of the 2D image were assigned to individual microlenses by calibration images with a fluorescent slide before each recording session. In this case the images were re-sampled and rectified with 11 pixel per lens and the reconstruction space extended from -100 to +100 μ m in 4 μ m steps.

FIGURE 4.5: Image processing work-flow and programs used in the process.

Preprocessing of deconvoluted images

The reconstructed xyzt (4D) recording had to be filtered, registered and interpolated in order to prepare the extraction the calcium fluorescence traces. Due to the massive amount of data per reconstructed dataset (up to 1 Terabyte) parallelization by cluster computing was implemented using the Thunder library. Thunder is an open source tool for large-scale analysis of neural data using the Apache Spark engine for distributed computing [261]. For parallelized data manipulation imaging datasets were loaded as Thunder objects and processed with thunders workflow or custom algorithms written in python (see 6.3). Reconstruction and registration were carried out on the Vienna Scientific Cluster and the "Mendel" Cluster of the Gregor Mendel Institute, respectively.

The main steps of preprocessing are

1. FFT-filtering to remove periodic artifacts of the deconvolution
2. Registration of the forebrain to remove movement artifacts
3. Interpolation of the voxel time-traces to remove clipping effects introduced by the registration
4. Segmentation and signal extraction of identified Regions of interests (ROI)

The microlenslet-array introduced a periodic grid as an artifact on each image which were partially removed by selectively masking periodic features in the Fourier-space of the images. Each image was transformed into the frequency space with a Fast Fourier transform algorithm (FFT) where the microlens grid artifacts appeared as periodic peaks within the power spectrum. The mask was an array of values between 0 and 1 of the same size as the image. Values of 0 were set to positions in the image where periodic peaks of the images fourier transform appeared by adjusting parameters depending on the microlens spacing and size of the picture. Then, the mask was blurred with a gaussian kernel of 2.5σ to avoid FFT-ringing artifacts. Multiplying the mask with the FFT of the image set the intensity of periodic grid artifacts in the power spectrum to 0. The masked power spectrum was transformed back to real space by inverse FFT and compared to the input image to evaluate the quality of the filter.

The FFT-filtered images were stabilized by moving and rotating them in space until they match a reference frame. This was accomplished using a registration algorithm of the SimpleITK wrapper of ITK (a large collection of image processing algorithms [262]). Each 3D volume of the movie (moving frame) is compared to a reference volume (called fixed frame) based on similarity. The fixed frame was defined either manually or by averaging the most stable frames over a few seconds. The best alignment in 3D of the moving to the fixed frame was found by a conjugate gradient line search (optimizer) using 0.01 % of the pixels to score similarity by correlation as a metric. The search was conducted in two steps to avoid getting stuck in local minima. First, the picture was binned 5x5 pixels and also spatially smoothed with a gaussian kernel of 5σ . Once the optimizer converged to a minimum the search was repeated from the final position of the first step without binning or smoothing. The similarity metrics as well as translation and rotations along x, y and z axis were inspected for quality control of the dataset and registration success.

Transformed voxels outside of the image do not contain fluorescent information and were interpolated with nearest-neighbor fluorescence intensities if they were moved into the final image during registration. Without this correction, they would

introduce high variation in fluorescence of the timetrace of this voxel due to their preassigned artificially constant intensity value during registration in ITK. Without correction, this introduced high variations in fluorescence of uninterpolated outside-voxels over time which gets picked up by the spatial segmentation algorithm which assigned ROIs based on the variance in fluorescence (see below).

The segmentation algorithm groups adjacent voxels with similar variance in fluorescence into blob shaped ROIs of the size of a neuron. From these so called filters the average fluorescent signal over time of all included voxels is extracted. First, the dataset was de-trended and inactive voxels discarded based on their time-domain variance. For segmentation of the voxel space, independent component analysis (ICA) was used to find voxels with highest variance over time. Adjacent voxels were clustered into neuron shaped blobs based on their size and dispersion. From these spatial filters fluorescent intensities F were extracted over the whole recording time and converted to $\Delta F/F_0 = 100 * (F(t) - F_0)/F_0$. Hereto, the mean fluorescence F_0 of each trace was subtracted from F and the result normalized by division with F_0 .

4.2.4 Preprocessing of neuronal activity traces

Preprocessing was done in MATLAB with custom scripts, storing fluorescence values in a 2-dimensional matrix with individual neuronal filters as rows and timepoints as columns. First, the filters found by segmentation are assigned to functional regions of the Zebrafish forebrain (OE, OB, TE and DE) by assigning the filters overlapping with a manually defined brain area on a maximum intensity projection (MIP) of the fish's forehead. Filters outside the head or not overlapping with any brainregion are discarded. Timepoints during strong movements of the fish were defined as excluded frames and interpolated with nearest-neighbor fluorescence. The traces were further denoised with a moving average filter with a window-size of 5 frames. To find responsive neurons the data was standardized by calculating the z-score of the $\Delta F/F_0$ trace with z indicating the distance between the measurement and the population mean in units of standard deviations. Neuronal traces were discarded if they did not show a signal change of at least 2 standard deviations (z-score of 2) after the stimulus.

4.2.5 Data preparation, correlation and dimensionality reduction

To analyze trajectories in principle component space, 250 timepoints after the stimulus onset were sorted based on the stimulus identity and trials with the same stimulus horizontally concatenated. Neuronal traces were interpolated over six frames around the point of concatenation to avoid sharp rises in fluorescence which would lead to artifacts in the following analysis. The resulting matrix is comprised of $250 \times N_{Stim}$ timepoints as rows and $N_{Neurons} \times N_{stim}$ neurons as columns for each stimulus, where N_{Stim} is the number of unique stimuli and $N_{Neurons}$ is the number of neuronal filters in the brainregion being analyzed. To compare responses between fishes or within the same fish but different experiments the datasets were normalized, sorted and averaged. In detail, fluorescence data preprocessed as outlined above was normalized to a range between 0 and 1 based on the minimum and maximum fluorescence, respectively. Sorting and averaging was done as described above but in this case also across experiments and different fish.

Correlation analysis was performed by comparing neuronal traces encoding one odor stimulus with neuronal traces of all other stimuli of a specific brain region. Comparisons were clustered based on comparisons between isotopomers, between amino acids or amino acids compared to water or the background, respectively, and their

average correlation was calculated. Distances were calculated similarly by determining the average euclidean distance between neuronal traces of one odor stimulus to others.

Dimensionality reduction by principle component analysis (PCA) was used to reduce the hard to interpret high-dimensional dataset by reducing it to a 3-dimensional representation which captures the odor-evoked activity in a more interpretable manner. The methodology calculates orthogonal projections of the high-dimensional dataset where each axis is a neuron weight vector termed principle component (PC). Each PC represents shared neuronal behavior which explain the most variance in the data in decreasing order. PCs were extracted from all neurons and timebins corresponding to a pair of odor-evoked activity. The coefficients of each PC were smoothed by a moving average filter and plotted in the orthogonal 3D space. This visualized how the neuronal population evolved over time in response to the odor stimulus.

Another way to measure similarity of odors is to measure how many substitutions are required to change one odor into the other (similar to the Hamming distance in information theory [263]). By exchanging more and more traces of one odor with another we gradually remove the information on isotopomers and can thus test the robustness of odor separation and noise level in the data. Here, an approach similar to "bootstrapping" [264] was applied to assign measures of accuracy to the results of an analysis. A randomly selected fraction of up to 50% of the neuronal responses of an odor was exchanged with the trace of another odor and the respective analysis repeated. Exchanging more than 50% of odor identities would duplicate datapoints by gradually inverting the assignment of the two scrambled odors and was avoided. After scrambling, the same analysis as with unscrambled assignments is repeated and its result compared to the original result of the analysis without scrambling odor identities. By repeating the processes n-times it is possible to estimate the likelihood of the original measurement and revealed the impact of odor assignment on the obtained result.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Spectroscopic characterization of odors

Based on the hypothesis on the detection of molecular vibrations [226] a large change in the frequency of the molecule should lead to a change in activation of an associated OR and ultimately a changed odor perception. Large changes in the frequency of odors are generally introduced by replacing hydrogen with deuterium thereby doubling its mass without changing the overall chemical properties of the molecule. All vibrations in which movement of the hydrogen occurs, namely C-H stretch, scissor, and wag modes, will be red-shifted significantly upon deuteration. Similar isotopic replacements of heavier atoms like C, N, or O have much smaller change in frequency because mass changes are small of the deuterated versus normal compounds (see also chapter on C.Elegans). Thus, the amino acids used in this study were chosen to carry the highest amount of stable deuterium labels per molecule. Another selection criterion was to sample diverse chemical features of the sidechains because it was unknown which shift in which spectroscopic region could lead to the biggest change in odor perception in the Zebrafish. Based on these assumptions L-Leucine (hydrophobic), L-Phenylalanine (phenol-ring), L-Lysine (charged), and L-Tryptophan (indol-ring) were chosen for this study. Their most common spectroscopic vibrations of amino acids [265] are summarized in table 4.1 showing which spectral features can be influenced via the type of deuteration chosen here.

X-H vibrations	bond	type	wavenumbers cm^{-1}
Hydroxyl	O-H	stretch	3610 - 3640
Amide A	N-H	stretch	3300 - 3500
Phenol	C-H	stretch	3000 - 3100
Alkenes	C-H	stretch	3020 - 3080
Alkanes	C-H	stretch	2850 - 2960
(Nitrile)	$\text{N}\equiv\text{H}$	stretch	2000 - 2150
Amide I	C=O, C-N	stretch, stretch	1600 - 1700
Amide II	N-H, C-C, C-N	bend, stretch, stretch	1510 - 1580
Amide III, IV	many	complex	1000 - 1500
Alkanes	C-H	wag, scissoring	1200 - 1400

TABLE 4.1: Important IR-vibrations of non-deuterated Aminoacids. Items in bold face change upon deuteration for aminoacids used in this thesis. Importantly, nitrile vibrations do not appear in normal, but in deuterated aminoacids. Values adapted from [265]

Spectroscopic modeling

If Zebrafish are able to detect deuteration it was important to know what part of the spectrum changed compared to normal odors. Thus, the shift in frequency upon deuteration was calculated for each aminoacid used in this study. Calculation followed protocols previously used in similar studies on olfaction [238].

The results are shown in figure 4.6 and show the effects of deuteration on frequency and amplitude of C-H associated modes. Upon deuteration C-H stretch vibrations around 3000 cm^{-1} decrease in intensity and show a pronounced shift of 1000 cm^{-1} to 2100 cm^{-1} where usually nitrile vibrations would show up (see table 4.1). Between 1500 and 1200 cm^{-1} lie C-H scissoring ($\approx 1450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and wag modes ($\approx 1250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). They shift by $\approx 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and add up in the Amide III and IV region (see table 4.1). In this region many spectroscopic features from complex vibrations governing the whole molecule are mixed thus leading to a convolution of vibrations depending only partially on deuteration. As a consequence of the larger amount of atoms participating in the vibrational mode, the small isotope effect is less pronounced and the shifts in frequency are smaller when compared to C-H stretch shifts.

1D-NMR

Impurities in the preparation of chemicals could be detected in the olfactory system of the fish and perceived differences in smell would no longer be attributable to the chemicals deuteration state but their chemical composition. To ensure high deuteration and chemical purity the samples were characterized by 1D-NMR spectroscopy (see figure 6.1 - 6.4). Deuteration reduces the peak height of hydrogen peaks, whereas purity is assessed by the absence of nonassignable peaks.

Peaks between 7 and 7.8 ppm show the residual hydrogens on the Phenol and Indol rings of Phenylalanine and Tryptophan whereas hydrogens of alkanes have assigned shifts between 1.4 and 1.9 ppm and between 2.8 and 4.5 ppm [255]. The success of deuteration is best visible for L-Tryptophan-indole-d5 where the peak height of Hydrogen atoms 2,4,5,6,7 on the Indol ring (>7.0 ppm) is strongly reduced whereas the alkene Hydrogens (>3.0 ppm) have high peak intensities. The integrated intensity of hydrogen signal at atom positions 2,4,5,6,7 quantifies the amount of residual hydrogen and thus the enrichment of Deuterium in the Indole-ring. In this case the enrichment amounts to 98.85%. Also, only singlet peaks appear for atoms 2,4,5,6,7 indicating

FIGURE 4.6: Computed vibrational spectra (IR intensities) of normal and deuterated amino acid odors. In all spectra the strongest changes occurred in the C-H stretch vibrations at around 2900 cm^{-1} which shifted by $\approx 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the region of nitrile stretch vibrations at around 2100 cm^{-1} . The lower intensity C-H wag and scissoring vibrations between 1400 and 1200 cm^{-1} mixed with the complex Amide III vibrations at around 1000 cm^{-1} . Unchanged spectral bands originated from N-H stretching at 3200 to 3800 cm^{-1} (Amide A), stretching of C=O and C-N at 1660 cm^{-1} (Amide I) and the complex N-H bend and C-C, C-N stretch vibration at 1580 cm^{-1} (Amide II).

that maximum one of the positions is carrying a hydrogen atom at a time. The non-deuterated positions 10 and 11 display doublet of doublets patterns indicating more than one hydrogens in the vicinity of each position on most of the molecules. Exchange of almost all hydrogens leads to spectra with almost no peaks visible as shown in the enrichments of 99.09 % for Lysine, 98.38 % for Phenylalanine and 99.03 % for Leucine, respectively. Only singlet peaks of low peak height were visible indicating that deuteration of all compounds was almost complete. The chemical purity was demonstrated by the absence of unassigned peaks in the spectrum. The only apparent non-assigned peak in the spectrum of Phenylalanine at 4.7 ppm is caused by atmospheric water in the solution [255] and thus not a contamination from the synthesis procedure. As a conclusion, the chemicals were found to absent of impurities and highly deuterated.

4.3.2 Animals and odor delivery

Discrimination between odors in Zebrafish was shown among others to depend timing of fluorescent change in subsets of cells of the mitral cells in the olfactory bulb [245]. Thus, the setup was optimized to allow for precise and reproducible timing of odor delivery. The flowrate of the buffer delivered to the fish during the experiment driven by gravity was highly stable and reproducible compared to when using a peristaltic pump. The program controlling the acquisition and odor delivery via the 3-way valve recorded the exact time and frame number of the stimulus. Both measures allowed for precise temporal alignment of stimuli onsets of the recorded fluorescent traces. To ensure consistency of buffer conditions, the same concentrated stock solution of E3 Buffer was used throughout all experiments to dilute the samples as well as flushing the system. Fresh preparations were made daily by diluting a 10 times stock in MQ water.

4.3.3 Image processing

FFT-Filter

Registration aligns static parts of the image over time to allow segmentation of ROIs that capture ideally one neuron over the time of the recording. However, registration algorithms aligned the static periodic grid of the microlenses instead of the moving forebrain of the fish. Thus, removing artifacts of the microlens array is necessary. The purpose of this filter was to remove the grid artifacts introduced by the lightfield array while preserving as much of the fluorescence originating from the Zebrafish. Recently, new methods have been published possibly offering a different rout to de-noising [266].

Figure 4.7 illustrates the process of the filtering of the pattern of periodic grid artifacts. Periodic spatial structures appear at distinct spatial frequencies in the power spectrum (FFT) of an image. The mask (figure 4.7 b) was designed to closely resemble these grid artifacts (figure 4.7 a) of each dataset. The line-width of the masks features was adjusted to the smallest possible size in a trade-off to remove most of the grid artifacts while preserving details of the fish's fluorescence as good as possible. Omitting the center of the image from masking preserves spatial frequencies coding for fine details of the fish's image. In this manner most periodic features were removed from the power spectrum (see figure 4.7 c).

Each image plane of the whole dataset was filtered with custom parameters for the FFT-filter for each dataset via the thunder library. As shown in figure 4.8 removal of less than 5 % of the total intensity of the original frame by the FFT-Filter almost completely abolishes grid artifacts in most of the planes of the reconstructed image.

FIGURE 4.7: Masking of periodic grid artifacts in FFT-space. Left: The unfiltered FFT of a xy-plane of one timepoint in a recording after fourier transformation. The image shows periodic patterns stemming from grid artifacts which are matched by the synthetic mask (middle). Applying the mask to the original image yields a FFT devoid of most of the periodic features while preserving the information of the recorded object.

In planes close to the center of the reconstructed volume, artifacts are strongest and not possible to remove. However, the information content in these planes is lowest due to the reduced lateral resolution [267]. Thus, the middle planes (planes 24-26 of total 51) were removed from the dataset to improve the performance of the subsequent registration step.

Registration

The registration algorithm allows to stabilize the position of neurons in space over the course of long recordings. This allows to detect and read out the fluorescence of ROIs corresponding to neurons. The twitching of non-paralyzed fish or long-term drifts of the imaging setup are picked up and corrected for as shown on 2000 frames (400s of recording (see figure 4.9). Spontaneous tail movements (dotted box in figure 4.9 a) of unparalysed the Zebrafish larva significantly translate and rotate the head although the tail of the larvae is cut free of agarose. The movement is corrected by rotating and translating the image in space until a high correlation with the fixed frame is achieved. However, quick movements during the camera acquisition time of 200 ms blurs and elongates the recorded neurons. This causes a drop in similarity to the fixed frame during movements although the pictures are otherwise optimally aligned. Nevertheless, the mean difference over the time of the tailmovement to the reference drops from $(50.3 \pm 20.3) \%$ to $(21.2 \pm 10.6) \%$ (figure 4.9 c). Remaining differences were accounted to camera noise, movement blur, tissue deformation, overall drift in fluorescence intensity of the Zebrafish and changes in neuronal activity.

4.3.4 Analysis of neuronal traces

Preprocessing of neuronal activity traces

The analyzed dataset is assembled from neuronal recordings of 7 out of more than 30 recorded fishes selected by the robustness and amplitude of the neuronal response to the odors stimuli. 16 recordings of pseudo-random presentation of up to 10 odors and control stimuli per recording resulted in 124 trials of individual stimuli (see table 4.2). Individual ROIs were detected with ICA (see 4.10 A). Of all the neurons detected

FIGURE 4.8: Result of the FFT-filtering. Maximum intensity projection of an a) unfiltered and b) filtered image. c) The difference of a) and b) reveals where the filter subtracts (blue) or adds (red) fluorescence. The summed change in fluorescence intensity due to filtering amounts to less than 5% of the total fluorescence intensity. d) Image intensity along a horizontal line at pixel 125 indicated by the dotted lines in images a)-c). The sharp periodic spikes of the unfiltered image (gray) are removed in the filtered image (green) removing periodic image artifacts (black) while underlying features are preserved.

FIGURE 4.9: Result of registration. a) Translation (in μm , top) and rotation (in degree, bottom) corrected by registration during 400 sec recording of unparalysed *D. rerio* neuronal activity. b) Absolute difference of fluorescence in *D. rerio* forebrain compared to reference frame integrated over time during fish movement (dotted box in a) before (left) and after (right) motion correction. The registered frame is much more similar to the registered frame indicated by the decline in strong deviations in fluorescence intensity. c) Normalized integrated absolute difference in fluorescence over x-Axis of b) before (left) and after (right) motion correction. Remaining differences after motion correction are due to noise and neuronal activity.

Stimulus type	Abbreviation	Trials
L-Lysine	LysN	18
L-Lysine-2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-d9	LysD	15
L-Pheynylalanine	PheN	27
L-Phenyl-d5-alanine-2,3,3-d3	PheD	24
Water	H ₂ O	27
Background	BKG	13

TABLE 4.2: Number of stimuli recorded from 7 fish.

by the ICA a total of 9140 ROIs or neuronal traces¹ showed a clear response with a z-score higher than 3 to the stimuli and were well defined when superimposed on the fish's brain.

The full dataset was comprised of 124 presented stimuli encoded in 64392 neuronal traces of at least 600 timepoints. All analysis steps below were restricted to <250 timepoints during which the stimulus response was present.

The presence of spontaneous neuronal background activity masks responses to the external stimuli and reduces the SNR significantly. Figure 6.5 underlines the fact, that standard deviations of all averaged fish trials is up to twice the averaged signal necessitating the filtering. Thus, neuronal traces were labeled based on their spatial location in functional brain regions and responsiveness to the stimulus (see figure 4.10 B&C). First, brain regions were then segmented manually and assigned to relevant brain regions based on morphology (see 4.10 B). Secondly, K-means clustering was used to select a subpopulation of neurons which responded the strongest to the actual stimulus as identified by visual inspection from an analysis involving 5 clusters (see cluster 2 in 4.10 C). The neurons thereby were comprised from different brain regions, but mostly (>90%) from OB and TEL where odorant processing takes place [245].

The example trial shown in figure 4.10 D shows the average response of all neurons, different brain region or clustered neurons. Discarding activity traces of neurons not directly responding to the stimulus aligned the signal strongly with the odorant stimuli within the first 200 timepoints after the stimulus (compare row All-DIE to Clust in figure 4.10 D). This highly specific selection of neurons directly responding to the stimulus by clustering reduced the total amount of neuronal traces in the analysis to 17456 (27%) individual neuronal traces encoding the stimuli. The population average of these clustered traces for all fish is shown in figure 4.10 E). Already from this crude analysis, a strong disparity between dissimilar amino acids and a slight disparity in response strength between isotopes of the same amino acid type was apparent.

Statistical analysis of population averaged response of isotope induced differences in brain dynamics

Differences between deuterated and non-deuterated odors could be manifested as large scale changes in global activity patterns as well as subtle changes in temporal and intensity response profile of neuronal subpopulations. As a first proxy, global change of population averages of each stimulus type across all fish were analyzed based on the

¹ROIs identified by this method do not necessarily coincide with individual neurons due to the lack of lateral resolution of this methodology. However, for the sake of simplicity the fluorescence trace of a ROI are termed "neuronal" trace as it is by definition composed of pixels with coordinated change in fluorescence as expected for individual neurons, or groups of neurons behaving the same way.

FIGURE 4.10: Segmentation of neurons and brain regions and extracted signals. A) Maximum intensity projection of the recorded brain of a single specimen. Colorful dots show 9 individually colored ROIs as found by segmentation with ICA. B) Segmentation of ROIs based on brain region in OB, TEL, DIE, and the cluster of neurons most responsive to stimuli, respectively. The position of clustered ROIs shows, that cells all over the brain respond to the stimulus onset. C) K-means clustering of activity traces of ROIs found the fish shown in A during the presentation of 10 pseudo-randomized stimuli and one control stimulus. Individual clusters and their respective neurons are separated by horizontal white lines and denoted with numbers 1-5. The stimulus protocol and onset of each stimuli is shown as colorful vertical lines. D) Example of averaged normalized fluorescence traces of neurons of different brainregions and clustered neurons (cluster 2 in C). Stimulus identity and onset is shown as vertical lines. E) Normalized population average of all neurons of the most responsive cluster per fish in the dataset to different amino acid stimuli (deuterated: 'D', not deuterated: 'N') over 200 timepoints (40s) after the valve was activated ($t=0$). The time until the first rise of fluorescence intensity is due to the volume of buffer between valve to fish.

traces in figure 4.10 E. Averaged amino acid stimuli vary slightly in temporal onset, maximum height and overall shape of the response but follow a similar temporal response profile with a steep rise to a peak of fluorescence between 50 and 80 frames and a decay to the baseline at up to 200 frames.

Integrated response and temporal alignment The differences in average traces between isotopomers are not significantly different taking into account the large amount of variation between different trials. Deuterated and non-deuterated odors of the same kind were statistically indistinguishable by their mean fluorescence change as shown in figure 4.11 A because they followed the same overall temporal evolution.

The differences might be complex and involve variations in steepness and maximum fluorescence of the peak response as well as different decay time profiles (i.e. illustrated by the profile of LysD compared to PheD in 4.10 E). The background activity was comprised of spontaneous baseline neuronal activity which was averaged out (see 4.11 A). To water, the fishes showed a weak continuous neuronal response with lower variation due to a lacking high fluorescence peak response. Its onset was temporally aligned with the mean fluorescence onset of odors which indicated that the valve switching was leading to the response (see 4.11 A). Overall this showed that mean intensity of responses was not able to significantly discriminate neither deuteration states nor dissimilar amino acids.

Changes in the overall temporal course of neuronal activation between stimuli the recordings require alignment in time with respect to the valve switching ($t=0$). To test this, the correlation of all timepoints to each other in figure 4.11 B shows that timepoints before and after 20 timeframes were not correlated to each other. The abrupt transition between correlation states was constant within a few frames over all trials which demonstrated highly reproducible temporal delivery of the stimuli. Furthermore, the first 80 frames during the rise of the stimulus response were highly inter-correlated but lost correlation with later timepoints during the decay of the stimulus response. This showed the reproducibility of stimulus delivery to the system, a reproducible baseline pre-stimulus and proper alignment of stimulus onset in time.

Temporal correlation within brain regions To investigate if clustering by brain region might disseminate stimulus responses their cross-correlation was determined. A single measure of how similar the strength and direction of complex timetraces behaved when compared to each other is illustrated and quantified as correlation coefficients in 4.11 C and D, respectively. Changes in the deuteration state of the same amino acid showed a strong correlation (>0.75) across whole trials (cluster 1-2, green and red) across different neuron types. Correlations between dissimilar amino acids (cluster 3, purple) were high in OE and across all celltypes but lower in OB neurons, where olfactory discrimination takes place [245]. Interestingly, OE neurons showed no correlation between the water stimulus and amino acid stimuli but displayed high correlation in other neuron types (OB, all neurons). This confirmed on the one hand, that the water stimulus was devoid of olfactants similar to the amino acids used meaning the stimulus protocol and washing step were sufficient. However, the residual activity and correlation in other neuronal types indicated a different way of neuronal processing for the water stimulus compared to amino acid odors. This analysis showed, that neuronal response to stimuli of different isotopes are strongly correlated within neurons selected by brain region. Thus, brain region was not a good discriminator for discerning isotope effects.

FIGURE 4.11: Overall comparison of Datasets. A) Mean normalized response to each stimulus (error-bars = standard deviations, n.s. = not significant of students t-test $p=0.05$) cannot discriminate isotopomers. B) Pearson correlation coefficients between individual timepoints of mean traces of all stimuli demonstrated the reproducibility of timing across trials. C) Correlation between whole timetraces of all stimuli for OE (top left), OB (top right) or all neurons (bottom left). The bottom right graph illustrates the patterns comprising clusters of correlations between (1-2) deuterated and non-deuterated amino acids of the same amino acid type, (3) between different amino acids, (4) between amino acids and water (5) and amino acids and background, respectively. Correlations of OE allow no discrimination between amino acids or isotopomers but show that stimuli are different compared to water. OBs correlations reveal strong correlations between isotopomers, but weaker correlations between amino acid species. Including all cells of the forebrain in the analysis shows the same trends but decreases the discriminability of the analysis. D) Mean correlation coefficients of clusters from C) in different neuronal subpopulations (same color code, Top left: OE, top right: OB, bottom left: all neurons).

Temporal correlation and euclidean distance over time As odor discrimination is most likely in the OB (see [245]) this region was investigated more closely. Figure 4.12 and 4.13 show the correlation and euclidean distances of neuronal activity over time. For this, the stimulus response was chunked in 7 second intervals and correlations between stimuli averaged per chunk. The results show, that the temporal evolution is complex and over all time-frames isotope induced neuronal behavior is highly correlated and has a close distance in neuron space. Also different amino acid types (Lys vs Phe) are highly correlated and close in neuronal space (see Figure 4.12 and 4.13 A).

Selecting the OB region indeed allows much better discrimination of differences between different amino acid types (Lys vs Phe) as indicated (see Figure 4.12 and 4.13 B). Most notably, the correlation between PheN and PheD is weak across all timeframes coming from a weak correlation between 14 and 21 seconds (see 4.12 B). This is not apparent in the neuronal distance space (see 4.13 B). This shows, that isotope induced differences between Phe stem rather from de-synchronization while average neuronal activity intensity stay the same.

FIGURE 4.12: Correlation coefficient between different subsets of neurons responding to different odorants over time. Correlation coefficient was measured in for A) all cells (6321 neurons of 7 fish) and B) a subset of neurons from the OB (1674 neurons of 7 fish).

Bootstrap analysis quantifies signal strength and randomness of responses

In order to assess the level of randomness between individual stimuli and quantify the signal strength, bootstrap analysis of the response was applied. Figure 4.14 A and B show how neuronal populations diverge over the course of the experiment when exposed to different stimuli as shown by the cumulative euclidean distance between neuronal populations over time. Distances in the PCA space were found previously to describe discrimination of odors in Zebrafish [245]. The distances measured here directly in neuronal space do not reduce the dimensionality and were thus closer to the unfiltered data, when compared to the convoluted signal of many neurons contributing to a single PCA. Critical for this analysis was choosing the correct subset of neurons directly responding to the stimulus in the OB only as established above. Normalization to chemically dissimilar odors (Lys compared to Phe, both non-deuterated) allowed to estimate the magnitude of dissimilarity when compared to chemically dissimilar odorants (purple trace in figure 4.14 B). Divergence of neuronal space between isotopomers to a similar cumulative distance as chemically dissimilar odors (100% in

FIGURE 4.13: Euclidean distance between different subsets of neurons responding to different odorants over time. Euclidean distance was measured in for A) all cells (6321 neurons of 7 fish) and B) a subset of neurons from the OB (1674 neurons of 7 fish). Each neuronal signal is represented by one dimension to the neuronal space in which the euclidean distance is measured. The color scale is adjusted in each field to the respective maximum. The maximum is indicated below and is normalized to the distance between chemically dissimilar odorants (LysN and PheN) across all timeframes.

figure 4.14 B) would show that isotopomers evoked neuronal patterns as dissimilar as encountered when perceiving two chemically different odors.

Normalized differences in neuronal space As expected, neuronal states evoked by amino acids were found to be very dissimilar from states evoked by water and background controls (Fig 4.14 A). When compared to chemically dissimilar odorants the distance in neuronal space was approximately 200 % higher for water and approximately 300 % for background, respectively. Distances between isotopomers were smallest (50 % and 70 % for Lysine and Phenylalanine, respectively), while differences between amino acids were smaller than controls, but bigger than distances between isotopomers. This result confirmed the validity of the control stimuli and showed that isotopomers evoke significantly distinct neuronal states which nonetheless are not as disparate as between chemically dissimilar odorants.

Quantifying signal strength by bootstrapping To quantify the amount of randomness in the neuronal populations and characterize the reproducibility of stimulus responses bootstrap analysis was applied. For this, a random subset of neurons was chosen and their neuronal activity traces contributing to a stimuli swapped with another stimulus. By repeating this analysis 10,000 times, the null distribution was plotted and compared to the actual distance without scrambling of odor identities. Figure 4.14 C shows that odor identities were scrambled chosen from a uniform distribution. This confirmed, that no bias was introduced due to unequal sampling between individual draws.

Figure 4.14 D shows the result of bootstrapping of 10,000 individual test per stimulus pair. The unscrambled values on the x-axis at 0% reflect the values plotted in figure 4.14 A. Scrambling successively more odor identities gradually removes the distance of odorants in neuronal space. This means, that the odor identities were responsible for the separability in the first place and demonstrates the ability of this method to determine the absolute signal strength.

FIGURE 4.14: Distances in neuronal space between stimuli. A) Cumulative distance between neuronal responses of all investigated stimuli normalized to the distance between dissimilar amino acids (LysN and PheN, 3) over full experiment. Isotopomers show the smallest distance in neuronal space (1 and 2), chemically dissimilar stimuli showed higher dissimilarity (3). Amino acids differ most to water (4) and background (BKG, 5). B) Distances in neuronal space over time normalized as in A) shows separation of isotopomer traces after ≈ 100 frames. C) Distribution of scrambled percentages of odor identities across 10000 individual experiments indicating a uniform distribution of experiments across randomly drafted neurons ($n\text{Bins} = 100$). D) Distances in neuronal space over time normalized as in A) with results of 10000 individual experiments of different percentages of scrambled odor identity. Distances of unscrambled identities are indicated with vertical lines for ease of view. Removing the odor identities gradually removes the distance in neuronal space indicating information content encoded in the neuronal response. Distances between stimuli remaining at 50% scrambling (random draft of neurons) revealed random differences in neuronal states not related to odor identities. E-F) Comparison of scrambling between isotopomers and within single stimulus of E) Lysine and F) Phenylalanine, respectively. The distances within one single stimulus identity are smaller than the distances between isotopomers. G-H) Analysis of scrambling within F) water and G) background control revealed the small differences between individual trials within the stimuli.

The amount of distance in neuronal space left after removing every odorant information (50 % scrambling) shows the distance due to non-odor related variations e.g. due to variations between the compared trials. Scrambling greatly reduced the distances between all investigated stimuli which indicated, that the observed differences are indeed due to the assigned odor identities and not by chance. The linear relation between distance and percentage of odor information removed by scrambling indicates, that the information is distributed equally amongst the neurons chosen for this analysis. Including neurons irrelevant to odor processing or not responding to the stimuli in the analysis would blur the differences between odor induced neuronal states resulting in a more horizontal line. The introduced noise could drown the signal of the amino acids to a degree where they might not be discriminated from the negative control (H₂O). This confirms the need for choosing a subset of neurons which is highly relevant to the separation of neuronal states based on odor identities.

The difference between the retained neuronal distance after complete scrambling and without scrambling is a measure of signal strength within the stimulus responses. Distances between isotopomers are reduced to approx. 10 % after scrambling, while distances between chemical dissimilar odorants retain 25 % distance after scrambling. Water and background stimuli retain approx. 45 % and 35 % of distance after complete scrambling. All distances after scrambling are well below their unscrambled values which indicated, that indeed odorant identity was responsible for the distances found by the analysis of unscrambled odorants.

Quantifying intra-trial variability and distance between isotopomers To investigate the degree to which variability within one odorant identity contributed to the distances in odorant space between odorants neurons were scrambled within single odorant responses. For this the neurons responding to a single stimulus were split in two groups and neurons scrambled between these groups 10,000 times, as described above. Figure 4.14 E-H shows the result of this analysis for amino acids and the controls. Distances in neuronal space between neurons within individual stimuli (LysN vs LysN or PheN and PheD) are small as indicated by the low starting value without scrambling. Scrambling leads to horizontal line which showed, that the neuronal traces belonging to this stimulus are all very similar. This revealed, that the individual stimulus responses between individual experiments lead to similar stimulus responses. The magnitude of differences between isotopomers as determined above of 50 % and 70 % for Lys and Phe, respectively, is thus reduced by approximately 10 % due to intra-trial variability. All together, this analysis revealed, that the distances in neuronal space between isotopomers (red and green line in figure 4.14 E and F, respectively) are indeed from differences in processing of odorant identities and not due to high variability in intra-trial differences.

4.3.5 Dimensionality reduction

An analogous method to euclidean distance in neuronal space is measuring distances in PCA-space. In order to deconvolute the complex neuronal responses in the high dimensional neuron space, PCA was applied to individual pairs of deuterated and non-deuterated amino acids. Distances between points in the PCA space are a measure for the similarity of complex activity patterns of the neuronal populations encoded by the PCs, whereby small distances correspond to similar activity patterns in the neuron space. The change in distance between two points in the PCA space after fully scrambling the odor identities measures to which degree the information of the odor identity contributed to their separation in the first place.

Figure 4.15 shows the result of the analysis for isotopomers of Phenylalanine compared to water and Lysine stimuli. The separation between Non-Deuterated Phenylalanine and Lysine in figure 4.15 A acts as a positive control to show how Zebrafish larvae discriminate chemically dissimilar stimuli. Isotopomers have a certain distance in PCA space but the difference is not as big when compared to the positive control which confirms results found as described above and in Figure 4.14. Scrambling of 50% of the isotopomers traces completely abolishes the separation between isotopomers as seen in figure 4.15 B. This indicates, that isotopomer identities indeed contributed to the dissimilarity in PCA space. To evaluate the influence of sampling bias on the isotopomers separability in PCA space different subsets of neurons were randomly chosen and the analysis repeated. Figure 4.15 C and D show that two different random subsets of neurons change the separability between isotopomers not as drastically as scrambling all odor identities, but nonetheless reduce the distance between isotopomers. Thus, the differentiability between isotopomers seems to increase with more neurons included in the analysis. This analysis shows, differences between isotopomers are apparent also in PCA-space and can be fully removed by scrambling. Subsets do not show a signal as robust as the full dataset.

FIGURE 4.15: PCA trajectories of neuronal stimuli of non-deuterated (green), deuterated (red), water (blue) or chemically dissimilar Amino Acid (purple). Trajectories start at the solid open circle and the first 45 frames (colorful solid dot marks 9 seconds post stimulus) are shown with solid lines. The rest of the trajectory is shown in pale colors. A) The unaltered data B) 50% of isotopomer identities scrambled C) random 50% subset of neurons drawn from A). D) another random 50% neurons drawn from A). Trajectories were smoothed with a running average filter.

4.4 Discussion of isotope induced changes in brain dynamics in olfaction

Subtracting the activity of whole brain regions as well as temporally resolved correlations were inconclusive with respect to differences in brain activity between isotopomers. However, both neuronal space (see section 4.3.4) and PCA space (see section 4.3.5) show differences between isotopomers of amino acids that persist even after scrambling of neuronal trace identities.

Being able to detect differences in brain states between isotopomers of up to 50 % and 70 % for Lys and Phe, respectively when compared to the magnitude evoked by chemically dissimilar odorants is very surprising. Adding 9 and 5 neutrons to Lys and Phe respectively should not impact their shape to 50 % of the change induced by exchanging a nonpolar, neutral, and hydrophobic benzyl ring of Phe with a basic, charged, aliphatic lysyl side-chain of Lys. It is hard to imagine how the slight increase in van der Waals radius induced by additional neutrons could induce half of the change in neuronal activation as by presenting completely differently shaped and charged sidechains. If the effects measured in this thesis are indeed triggered solely by binding events to OR the observations in this thesis are not compatible with the classical theory in olfaction and would support the theory of a vibrational activation of receptors.

However, when testing the vibrational theory of olfaction, purity of the sample, suitability of the model system and proximity to receptor-events are considered of highest importance as discussed in [229, 233, 235]. Figure 4.2 shows the body of literature on different levels of the odors interaction and the reactions triggered on different levels of complexity inside an animal. While understanding odorant \rightarrow receptor interaction is the ultimate goal, most studies were carried out measuring perceptual or behavioral changes [228, 236–239] which have been criticized as being anecdotal and detached from receptor events [229, 233, 235]. As the experiments laid out here also provide evidence on the level of brain dynamics, we have to address all key points of olfaction (see figure 4.2) and the main critique of previous studies.

One often voiced concern is the chemical purity of odorant samples. In this study it was shown, that samples are very pure as demonstrated by 1D-NMR (see figure 6.1 - 6.4). The amino acids do not involve novel sophisticated synthesis steps as encountered in previous studies [233, 237] and chemical purity of simple amino acids is thus not surprising. Nonetheless, it cannot be excluded, that impurities from the deuteration process might be contaminants in the sample which are undetectable by NMR.

Furthermore, the molecules used in this thesis are much smaller compared to previously used isotope effects with odorants. This means less hydrogens can be exchanged for deuterium which induces smaller changes in the vibrational landscape of the molecule. Nonetheless, FTIR calculations performed in this thesis similar to analysis performed previously [238] demonstrated that C-H stretch vibrations are affected the most by deuteration and spectral changes are clearly visible in the relevant spectral region. The magnitude and completeness of spectroscopic shifts to background free regions confirmed the suitability of the amino acids Lys and Phe for testing isotope effects on olfaction.

Previous studies pointed out, that mucus contains enzymes susceptible to isotope effects [240]. The olfactory system of fish contains a lot of mucus with many functional enzymes embedded in it [231, 247], however, the exact protein composition is not investigated. Thus, it cannot be excluded, that in this study perireceptor events

altered the isotopomers of amino acids before being recognized by OR. Since no differences between isotopomers was measured, isotope sensitive perireceptor events might have increased the noise level to a degree obstructing detection of differences between isotopomers by artificially altering isotopomers to evoke more similar neuronal responses. Future studies of living animals might use a common broad spectrum of protein-inhibitors to block enzymatic activity in the mucus during the experiment. However, it has to be carefully evaluated how protease inhibitors impact OR function to avoid additional artifacts due to unwanted inhibition of the olfactory receptors GPCR.

One critique of Blocks *et al.* measurement of receptor activation was, that measurements were carried out *in vitro* not fully reproducing the environment needed for allowing proper OR function [234]. This study does not measure receptor activation directly but determines the resulting neuronal activity *in vivo*. This means, that the tissues and electron transport chains required for the mechanism proposed by Turin [226] are functional. The finding, that analysis of neuronal activity can classify isotopomers to a degree is thus in line with [234] criticizing findings on receptor level where activity was not dependent on deuteration [233].

In order to close the gap between whole brain activity and measurements of OR activity measurements of *in situ* or *in vivo* receptor activation by determining OR activity directly in the OSNs of the OE would need major technical improvements of existing techniques. Targeting the state-of-the-art *in vitro* Luciferase reporter construct for ORs [241] used by Block *et al.* selectively to the OSNs of a living organism [242] could circumvent this limitation. Imaging a transgenic fish line with this reporter construct in place would allow a more physiological evaluation of receptor activity as requested by Turin [234]. However, no such fish line exists up to date. Recording of OSN activity by calcium imaging would provide the integrated response of the second-messenger cascade triggered by the receptors activity. As such, this study provides the most physiological measurement of integrated receptor activity up to date.

The question, if the dissimilarity between isotopomers determined in this thesis is perceivable is hard to answer with the experimental paradigm chosen.

As previously determined, neuronal activation of OSN is too similar to discriminate even dissimilar odors [245]. Also here, dissimilar odors (Phe - Lys) were evoking very similar response patterns. However, the computation in the OB is able to classify dissimilar odors into stable output patterns in the neuronal activity space. This could be answered by investigating more complex patterns in higher order brain regions [253] or having a behavioral paradigm similar to [228, 236–239] e.g. with a freely swimming and behaving fish. The finding, that maximally 50% and 70% neuronal activity changes is contradictory of the predicted strong and significant changes in perceived smell if isotopic shifts between isotopomers are big enough as predicted in the originally proposed theory by Turin [226] albeit further non-linearities in odorant processing by higher order brain regions might still amplify this difference to a strong perception.

Further improvements could be done by changing the type of isotopes. Changes in the tested amino acids C-H stretch vibrations might not influence the electron tunneling rate in the OR. To exclude this possibility, either different odorants or isotope labels would need to be tested. Different odorants however, are less well characterized in Zebrafish olfaction and different isotope labels would involve changing heavier atoms which significantly reduces the level of mass change per atom and thus the spectroscopic shift. Furthermore, more complex synthetic pathways might increase the chance of contamination with impurities.

The choice of model system could also influence the ability to discriminate isotopes on the neuronal level. Odor evoked activity patterns between Lys and Phe showed low correlation [268] and separation in neuronal space in at least three month old adult Zebrafish [245]. However, the analysis in this paper is based on fish larvae at 5-7 dpf with a still developing brain. The larval brains total number of cells [269], interconnectivity [270] and number of glomeruli [271] was found to be significantly lower compared to adults. Classification of complex odors depends on these factors and as such larvae are expected to be worse in discrimination of very similar odors. However, dissimilar odors displayed significant changes in neuronal patterns which proved that dissimilar odors can be distinguished by the developing larvae brain. We introduced large spectroscopic shifts which are hypothesized to evoke strong changes in the receptor activation [226]. Thus, while in theory larvae should be able to detect and classify these strong isotope evoked changes in OSN activity the signal strength might be increased by using adult specimen. This might need more advanced microscopes with higher field of view to accommodate the larger brain size and to allow for deeper tissue penetration.

The theory originally proposed by Turin predicts strong and significant changes in perceived smell if isotopic shifts between isotopomers are big enough [226]. Since spectroscopic shifts were determined to be strong and modest changes in neuronal activation patterns we provide evidence that is not in only partially in conflict with the original hypothesis. Isotopomers of Lysine and Phenylalanine showed disparate brain states in olfactory related brain regions which is best explained by vibrationally assisted electron tunneling in olfactory receptors. However, the study has many limitations: The strength and weakness of the study lies in the physiological conditions of the OR and OSN. While a physiological surrounding allows to study the *in vivo* effects similar to perception or behavior studies they also introduce the possibility for peri-receptor events and odorant mucus interactions to produce false positive signals (see also figure 4.2). The evidence is less distant to the receptor activation study by Block *et al.* [233], however at the same time not as controlled as their *in vitro* experiments. Carefully crafting an experimental setup which controls for all the above limitations while repeating the stimulus with the two identified amino acids Lysine and Phenylalanine would be an advised next step. Also maybe isotopomer content in the amino acids could be titrated and its effect on signal strength (difference in brain behavior) characterized. Nonetheless, different synthesis methods might introduce chemical artifacts which are not perceivable in 1D-NMR as described by [233] so great care has to be taken to chemical purity of the reagents. This might be circumvented by screening a range of amino-acid or completely different chemical odorants which display a range of shifts in IR signals. The currently presented experimental paradigm can be used to screen the effect on signal strength dependent on the underlying structure and isotopomer count to rationalize the correlations between signal strength and IR-shift.

To summarize, a promising experimental paradigm conserving *in vivo* OR and OSN environment was established which can be used to characterize the impact of isotopomers on differences in brain states of olfactory processing. This paradigm might be useful in screening more diverse chemical isotopomer libraries and serve as a guide for receptor activation experiments that currently lack from limitations due to OSNs being examined *in vitro*.

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Chapter 5

Appendix A

5.1 Plasmid DNA and Protein Sequences

5.1.1 DNA Sequence of pSP64-tRNATyr^{CUA}

The sequence of the tRNA^{Tyr}_{CUA} is colored red with the anticodon in yellow and the T7 Promotor is colored green.

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1 GAATACAAGC TTGGGCTGCA GGTGCGACTCT AGAGGATCCC CCGCGGATCC GGATGGATC
61 CTTGGTGGTC GGGGAAGGAT TCGAACCTTC GAAGTCGATC ACGGCAGATT TAGAGTCTGC
121 TCCCTTTGGC CGCTCGGGAA CCCCACCTA AGTCGACTCGT ATTAGAATTC CCGTGGGCGA
181 GCTCGAATTC GTAATCATGG TCATAGCTGT TTCCTGTGTG AAATTGTTAT CCGCTCACAA
241 TTCCACACAA CATACGAGCC GGAAGCATAA AGTGTAAGC CTGGGGTGCC TAATGAGTGA
301 GCTAACTCAC ATTAATTGCG TTGCGCTCAC TGCCCGCTTT CCAGTCGGGA AACCTGTTCG
361 GCCAGCTGCA TTAATGAATC GGCCAACGCG CGGGGAGAGG CGGTTTGCGT ATTGGGCGCT
421 CTTCCGCTTC CTCGCTCACT GACTCGCTGC GCTCGTTCGT TCGGCTGCGG CGAGCGGTAT
481 CAGCTCACTC AAAGGCGGTA ATACGGTTAT CCACAGAATC AGGGGATAAC GCAGGAAAGA
541 ACATGTGAGC AAAAGGCCAG CAAAAGGCCA GGAACCGTAA AAAGGCCGCG TTGCTGGCGT
601 TTTTCCATAG GCTCCGCCCC CCTGACGAGC ATCACAAAAA TCGACGCTCA AGTCAGAGGT
661 GGCGAAACCC GACAGGACTA TAAAGATACC AGGCGTTTCC CCCTGGAAGC TCCCTCGTGC
721 GCTCTCCTGT TCCGACCCTG CCGCTTACCG GATACCTGTC CGCCTTTCTC CCTTCGGGAA
781 GCGTGGCGCT TTTCATAGC TCACGCTGTA GGTATCTCAG TTCGGTGTAG GTCGTTTCGCT
841 CCAAGCTGGG CTGTGTGCAC GAACCCCCCG TTCAGCCCGA CCGCTGCGCC TTATCCGGTA
901 ACTATCGTCT TGAGTCCAAC CCGGTAAGAC ACGACTTATC GCCACTGGCA GCAGCCACTG
961 GTAACAGGAT TAGCAGAGCG AGGTATGTAG GCGGTGCTAC AGAGTTCTTG AAGTGGTGGC
1021 CTAACACGG CTACACTAGA AGGACAGTAT TTGGTATCTG CGCTCTGCTG AAGCCAGTTA
1081 CCTTCGAAA AAGAGTTGGT AGCTCTTGAT CCGGCAAACA AACCACCGCT GGTAGCGGTG
1141 GTTTTTTTGT TTGCAAGCAG CAGATTACGC GCAGAAAAAA AGGATCTCAA GAAGATCCTT
1201 TGATCTTTTC TACGGGTCT GACGCTCAGT GGAACGAAAA CTCACGTAA GGGATTTTGG
1261 TCATGAGATT ATCAAAAAGG ATCTTCACCT AGATCCTTTT AAATTAATAA TGAAGTTTTA
1321 AATCAATCTA AAGTATATAT GAGTAAACTT GGTCTGACAG TTACCAATGC TTAATCAGTG
1381 AGGCACCTAT CTCAGCGATC TGTCTATTTT GTTCATCCAT AGTTGCCTGA CTCCCCGTGC
1441 TGTAGATAAC TACGATACGG GAGGGCTTAC CATCTGGCCC CAGTGCTGCA ATGATACCGC
1501 GAGACCCACG CTCACCGGCT CCAGATTTAT CAGCAATAAA CCAGCCAGCC GGAAGGGCCG
1561 AGCGCAGAAG TGGTCCTGCA ACTTTATCCG CCTCCATCCA GTCTATTAAT TGTTGCCGGG
1621 AAGCTAGAGT AAGTAGTTCG CCAGTTAATA GTTTGCGCAA CGTTGTTGCC ATTGCTACAG
1681 GCATCGTGGT GTCACGCTCG TCGTTTGTA TGGCTTCATT CAGCTCCGGT TCCCAACGAT
1741 CAAGGCGAGT TACATGATCC CCCATGTTGT GCAAAAAAGC GGTTAGCTCC TTCGGTCCCTC
1801 CGATCGTTGT CAGAAGTAAG TTGGCCGCGAG TGTTATCACT CATGGTTATG GCAGCACTGC
1861 ATAATTCTCT TACTGTCATG CCATCCGTAA GATGCTTTTC TGTGACTGGT GAGTACTCAA
1921 CCAAGTCATT CTGAGAATAG TGTATGCGGC GACCGAGTTG CTCTTGCCCG GCGTCAATAC
1981 GGGATAATAC CGCGCCACAT AGCAGAACTT TAAAAGTGCT CATCATTGGA AAACGTTCTT

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2041 CGGGGCGAAA ACTCTCAAGG ATCTTACCGC TGTTGAGATC CAGTTCGATG TAACCCACTC
2101 GTGCACCCAA CTGATCTTCA GCATCTTTTA CTTTACCAG CGTTTCTGGG TGAGCAAAAA
2161 CAGGAAGGCA AAATGCCGCA AAAAAGGGAA TAAGGGCGAC ACGGAAATGT TGAATACTCA
2221 TACTCTTCCT TTTCAATAT TATTGAAGCA TTTATCAGGG TTATTGTCTC ATGAGCGGAT
2281 ACATATTTGA ATGTATTTAG AAA

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The resulting tRNA has a length of 85 Basepairs, weighs 27,232 Da and after aminoacylation with tyrosine 27,413.2 Da ($\Delta 181.2$ Da). The RNA sequence of the anticodon is colored yellow. The Aminoacid is aminoacylated to the 3' end of the RNA at the acceptor arm with the canonical sequence CCA.

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1 GGUGGGGUUC CCGAGCGGCC AAAGGGAGCA GACUCUAAAU CUGCCGUCAU CGACUUCGAA
61 GGUUCGAAUC CUUCCCCAC CACCA

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5.1.2 pRSF1b-KcsAFl and pRSF1b-KcsAFl-Y78am sequences

pRSF1b-KcsAFl is the sequence of the wildtype full-length His-tagged KcsA construct. The Y78am mutation was introduced by mutating C325G (red) with the mutagenic primers shown below:

forward: 5'-CTACCGTGGGTTAGGGCGACTTGTATC-3'

reverse: 5'-GATACAAGTCGCCCTAACCCACGGTAG-3'

Plasmid Sequence:

```

1 GGGGAATTGT GAGCGGATAA CAATCCCCT GTAGAAATAA TTTTGTTTAA CTTTAATAAG
61 GAGATATACC ATGATGCATC ATCATCATCA TCATCCGCCA ATGTTGTCCG GTCTGCTTGC
121 TCGTCTGGTT AAGTTGCTTC TGGGCCGTCA CGTTCTGCG CTGCACTGGC GTGCTGCAGG
181 CGCTGCCACC GTCCTTCTGG TGATCGTACT GCTTGCTGGT TCCTACTTGG CGTTTCTGGC
241 TGAACGGGGC GCACCTGGTG CTCAGCTTAT TACTTATCCT CGTGCCTTGT GGTGGTCTGT
301 CGAGACCGCT ACTACCGTGG GTTA■GGCGA CTTGTATCCG GTGACCCTTT GGGGTCTGCT
361 GGTAGCGGTT GTCGTTATGG TGGCTGGCAT CACCTCCTTC GGTCTGGTAA CTGCTGCCCT
421 TGCTACTTGG TTTGTAGGCC GCGAACAAGA GCGTCGTGGT CATTTCTGTT CACTACTCTGA
481 AAAAGCGGCT GAGGAGGCAT ACACCCGTAC TACCCGTGCT CTGCACGAGC GCTTTGACCG
541 TCTGGAACGT ATGCTTGACG ACAACCGCCG GTGACTCGAG TCTGGTAAAG AAACCGCTGC
601 TGCGAAATTT GAACGCCAGC ACATGGACTC GTCTACTAGC GCAGCTTAAT TAACCTAGGC
661 TGCTGCCACC GCTGAGCAAT AACTAGCATA ACCCCTGGG GCCTCTAAAC GGGTCTTGAG
721 GGGTTTTTTG CTGAAACCTC AGGCATTTGA GAAGCACACG GTCACACTGC TTCCGGTAGT
781 CAATAAACCG GTAAACCAGC AATAGACATA AGCGGCTATT TAACGACCCT GCCCTGAACC
841 GACGACAAGC TGACGACCGG GTCTCCGCAA GTGGCACTTT TCGGGGAAAT GTGCGCGGAA
901 CCCCTATTTG TTTATTTTTC TAAATACATT CAAATATGTA TCCGCTCATG AATTAATTCT
961 TAGAAAAACT CATCGAGCAT CAAATGAAAC TGCAATTTAT TCATATCAGG ATTATCAATA
1021 CCATATTTTT GAAAAAGCCG TTTCTGTAAT GAAGGAGAAA ACTCACCGAG GCAGTTCCAT
1081 AGGATGGCAA GATCCTGGTA TCGGTCTGCG ATTCCGACTC GTCCAACATC AATACAACCT
1141 ATTAATTTCC CCTCGTCAAA AATAAGGTTA TCAAGTGAGA AATCACCATG AGTGACGACT
1201 GAATCCGGTG AGAATGGCAA AAGTTTATGC ATTTCTTTCC AGACTTGTTT AACAGGCCAG
1261 CCATTACGCT CGTCATCAAA ATCACTCGCA TCAACCAAAC CGTTATTCAT TCGTGATTGC
1321 GCCTGAGCGA GACGAAATAC GCGGTGCGTG TAAAAAGGAC AATTACAAAC AGGAATCGAA
1381 TGCAACCGGC GCAGGAACAC TGCCAGCGCA TCAACAATAT TTTACCTGA ATCAGGATAT
1441 TCTTCTAATA CCTGGAATGC TGTTTTCCCG GGGATCGCAG TGGTGAGTAA CCATGCATCA
1501 TCAGGAGTAC GGATAAAATG CTTGATGGTC GGAAGAGGCA TAAATTCCGT CAGCCAGTTT
1561 AGTCTGACCA TCTCATCTGT AACATCATTG GCAACGCTAC CTTTGCCATG TTTCAGAAAC
1621 AACTCTGGCG CATCGGGCTT CCCATACAAT CGATAGATTG TCGCACCTGA TTGCCGACA
1681 TTATCGCGAG CCCATTTATA CCCATATAAA TCAGCATCCA TGTTGGAATT TAATCGCGGC
1741 CTAGAGCAAG ACGTTTCCCG TTGAATATGG CTCATACTCT TCCTTTTTCA ATATTATTGA
1801 AGCATTATC AGGGTTATTG TCTCATGAGC GGATACATAT TTGAATGTAT TTAGAAAAAT

```

```

1861 AAACAAATAG GCATGCAGCG CTCTTCCGCT TCCTCGCTCA CTGACTCGCT ACGCTCGGTC
1921 GTTCGACTGC GCGGAGCGGT GTCAGCTCAC TCAAAAGCGG TAATACGGTT ATCCACAGAA
1981 TCAGGGGATA AAGCCGAAA GAACATGTGA GCAAAAAGCA AAGCACCGGA AGAAGCCAAC
2041 GCCGCAGGCG TTTTCCATA GGCTCCGCC CCCTGACGAG CATCACAAAA ATCGACGCTC
2101 AAGCCAGAGG TGGCGAAACC CGACAGGACT ATAAAGATAC CAGGCGTTTC CCCCTGGAAG
2161 CTCCCTCGTG CGTCTCCTG TTCCGACCCT GCCGCTTACC GGATACCTGT CCGCCTTTCT
2221 CCCTTCGGGA AGCGTGGCGC TTTCTCATAG CTCACGCTGT TGGTATCTCA GTTCGGTGTG
2281 GGTCGTTCCG TCCAAGCTGG GCTGTGTGCA CGAACCCCGG GTTCAGCCCG ACCGCTGCGC
2341 CTTATCCGGT AACTATCGTC TTGAGTCCAA CCCGGTAAGA CACGACTTAT CGCCACTGGC
2401 AGCAGCCATT GGTAAGTATG TTAGAGGACT TTGTCTTGAA GTTATGCACC TGTTAAGGCT
2461 AAAGTAAAG AACAGATTTT GGTGAGTGCG GTCCTCCAAC CCACTTACCT TGGTTCAAAG
2521 AGTTGGTAGC TCAGCGAAC TTAGAGAAAAC CACCGTTGGT AGCGGTGGTT TTTCTTTATT
2581 TATGAGATGA TGAATCAATC GGTCTATCAA GTCAACGAAC AGCTATTCCG TTAATCTAGA
2641 TTTTCAAGTCA ATTTATCTCT TCAAATGTAG CACCTGAAGT CAGCCCATA CGATATAAGT
2701 TGTAATTCTC ATGTTAGTCA TGCCCGCGC CCACCGGAAG GAGCTGACTG GGTGAAGGC
2761 TCTCAAGGGC ATCGGTCGAG ATCCCGGTGC CTAATGAGTG AGCTAACTTA CATTAATTGC
2821 GTTGCGCTCA CTGCCGCTT TCCAGTCGGG AAACCTGTCG TGCCAGCTGC ATTAATGAAT
2881 CGGCCAACGC GCGGGGAGAG GCGGTTTGC TATTGGGCGC CAGGGTGGTT TTTCTTTTCA
2941 CCAGTGAGAC GGGCAACAGC TGATTGCCCT TCACCGCCTG GCCCTGAGAG AGTTGCAGCA
3001 AGCGGTCCAC GCTGGTTTGC CCCAGCAGGC GAAAATCCTG TTTGATGGTG GTTAACGGCG
3061 GGATATAACA TGAGCTGTCT TCGGTATCGT CGTATCCAC TACCGAGATG TCCGCACCAA
3121 CGCGCAGCCC GGAATCGGTA ATGGCGCGCA TTGCGCCAG CGCCATCTGA TC GTTGCAA
3181 CCAGCATCGC AGTGGGAACG ATGCCCTCAT TCAGCATTG CATGGTTTGT TGA AACCGG
3241 ACATGGCACT CCAGTCGCCT TCCC GTTCCG CTATCGGCTG AATTTGATTG CGAGTGAGAT
3301 ATTTATGCCA GCCAGCCAGA CGCAGACGCG CCGAGACAGA ACTTAATGGG CCCGCTAACA
3361 GCGCGATTTG CTGGTGACCC AATGCGACCA GATGCTCCAC GCCAGTCGC GTACCGTCTT
3421 CATGGGAGAA AATAATACTG TTGATGGGTG TCTGGTCAGA GACATCAAGA AATAACGCCG
3481 GAACATTAGT GCAGGCAGCT TCCACAGCAA TGGCATCCTG GTCATCCAGC GGATAGTTAA
3541 TGATCAGCCC ACTGACGCGT TCGCGGAGAA GATTGTGCAC CGCCGCTTTA CAGGCTTCGA
3601 CGCCGCTTCG TTCTACCATC GACACCACCA CGCTGGCACC CAGTTGATCG GCGCGAGATT
3661 TAATCGCCGC GACAATTTGC GACGGCGCGT GCAGGGCCAG ACTGGAGGTG GCAACGCCAA
3721 TCAGCAACGA CTGTTTGCCC GCCAGTTGTT GTGCCACGCG GTTGGGAATG TAATTCAGCT
3781 CCGCCATCGC CGCTTCCACT TTTTCCCGCG TTTTCGAGA AACGTGGCTG GCCTGGTTCA
3841 CCACGCGGGA AACGTCTGA TAAGAGACAC CGGCATACTC TGCGACATCG TATAACGTTA
3901 CTGGTTTCAC ATTCACCACC CTGAATTGAC TCTTCCCG GCGCTATCAT GCCATACCGC
3961 GAAAGTTTTT GCGCCATTCG ATGGTGTCCG GGATCTCGAC GCTCTCCCTT ATGCGACTCC
4021 TGCATTAGGA AATTAATACG ACTCACTATA

```

KcsAFl protein Sequence (116 amino acids, 18,637.6 Da):

```

1 MMHHHHHPP MLSGLLARLV KLLGRHGSA LHWRAAGAAT VLLVIVLLAG SYLAVLAERG
61 APGAQLITYP RALWWSVETA IVGYLDLYP VTCWGRVAV VVMVAGITSF GLVTAALATW
121 FVGREQERR HFVRHSEKAA EEAYTRTTRA LHERFDRLER MLDDNRR

```

The amino acids comprising the selectivity filter are colored green.

KcsAFl-Y78am protein Sequence (83 amino acids, 9,042.7 Da):

```

1 MMHHHHHPP MLSGLLARLV KLLGRHGSA LHWRAAGAAT VLLVIVLLAG SYLAVLAERG
61 APGAQLITYP RALWWSVETA TTVG

```

5.2 Nanion setup for Electrophysiology

Figure 5.1 gives an impression of the precise dimensions of the Nanion system.

FIGURE 5.1: Nanion setup and dimensions (all measurements in mm). Top: side view of cut through the Faraday shield and electrode holder of the Nanion setup. Middle: side view of cut through NPC10 chip with the aperture shown on the right side. Bottom: Example pictures of usage of NPC10 chips introducing degrees of variability to the setup. Left: loading buffer as internal solution. Middle: Placement of Ag/Cl electrode in inner reservoir and placement of chip. Right: Volume of external solution and placement of ground electrode. (Bottom figures adapted from Nanion.de)

Chapter 6

Appendix B

6.1 NMR spectroscopy of amino acids

The following NMR spectra of the deuterated amino acids were acquired by the manufacturer CDN. The chemical formula of the corresponding amino acid has all carbon atoms noted according to IUPAC nomenclature. Deuterated groups of the structural formulas are shown in purple, while groups in blue do not contain Deuterium. The peaks are assigned according to the numbering found on the structural formula. If applicable, numbers below brackets denote the integrated intensity of the peak included in the bracket.

FIGURE 6.1: The 1D NMR spectrum of L-Leucine-d10 showed high deuteration and purity of the amino acid.

FIGURE 6.2: The 1D NMR spectrum of L-Lysine-2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-d9 HCl showed high deuteration and purity of the amino acid.

FIGURE 6.3: The 1D NMR spectrum of L-Phenyl-d5-alanine-2,3,3-d3 showed high deuteration and purity of the amino acid. The peak at approx. 4.8 ppm could be caused by contamination from atmospheric H₂O.

FIGURE 6.4: The 1D NMR spectrum of L-Tryptophan-2,4,5,6,7-d5 (indole-d5) showed high deuteration and purity of the amino acid.

6.2 Averaged stimulus responses

FIGURE 6.5: Averaged stimulus responses with corresponding standard deviation. The standard deviations of all averaged fish trials is up to twice the averaged signal.

6.3 Registration of LFM Imaging Data

The script below uses simpleITK to align a 3D volumes in space with a reference volume, filters out artifacts of the Microlens grid, Interpolates invalid frames and saves a registered 3D volume. It requires an installed and configured version of Thunder and Spark [261] as well as Python 2.7.

6.3.1 How to run the program:

CAREFUL: A rerun with the same -outdir settings overwrites all previous data in that outdir in case

The simplest running version:

```
spark-submit --master spark://sparkmaster:7077
--jars ~/thunder/lib/thunder_2.10-0.5.0.jar
~/simpleitk_registration/do_reg.py -indir ~/unreg_tiffs/ -outdir ~/reg_tiffs/
```

Start, stop and fixed frame are set by the program, all tiff files in the indir will be FFT-filtered, registered, interpolated and saved in the outdir. Explanations of these and more parameters are below under INPUTS.

Load Parameters from JSON or previous run

add "-JSON_file pathtoJSONFile.JSON" to your command, to automatically read in the parameters defined in this file. A previous run gives you a /para/parameters.JSON file with all parameters used throughout the run which can be edited or simply used to rerun the exact same registration.

Load Parameters by Textfile

This option is good in case you want to store and start your jobs with scriptfiles for later reproducibility. Use a configfile with all parameters you would like to use and give it to the program as follows:

```
spark-submit --master spark://sparkmasterURL:7077 --jars ~/project_software/
thunder-git/python/thunder/lib/thunder_2.10-0.5.0.jar ~/project_software/
simpleitk_registration/do_reg.py @pathtoconfigfile.txt
```

The txtfile should be formatted as follows a new line after each :

```
-mandatory_parameter_name1
mandatory_parameter1
-mandatory_parameter_name2
mandatory_parameter2
-optional_parameter_name1
optional_parameter1
```

Below is a small working example with 2 mandatory and one optional parameter:

```
-indir
/home/indir/
-outdir
/home/outdir/
--stop
3
```

6.3.2 Inputs

Mandatory

Mandatory parameters are given to the script by using a single dash '-mandatoryparameter'

indir Folder containing input tiffs

outdir Folder which will contain all output generated by the program

Optional

Optional parameters are given to the script by using a double dash '-optionalparameter'

Parsing of Parameters

JSON_file: Give filelocation of JSON file to load all specified parameters in the file. All nonspecified parameters will be set by the script. Indir/Outdir still have to be specified. Useful to rerun script by using ./para/parameters.JSON. Additional parameters given to the program will overwrite the predefined parameters in the JSON file and allow small tweaks without having to specify all parameters previously defined.

Dataset definition

start Index of first Frame to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder). If omitted set to first frame. If the first 100 frames need to be registered start at 0 and stop at 99.

stop Index of last Frame to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder). If omitted set to first frame

fixed Index of fixed Frame to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder). If omitted set to first frame.

crop Crop range for moving images: xleft, xright, yup, ydown, zup, zdown. Specifies the CROPPING of the image from left, right, up and down, respectively. (20,20,100,100,2,2) will crop 20 pixels from left and right border and 100 pixels from both top and bottom, and 2 zplanes from top and bottom. In the bottom you'll find a semiautomated script on how to get the right crop parameters from Fiji/Imagej

crop_fix Crop range for fixed image only (in case you want to register two different datasets on each other). See "crop" for specs

crop_mov Crop range for moving images only (in case you want to register two different datasets on each other). See "crop" for specs

Program steps to be executed

Run with 1, skip with 0.

FFT Execute FFT-Grid Filtering (default = 1)

dp_reg Execute SimpleITK-Registration (default = 1)

interp Execute Interpolation (default = 1)

postpro Used in combination with `-excl_thrsld` and `-excl_width` to redefine excluded Frames. Overwrites only /meta/MetricsResult.png, leaves /data/ untouched. Looks up para/parameters.JSON to find fixed frame of the run (plots are normalized to this frames' metrics) and replots with new cutoffs. Run will be aborted afterwards. (default = 0)

excl_thrsltd Exclude Frame after i.e. 2.5 standard Deviations of change in 1st derivative of metrics of registration. (default = 2.5 [standard deviations])

excl_width Excludes range of frames with width = x before and after an excluded frame. (default = 0)

Controlling the outputs of the program

Run with 1, skip with 0.

bool Write out one volume with True/False indicating valid voxels at each position x,y,z (default = 0) Only works with `-interp 1`

ts Write out the timeseries (default = 1)

tiff Write out the tiffs generated from the timeseries (Computationally quite expensive additional step) (default = 0)

MIPtiffs Write out also a MIP of the tiffs in case they are generated (Computationally inexpensive additional step) (default = 1)

optimize SimpleITKs registration algorithm can be tuned via 6 optimizer values by penalizing movement along an degree of freedom. The higher the value the more rigid the movement. Current defaults are set to penalize degrees of freedom leading to strong z-shifts: default = 1, 1, 0.1, 0.00002, 0.00002, 0.00005 for xrot, yrot, zrot, xtrans, ytrans, ztrans.

min_valid_timepoints Exclude Voxel if less than fraction x of the timetrace of the voxel is valid. Use values between 0 and 1 (default = 0.5). Used to exclude voxels usually at the borders which get set to 0 too often due to shifts by the registration.

Defining parameters of FFT grid filter

FFT_grid_param: Pass the following arguments to influence the grid parameters

ox pixel pitch of overtones in x; default = 0

oy pixel pitch of overtones in y; default = 0

wx widthx of big bars at y=0; default = 5

wy widthx of big bars at x=0; default = 4

c distance from center; default = 60

wox width of overtone spots along x; default = 6

woy height of overtone spots along y; default = 6

wox_big height of big overtone spots at y = 0; default = 12

woy_big height of big overtone spots at x = 0; default = 12

wol width of overtone lines; default = 2

use: `-FFT_grid_param 0,0,5,4,60,6,6,12,12,2` for cropped 500x500 px images of the forebrain only use: `-FFT_grid_param 0,0,7,7,35,6,6,12,12,2` for uncropped 968x946 px images

Outputs

The outdir will contain 3 Folders:

outdir\Para:

Contains the parameters.JSON file with all parameters used to run the registration. Can be used to exactly replicate the registration with the same parameters by using `JSON_file` option while starting the program.

outdir\Meta:

Contains the logs and figures generated by the program for troubleshooting:

debuglog.log Gives general information about the progress of the registration (duration, steps, etc). Watch during registration with `tail -f ./debuglog.log`

FFT_Mask_result.png Shows what Mask was generated by `-FFT_grid_param` options and how it was applied to one of the images

FFT_Filter_quality.png Shows how successful the FFT-grid filter was in removing periodic noise from the microlenses. Edge detection algorithms (Sobel, Canny) are applied to a part of one plane of the fixed image

MetricsResult.png : Shows the similarity metrics, the movement along each degree of freedom and their cumulative euclidean distance of the moving image of each timestep compared to the fixed image as standard deviations. The squared 1st derivative of all metrics is shown below with the excluded frames underlaid in yellow. The threshold used to determine excluded frames is shown as a horizontal dotted red line in those plots. The threshold can be set by `-excl_thrslid`

outdir\Data:

Contains all data generated by the run:

fixed_img.npy fixed image just in case you need it as a control. **measurements:** contains measurements of metrics of registration as a bool file for postprocessing and later extraction of excluded frames (saved as binary pickle file by spark)

bool_indicator one volume with True/False indicating valid voxels at each position `x,y,z` (saved as binary pickle file by spark)

timeseries Binary Thunder timeseries object after cropping, filtering, registration and interpolation (if done)

images individual tiffs generated of the data in the timeseries object (`img0000.tif`, `img0001.tif...`)

MIPs Maximun intensity projection of registered images (`imgMIP0000.tif`, `imgMIP0001.tif...`)

6.3.3 Explanation of individual program parts

FFT-Grid Filter

Removes periodic artefacts from Microlenses of the LFM setup by applying a mask of periodic gridlines to the fourier transform of the input image. `-FFT_grid_param` sets how the mask will look like and generates it automatically based on the size of the input image. Very irregular (`x » y`) and very small images usually produce bad results; the grid needs to be adjusted by the `FFT_grid_param`.

Registration

SimpleITKs image registration method uses correlation as a metric of similarity and a conjugate gradient line search to find the minimum. Input images are first being normalized from 0 to 1 as float32. Then it downsamples and smoothes the image by a factor of 2 to perform a rough search and then continues with a fine search on the original image from the endpoint of the rough search. The pictures are rotated and translated with linear interpolation, normalized to their original min and max brightness value. The metrics saved in the /data/measurements folder is an array with each key as the respective time point and the value as:

```
[Metrics_start, Metrics_stop, x_rot_start, y_rot_start, z_rot_start,
  x_pos_start, y_pos_start, z_pos_start, x_rot_stop, y_rot_stop, z_rot_stop,
  x_pos_stop, y_pos_stop, z_pos_stop, eucl_dist_of_xyz_rotat,
  eucl_dist_of_xyz_pos]
```

Interpolation

Removes gaps of a 1D timetrace by Interpolation. The registration sets pixels outside the moving volume which move into the volume to NaN. These voxels are being picked up by the ICA due to their strong variance and need to be removed.

Input:

Data = Intensity of a single voxel over time. Bad Pixels as NaN! `min_valid_timepoints` = Float $0 < x < 1$ indicating the allowed percentage of gaps in Percent (0.90 means, that not more than 10 percent gaps are allowed) Fills up Gaps at the start/end with the first/last value greater 0 and interpolates gaps in the middle of the timetrace by `numpy.interp`

Output:

rdd of tuple of (bool, data). Bool is an indicator if this voxel was rejected (False) or interpolated (True) based on the settings of "`min_valid_timepoints`". data is the intensity of a single voxel over time with interpolated start, end and gaps inbetween. If the pixel failed to fulfill "`min_valid_timepoints`" criterium the trace is set to 0

6.3.4 Code of main program part "do_reg.py"

```
import matplotlib as mpl
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D
import numpy as np
import scipy as sp
from scipy import ndimage
from scipy import io
from scipy.spatial import distance
import scipy.io
import time
import seaborn as sns
import tiff file
import SimpleITK as sitk
import os
import sys
import glob
import argparse
import os.path
from time import gmtime, strftime
import csv
import h5py
```

```

import json
import FFT_Grid_Filter as FFT
import logging
import thunder
from thunder import ThunderContext
from ParameterClass import RegParam
from RegOut import RegOut
import random

def extant_dir(dirname):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - checks that dir exists but does not open.
    """
    if not os.path.isdir(dirname):
        raise argparse.ArgumentError("{0} is not a dir".format(dirname))
    return dirname

def extant_file(filename):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - checks that dir exists but does not open.
    """
    if not os.path.isfile(filename):
        raise argparse.ArgumentError("{0} is not a file".format(filename))
    return filename

def chunk_shape(s):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - Checks that crop parameters are 6 ints.
    """
    try:
        a, b, c, d, e, f = map(int, s.split(','))
        return (a, b, c, d, e, f)
    except:
        raise argparse.ArgumentTypeError("Crop shape must be four comma-separated integers, e.g. 1,2,3,4,5,6")

def fraction_shape(s):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - checks that the value is between 0 and 1.
    """
    try:
        isinstance(s, float)
        0 <= s <= 1
        return s
    except:
        raise argparse.ArgumentTypeError("Fraction shape has to be a float between 1 and 0. i.e. 0.92.")

def optimize_shape(s):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - checks that optimize values are 6 digits.
    """
    try:
        a, b, c, d, e, f = map(float, s.split(','))
        return (a, b, c, d, e, f)
    except:
        raise argparse.ArgumentTypeError("Optimize shape must be six comma-separated integers, e.g. 1,2,3,4,5,6 for xrot,yrot,zrot,xtrans,ytrans,ztrans")

def FFT_Grid_Param_shape(s):
    """
    'Type' for argparse - checks that the FFT_Grid values are 10 digits.
    """
    try:
        a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j = map(float, s.split(','))
        return(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j)
    except:
        raise argparse.ArgumentTypeError('FFT_Grid parameter shape must be 10 comma-separated floats, e.g. [1.,2.,3.,4.,5.,6.,7.,8.,9.,10.]')

```

```

def get_image_dimensions(sitk_image):
    """
    takes any sitk image and returns numpy_like image informations
    """
    z, x, y = (np.shape(sitk.GetArrayFromImage(sitk.Cast(sitk_image, sitk.
        sitkFloat32))))
    ratio = float(x)/y
    return x, y, z, ratio

def get_excl_frames(P, out, outnorm, outgrad, timepoints):
    """
    Defines boolean list of excluded frames. Only those frames are TRUE if none of
    the measurements gradients surpass X-times the std.
    TODO: Implement physical values of drift and rotation and their velocities as
    cutoff!! Maybe throw out SD plotting all together?
    """
    stds = P.excl_thrsld # how many SDs should be allowed before frame is
        declared bad!
    #determine the thresholds over which frame is declared excluded
    thrsld_measures = []
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 2]) * stds) # metrics
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 16]) * stds) # euctrans
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 15]) * stds) # thrsld_eucrot
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 12]) * stds) # thrsld_trans1
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 13]) * stds) # thrsld_trans2
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 14]) * stds) # thrsld_trans3
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 9]) * stds * 1.5) # thrsld_rot1
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 10]) * stds * 1.5) # thrsld_rot2
    thrsld_measures.append(np.std(outgrad[:, 11]) * stds) # thrsld_rot3
    excl_frm_prerange = np.zeros_like(out[:, 0], dtype=bool)
    excl_frm_prerange = (outgrad[:, 2] > thrsld_measures[0]) | (outgrad[:,16] >
        thrsld_measures[1]) | (outgrad[:,15]>thrsld_measures[2]) | (outgrad[:,12]>
        thrsld_measures[3]) | (outgrad[:,13]>thrsld_measures[4]) | (outgrad[:,14]>
        thrsld_measures[5]) | (outgrad[:,9]>thrsld_measures[6]) | (outgrad[:,10]>
        thrsld_measures[7]) | (outgrad[:,11]>thrsld_measures[8])
    excl_frm, width = range_exclude(excl_frm_prerange, timepoints, P.excl_width)
    #save excl_frms
    param = open(P.meta_fldr + "excluded_frames.txt", "w")
    for pair in make_excl_frm_look_nice_for_JSON(excl_frm):
        param.write(str(pair) + ",\n")
    param.close()
    return excl_frm, excl_frm_prerange, thrsld_measures, width

def make_excl_frm_look_nice_for_JSON(excl_frm):
    """
    generate nice looking excluded frames file for JSON input of ICA. Pairs
    beginning and end index of ranges of excluded frames
    takes i.e. [613, 614, 615, 701, 702, 703, 704] and gives back [[613, 615],[701,
    704]] for JSON
    """
    exframes=np.where(excl_frm)[0]
    cnt = 0
    pairs=[]
    for ix in range(np.size(exframes)-1):
        if cnt == 0:
            tmp=[]
            tmp.append(exframes[ix])
            cnt = 1
            elif (exframes[ix]+1 != exframes[ix+1]):
                tmp.append(exframes[ix])
                pairs.append(tmp)
                cnt = 0
            elif ix==np.size(exframes):
                pairs.append(exframes[ix])
            else:
                continue
    return pairs

def range_exclude(excl_frm, timepoints, width = 1):
    """
    Excludes range of frames with width = x before and after an excluded frame
    """

```

```

if width != 0:
tempexfr = np.zeros_like(excl_frm, dtype=bool)
for frame in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
if frame > width:
tempexfr[frame - width:frame + width + 1] = True
if frame <= width:
tempexfr[:frame + width] = True
if frame >= timepoints - width:
tempexfr[frame - width:] = True
excl_frm = tempexfr
kept_frames = np.logical_not(excl_frm)
return excl_frm, width

def check_if_inputfile_is_in_measurementrange(P):
"""
This function was necessary before the switch to lexicographic indexing and is
now obsolete.
checks if the timepoint of the fixed image is within the range of timepoints
which were registered.
"""
fp_input = os.path.split(P.fixed)[0]
if fp_input == P.fixed and P.fxd_ndx in out[:,0]:
fxd_ndx = np.where(out[:,0]==P.fxd_ndx)[0][0]
fxd_ndx.flatten()
else:
fxd_ndx=0
return fxd_ndx

def get_gradients(out, fxd_ndx):
"""
Normalizes the timetraces of the measurements and returns 1st derivative^2
"""
outnorm = np.zeros_like(out) #normalized results
outgrad = np.zeros_like(out) #normalized derivatives of results
outgrad_notnorm = np.zeros_like(out)
for ix in range(1, np.shape(out)[1]): #iterates over parameterlists stored in
out
outnorm[:,ix] = norm_by_std(out[:,ix]-(out[fxd_ndx,ix]))
outgrad[:,ix] = norm_by_std(np.gradient(out[:,ix]-out[fxd_ndx,ix])**2)
outgrad_notnorm[:,ix] = np.gradient(out[:,ix]-out[fxd_ndx,ix])**2
return outnorm, outgrad, outgrad_notnorm

def norm_by_std(Arr):
"""
Normalizes an array... could also use lambda expression for that actually...
"""
Arr=(Arr-np.mean(Arr))/np.std(Arr)
return Arr

def Get_Exframes_Plot_Metrics_result(P, measures_array, outputnamestr):
"""
Calculates all the excluded frames, planes, normalized and 1st derivative
measurement traces and plots everything.
"""
out = np.ndarray(shape=(0,17))
measures_array = [np.insert(x[1], 0, x[0]) for x in measures_array] #add the
key to the measurement
out = [np.vstack((out, measurement)) for measurement in measures_array]
out = np.reshape(out, (np.shape(measures_array)[0],17))
timepoints = len(out[:,0])
fxd_ndx = P.fxd_ndx #check_if_inputfile_is_in_measurementrange(P) #the check is
obsolete but only if from same dataset.
outnorm, outgrad, outgrad_notnorm = get_gradients(out, P.fxd_ndx)
excl_frm, excl_frm_prerange, thrsld_measures, width = get_excl_frames(P, out,
outnorm, outgrad, timepoints)
#rem_perc, rem_perc_ex = get_remain_pxl(P, out, timepoints, excl_frm)
#excl_pln, excl_pln_ex, incl_pln_rng, incl_pln_rng_ex = get_excl_planes(P,
rem_perc, rem_perc_ex)
#Plot the result
plot_metrics_and_save_png(P, out, outnorm, outgrad, timepoints, excl_frm,
thrsld_measures, 'SD', outputnamestr)

```

```

plot_metrics_and_save_png(P, out, out, outgrad_notnorm, timepoints, excl_frm,
    thrsl_d_measures, 'Metric', outputnamestr)
if outputnamestr == '_pre':
    P_save = P
    P.excl_thrsl_d = 0.1
    excl_frm, _, _, _ = get_excl_frames(P, out, outnorm, outgrad, timepoints)
    list_of_stable_indices = np.arange(0, timepoints)
    list_of_stable_indices = np.delete(list_of_stable_indices, np.where(excl_frm))
    while np.float(np.size(list_of_stable_indices))/timepoints < 0.2:
        P.excl_thrsl_d = P.excl_thrsl_d + 0.1
        excl_frm, _, _, _ = get_excl_frames(P, out, outnorm, outgrad, timepoints)
        list_of_stable_indices = np.arange(0, timepoints)
        list_of_stable_indices = np.delete(list_of_stable_indices, np.where(excl_frm))
    P = P_save
    return list_of_stable_indices

def plot_metrics_and_save_png(P, out, normalized, gradient, timepoints,
    excl_frm, thrsl_d_measures, figuretype, outputnamestr):
    """
    Takes processed metrics from finished registration to plot their components
    over time. Y axis can be adjusted to display standard deviations or Metric
    units (mdeg, micrometer) and saves the resulting plot in the meta directory
    """
    if figuretype == 'SD':
        figurename = 'MetricsResult_SD_units' + outputnamestr + '.png'
        y_labels = ['SD of Metric Value', 'SD of Euclid distance', 'SD of Euclid
            Rotation', 'SD of Shift', 'SD of Rotation', 'SD of derivative of Metric
            Value', 'SD of derivative of Euclid distance', 'SD of derivative of Euclid
            Rotation', 'SD of derivative of Shift', 'SD of derivative of Rotation']
    elif figuretype == 'Metric':
        figurename = 'MetricsResult_metric_units' + outputnamestr + '.png'
        y_labels = ['Metric Value', 'Euclid distance [um]', 'Euclid Rotation [deg]', '
            Shift [um]', 'Rotation [deg]', 'Derivative of Metric Value', 'Derivative of
            Euclid distance [velocity]', 'Derivative of Euclid Rotation [angular
            velocity]', 'Derivative of Shift [velocity]', 'Derivative of Rotation [
            angular velocity]']

    outnorm = normalized
    outgrad = gradient

    fig, (ax0, ax1, ax2, ax3, ax4, ax5, ax6, ax7, ax8, ax9) = plt.subplots(nrows
        =10, figsize=(20,50))
    fig.text(0.5, 0.95, '', horizontalalignment='center')

    xlim1 = min(out[:,0]) # starttimeframe of plot
    xlim2 = max(out[:,0]) # endtimeframe of plot
    ax0.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:,2], color = 'k')
    ax0.set_title('Metric Value relative to Image #' + str(P.fxd_ndx))
    ax0.set_xlabel('Frame')
    ax0.set_ylabel(y_labels[0])
    ax0.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

    ax1.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:, 16], color = (0.482353, 0.407843,
        0.933333))
    ax1.set_title('Euclidean distance in 3D relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.
        fxd_ndx, 0])))
    ax1.set_xlabel('Frame')
    ax1.set_ylabel(y_labels[1])
    ax1.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

    ax2.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:, 15], color = (0.780392, 0.0823529,
        0.521569))
    ax2.set_title('Euclid Rotation in 3D relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.
        fxd_ndx, 0])))
    ax2.set_xlabel('Frame')
    ax2.set_ylabel(y_labels[2])
    ax2.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

    ax3.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:, 12], label = "X-Shift", color = 'r')
    ax3.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:, 13], label = "Y-Shift", color = 'g')
    ax3.plot(np.arange(timepoints), outnorm[:, 14], label = "Z-Shift", color = 'b')
    ax3.set_title('X-Y-Z-shift relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.fxd_ndx,0])))

```

```

ax3.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax3.set_ylabel(y_labels[3])
ax3.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(0.9, 1), loc=2, borderaxespad=0.)
ax3.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

ax4.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outnorm[:, 9], label = "X-Rot", color = 'r')
ax4.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outnorm[:, 10], label = "Y-Rot", color = 'g')
ax4.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outnorm[:, 11], label = "Z-Rot", color = 'b')
ax4.set_title('X-Y-Z-Rotation relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.fxd_ndx,0])))
ax4.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax4.set_ylabel(y_labels[4])
ax4.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(0.9, 1), loc=2, borderaxespad=0.)
ax4.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

for ix in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
ax5.axvline(ix,linewidth=5, color = (1, 1, 0.4))
ax5.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 2], color = 'k')
ax5.axhline(thrsld_measures[0], linewidth=2, color = 'r', linestyle = 'dashed')
ax5.set_title('1st derivative of Metric Value relative to Image #' + str(int(out
[P.fxd_ndx,0])))
ax5.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax5.set_ylabel(y_labels[5])
ax5.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

for ix in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
ax6.axvline(ix,linewidth=5, color = (1, 1, 0.4))
ax6.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:,16], color = (0.482353, 0.407843,
0.933333))
ax6.axhline(thrsld_measures[1], linewidth=2, color = 'r', linestyle = 'dashed')
ax6.set_title('1st derivative of Euclidean distance in 3D relative to Image #' +
str(int(out[P.fxd_ndx,0])))
ax6.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax6.set_ylabel(y_labels[6])
ax6.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

for ix in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
ax7.axvline(ix,linewidth=5, color = (1, 1, 0.4))
ax7.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:,15], color = (0.780392, 0.0823529,
0.521569))
ax7.axhline(thrsld_measures[2], linewidth=2, color = 'r', linestyle = 'dashed')
ax7.set_title('Euclid Rotation in 3D relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.
fxd_ndx,0])))
ax7.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax7.set_ylabel(y_labels[7])
ax7.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

for ix in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
ax8.axvline(ix,linewidth=5, color = (1, 1, 0.4))
ax8.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 12], label = "X-Shift", color = 'r')
ax8.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 13], label = "Y-Shift", color = 'g')
ax8.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 14], label = "Z-Shift", color = 'b')
ax8.axhline(thrsld_measures[3], linewidth=2, color = 'r', linestyle = 'dashed')
ax8.set_title('X-Y-Z-shift relative to Image #' + str(int(out[P.fxd_ndx,0])))
ax8.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax8.set_ylabel(y_labels[8])
ax8.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(0.9, 1), loc=2, borderaxespad=0.)
ax8.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

for ix in np.where(excl_frm)[0]:
ax9.axvline(ix,linewidth=5, color = (1, 1, 0.4))
ax9.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 9], label = "X-Rot", color = 'r')
ax9.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 10], label = "Y-Rot", color = 'g')
ax9.plot(np.arange(timepoints),outgrad[:, 11], label = "Z-Rot", color = 'b')
ax9.axhline(thrsld_measures[6], linewidth=2, color = 'r', linestyle = 'dashed')
ax9.set_title('1st derivative of X-Y-Z-Rotation relative to Image #' + str(int(
out[P.fxd_ndx,0])) + '. Thresholds augmented by factor of 1.5 to not
produce too many false negatives.')
ax9.set_xlabel('Frame')
ax9.set_ylabel(y_labels[9])
ax9.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(0.9, 1), loc=2, borderaxespad=0.)
ax9.set_xlim(xlim1, xlim2)

```

```

plt.tight_layout()
fig.savefig(P.meta_fldr + figurename)
return
#return excl_frm, excl_frm_prerange, rem_perc, rem_perc_ex, thrshld,width,
    excl_pln, excl_pln_ex, incl_pln_rng, incl_pln_rng_ex

def interpolate_voxel_timetrace(P, data, min_valid_timepoints=0.75):
    """
    Removes gaps of a 1D timetrace by Interpolation.
    Input:
    Data = Intensity of a single voxel over time. Bad Pixles as NaN!
    min_valid_timepoints = Float 0 < x < 1 indicating the allowed percentage of
        gaps in Percent (0.90 means not more than 10 percent gaps)
    Fills up Gaps at the start/end with the first/last value > 0 and interpolates
    gaps in the middle of the timetrace by interpolation (numpy)
    """

    datainput = data
    if P.interp == 0:
        indicator = True
        return (indicator, np.float32(data))
    flag = ~np.isnan(data) #make boolean mask from the data for validtimepoints ==
        True
    if np.size(np.where(flag)) == 0: #if all pixles of voxel over time are invalid:
        exclude voxel and return input (just so there's something)
        indicator = False
        return (indicator, np.float32(np.zeros_like(datainput)))

    ratiovalid = np.float(np.sum(flag))/np.size(flag)
    if ratiovalid <= min_valid_timepoints:
        indicator = False #still interpolate and stuff but set the flag to invalid.
        return (indicator, np.float32(np.zeros_like(datainput)))
    else:
        indicator = True
        if ~flag[0]: #prepare start and ends first
            cnt = np.min(np.where(flag))
            data[:cnt] = data[cnt] #fill start
            flag[:cnt] = True
        if ~flag[-1]:
            cnt = np.max(np.where(flag))
            data[cnt:] = data[cnt] #fill end
            flag[cnt:] = True
        not_nan = np.logical_not(np.isnan(data))
        indices = np.arange(len(data))
        data = np.interp(indices, indices[not_nan], data[not_nan])
        return (indicator, np.float32(data))

def cut_rim(P, imgs, rim = 20):
    """
    Cuts away border of default 20 pixles of the x/y-plane.
    Rippling artifacts of the FFT-filter at the edges of the picture stay
    at the same position although the fish is moving and thus interfere with
    registration.
    """
    if rim != 0:
        imgs = imgs.crop((rim,rim,0),(P.x-rim,P.y-rim,P.z))
        P.x = P.x-rim*2
        P.y = P.y-rim*2
        return imgs

def time_to_log(start ,log):
    """
    Adds entry of current time and runtime since start to logfile
    """
    end = time.time()
    log.info(time.strftime("%H:%M:%S") + " Time passed since start: %5.1f seconds
        " % (end - start))

def make_figure_of_interpolation(ts):
    """

```

```

plots a figure illustrating the success of the interpolation and saves it to
the meta directory
"""
fig, (ax0, ax1) = plt.subplots(nrows=2, figsize=(20,20))
examples = ts.subset(nsamples=100, thresh=0.01)
examples = ts.values().filter(lambda x: np.std(x) > 0.01).cache()
ax0.plot(examples.T[0:50,:]);
(indicator, interpolated_traces) = [interpolate_voxeltime(x,
    min_valid_timepoints=0.5) for x in examples]
ax1.plot(interpolated_traces.T[0:50,:]);
fig.savefig(P.meta_fldr + 'Interpolation_result.png')
print">>>>>picturesaved"
return

def save_as_tiff(P, k, v):
    """
    Saves an image file and MIP if necessary to the outfolder.
    """
    image = np.rollaxis(v, 2, 0) # (x,y,z to z,x,y, necessary for proper opening
        in fiji and matlab)
    tiffname = P.im_fldr + 'img%04d.tif' % k, image)
    if P.MIPTiffs == 1:
        MIPimage = np.max(image, 0) # MIP along z which is now at axis = 0
        tiffname = P.MIP_fldr + 'imgMIP%04d.tif' % k, MIPimage)
    return (k, v)

def convert_tstuple_to_16_bit_ts(log, timeseries_as_tuple_bool_ts):
    """
    Converts timeseries as tuple (bool, ts) to uint16, sets minimum value to 0 and
    maximum to 65535 and returns only the timeseries object
    """
    totalmin = np.min(timeseries_as_tuple_bool_ts.applyValues(lambda bool_and_ts:
        bool_and_ts[1].min()))
    totalmax = np.max(timeseries_as_tuple_bool_ts.applyValues(lambda bool_and_ts:
        bool_and_ts[1].max()))
    log.info("Setting global Zero, the total minimum Found is:")
    log.info(totalmin)
    log.info("the total Maximum Found is:")
    log.info(totalmax)
    roundfactor = 65535. / totalmax
    time_to_log(start ,log)
    only_ts_as_uint16 = timeseries_as_tuple_bool_ts.applyValues(lambda bool_and_ts:
        np.round(bool_and_ts[1] - totalmin) * roundfactor).astype(np.uint16,
        casting='unsafe')
    return only_ts_as_uint16

def apply_mask(imgs, mask):
    """
    Checks if a mask is defined and starts the masking process
    """
    if mask == None:
        return imgs
    else:
        imgs = imgs.applyValues(lambda image: mask_image(image, mask))
    return imgs
def mask_image(image_3D, bool_mask_3D):
    """
    applies a boolean mask to the images given to this function
    """
    if np.shape(bool_mask_3D)[2] != np.shape(image_3D)[2]:
        bool_mask_3D = bool_mask_3D[:, :, :np.shape(image_3D)[2]]
        image_3D[bool_mask_3D] = 0
    return image_3D

def mask_timeseries(key, value, mask_3D_bool):
    """
    Applies a boolean mask to the whole timeseries
    """
    if not mask_3D_bool[key]:
        value = np.zeros_like(value)
    return (key, value)

```

```

def parse_parameters():
    """
    Reads in parameters given to the program during startup
    """
    parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(fromfile_prefix_chars='@', description='
    Register a dir of images. Either write input commands directly to command
    line or give: "do_reg.py @pathtoconfigfile.txt" for reading in arguments.
    Format in File for example: -indir\\mnt/indir/\\-outdir\\n/temp/outdir
    /\\--fixed\\3\\n--crop\\n 10,20,30,40,3,4')
    parser.add_argument('--JSON', default = None, help='Give path to JSON parameter
    file to be loaded')
    parser.add_argument('-indir', type=extant_dir, help='Directory containing the
    TIFFs (with each TIFF containing one z-stack). Tiffs in folder will be
    lexicographically sorted for future indexing')
    parser.add_argument('-outdir', type=None, help='Output path. Contains
    subfolders meta/data/para with results of registration. Para: parameters
    parsed to and generated by the program. Metrics: The metrics of the
    registration and FFT Filter Results. Data: folder containing the Results.')
    parser.add_argument('--fixed', type=int, default=None, help='Index of fixed
    Frame to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder)
    . If omitted set to first frame')
    parser.add_argument('--start', type=int, default=None, help='Index of first
    Frame to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder.
    i.e. to register 100 Files start at 0 and stop at 99!')
    parser.add_argument('--stop', type=int, default=None, help='Index of last Frame
    to register (according to lexicographic sorting of input tiff folder).
    Uses last frame in folder if not set.')
    parser.add_argument('--crop', type=chunk_shape, default='0,0,0,0,0,0', help='
    Crop range for moving images: xleft, xright, yup, ydown, zup, zdown.
    Specifies the CROPPING of the image from left, right, up and down,
    respectively. (20,20,100,100,2,2) will crop 20 pixels from left and right
    border and 100 pixels from both top and bottom, and 2 zplanes from top and
    bottom.')
    parser.add_argument('--crop_fix', type=chunk_shape, default=None, help='Crop
    range for fixed image only (in case you want to register two different
    datasets on each other). See "crop" for specs')
    parser.add_argument('--crop_mov', type=chunk_shape, default=None, help='Crop
    range for moving image only (in case you want to register two different
    datasets on each other). See "crop" for specs')
    parser.add_argument('--FFT', type=int, default='1', help='Do the FFT Filtering
    if set to 1, skip if set to 0')
    parser.add_argument('--do_reg', default = 1, help='Execute Registration if 1.
    Skip with 0')
    parser.add_argument('--excluded_frames', type=int, default = 0, help='Set to 1
    to do redefine excluded_frames only. Will search for the metrics file in
    outpath and do the graphs based on new --excl_thrsld.')
    parser.add_argument('--interp', default = 1, help='Execute Interpolation if 1.
    Skip with 0')
    parser.add_argument('--bool', default = 0, help='Save Boolarray if 1. Skip with
    0')
    parser.add_argument('--ts', default = 1, help='Save Timeseries if 1. Skip with
    0')
    parser.add_argument('--tiff', default = 1, help='Save registered tiffs if 1.
    Skip with 0. This step is computationally quite expensive.')
    parser.add_argument('--MIPtiffs', default = 1, help='If tiffs are saved: Save
    also MIP of registered tiffs if 1. Skip with 0. Inexpensive and occupy not
    much space')
    parser.add_argument('--optimize', type=optimize_shape, default='
    1.,1.,0.1,0.00002,0.00002,0.00005', help='6 optimizer values for xrot,yrot,
    zrot,xtrans,ytrans,ztrans')
    parser.add_argument('--reg_method', type=str, default='rigid', help='rigid
    chooses VersorRigid3DTransform, bspline the slower bspline registration.')
    parser.add_argument('--shrink_factors', default='6,2,1', help='Binning at each
    step of a multistep registration')
    parser.add_argument('--sigmas_per_level', default='6,2,1', help='Smoothing at
    each step of a multistep registration in um (with 20x objective each pixel
    = 0.681 um')

```

```

parser.add_argument('--FFT_grid_param', type=FFT_Grid_Param_shape, default='
0,0,5,4,60,6,6,12,12,2', help='Pass the following arguments to influence the
grid parameters: [ox(pixel pitch of overtones in x), oy(pixel pitch of
overtones in y), wx (widthx of big bars at y=0), wy (widthx of big bars at
x=0), c (dist from center), wox (width of overtone spots along x), woy (
height of overtone spots along y), wox_big(height of big overtone spots at
y =0), woy_big(height of big overtone spots at x =0), wol (width of
overtone lines)]')
parser.add_argument('--excl_thrslld', type=float, default=2.5, help='Exclude
Frame after i.e. 2.5 standard Deviations of change in 1st derivative of i.e
. translation')
parser.add_argument('--excl_width', type=int, default=0, help='Excludes range
of frames with width = x before and after an excluded frame.')
parser.add_argument('--min_valid_timepoints', type=fraction_shape, default=0.5,
help='Exclude Plane if i.e. 0.92 of the frame is valid. Use values between
0 and 1.')
parser.add_argument('--mask', type=str, default=None, help='mask for getting
eyes off the stuff.')
parser.add_argument('--middle_out', type=int, default=1, help='Removes planes
23 to 27 from 51 planes. Does not work with stacks that do not have 51
planes')
parser.add_argument('--prereg', type=int, default=0, help='Generate an averaged
fixed frame from the 20 most stable images of the first 100 images of the
registration')
parser.add_argument('--verbose', type=int, default=0, help='Print lots of Logs
during registration')
args = parser.parse_args()
return args

def check_postprocessing(P, log):
"""
Checks if only postprocessing is desired, reads in metrics, plots which frames
should be excluded and ends the program. by refining excl_thrslld parameter
the amount of excluded frames can be tuned.
"""
if P.excluded_frames == 1:
log.info("Will only replace the MetricsResult.png based on the exclusion
threshold of %f Standard deviations" %P.excl_thrslld)
#load measures pickle
_, sc = P.initiate_pyspark_thunder()
measures = sc.pickleFile(P.meas_fldr).collect()
excl_thrslld_save = P.excl_thrslld
P.load_JSON(P.para_fldr + 'parameters.JSON')
P.excl_thrslld = excl_thrslld_save
Get_Exframes_Plot_Metrics_result(P, measures)
log.info("Exiting the Program, New Plot has been generated, old one overwritten
.")
sys.exit()
else:
return

def run_reg(P, index, moving_in, fixed_in, mask_bool, reg_method):
"""
Image Registration Method registers a volume on a given reference image.
Gives back a key value pair of the index as a key
and a tuple of the registered image and measurements of the registration as a
value.
(index, (reg_img_as_float32array, measurements_to_save))

Parameters
-----
P : Parameters object
Object containing all parameters of the dataset and registration created with
the "ParameterClass.py"

index : int
Index of current frame to be registered

moving_in : np_ndarray
3D-Array (of usually uInt16) to be registered. Output as float32 array.

fixed_in : np_ndarray

```

3D-Array (of usually uInt16) used as reference image

Output

```

-----
index : int
Index of current frame to be registered

reg : np.ndarray
3D-Array of registered frame as float32, scaled to min and max of the input
array.

measurements_to_save : array of floats
Measurements taken during registration arranged in following way # dict would
    have been nicer I guess...
[Metrics_start, Metrics_stop,
x_rot_start, y_rot_start, z_rot_start, x_pos_start, y_pos_start, z_pos_start,
x_rot_stop, y_rot_stop, z_rot_stop, x_pos_stop, y_pos_stop, z_pos_stop,
eucl_dist_of_xyz_rotat, eucl_dist_of_xyz_pos]
"""
if P.verbose:
import logging
logger = logging.getLogger('do_reg_%05d' % index)
logger.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
ch = logging.StreamHandler()
ch.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
fh = logging.FileHandler(P.meta_fldr + 'debuglog_doreg_%05d.log' % index)
fh.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
formatter = logging.Formatter('%(asctime)s [%(levelname)s] %(name)s: %(funcName)
    s: %(lineno)d): %(message)s')
ch.setFormatter(formatter)
fh.setFormatter(formatter)
logger.addHandler(fh)
logger.addHandler(ch)
logger.info('Starting do_reg()')

if P.middle_out == 1:

nomiddle = ( 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16,
17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40,
    41, 42, 43, 44,
45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50)
#Instead of throwing the palnes out, one could make a mask of the middle planes
    to keep the information!!!
#maybe better to keep more information
#mid_bool = np.zeros_like(fixed_in)
#mid_bool[:, :, nomiddle] = 1
#mid_bool = mid_bool > 0 #tadaa ready.
moving_in = moving_in[:, :, nomiddle]
fixed_in = fixed_in[:, :, nomiddle]
if mask_bool != None:
mask_bool = mask_bool[:, :, nomiddle]

iwfilter = sitk.RescaleIntensityImageFilter() #initialize Filters
iwfilter.SetOutputMinimum(0.)
iwfilter.SetOutputMaximum(1.)

fixed = sitk.GetImageFromArray(fixed_in) #Initiating fixed and moving image
fixed = sitk.Cast(fixed, sitk.sitkFloat32)
fixed.SetSpacing(P.sitk_spacing)
fixed = iwfilter.Execute(fixed)

moving = sitk.GetImageFromArray(moving_in)
moving = sitk.Cast(moving, sitk.sitkFloat32)
moving.SetSpacing(P.sitk_spacing)
moving = iwfilter.Execute(moving)

R = sitk.ImageRegistrationMethod()
R.SetGlobalDefaultNumberOfThreads(2)

```

```

if reg_method == 'rigid':
if not P.prereg:
if index == P.fxd_ndx: #give back input image if image == fixed image (avoids
    errors during registration)
measurements_to_save = np.array([-1,-1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
    0])
return (index, (moving_in, measurements_to_save, 0, 0))
R.SetMetricAsCorrelation()
R.SetOptimizerAsConjugateGradientLineSearch(learningRate=1e-3,
numberOfIterations=400,
convergenceMinimumValue=1e-6,
estimateLearningRate=True)
R.SetMetricSamplingPercentage(0.01) #smallest sampling percentage found which
    converges to good Metrics == 0.005
tx = sitk.CenteredVersorTransformInitializer(fixed, moving, sitk.
    VersorRigid3DTransform()) #Setting the transformation parameters
R.SetShrinkFactorsPerLevel([5, 1])
R.SetSmoothingSigmasPerLevel([5, 1])

elif reg_method == 'coarse':
if index == P.fxd_ndx: #give back input image if image == fixed image (avoids
    errors during registration)
measurements_to_save = np.array([-1,-1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
    0])
return (index, (moving_in, measurements_to_save, 0, 0))
R.SetMetricAsCorrelation()
R.SetOptimizerAsConjugateGradientLineSearch(learningRate=1e-3,
numberOfIterations=13,
convergenceMinimumValue=1e-4,
estimateLearningRate=True)
R.SetMetricSamplingPercentage(0.001)
tx = sitk.CenteredVersorTransformInitializer(fixed, moving, sitk.
    VersorRigid3DTransform()) #Setting the transformation parameters
R.SetShrinkFactorsPerLevel([5])
R.SetSmoothingSigmasPerLevel([5])

elif reg_method == 'bspline':
transformDomainMeshSize = [20,20,3]#[np.int(np.round(20 * P.x / 500.)), np.int(
    np.round(20 * P.y / 500.)), np.int(np.round(3 * P.z / 51.))] #[20,20,3]
    worked good for my 500x500x51 pictures
tx = sitk.BSplineTransformInitializer(fixed, transformDomainMeshSize)
R.SetOptimizerAsConjugateGradientLineSearch(learningRate=1e-3,
numberOfIterations=13,
convergenceMinimumValue=1e-4,
estimateLearningRate=True)
R.SetMetricSamplingPercentage(0.005)
R.SetShrinkFactorsPerLevel([1])#[[10, 5, 2, 1]] # binning each step: 2x first
    step. None last step # Multisteps
R.SetSmoothingSigmasPerLevel([1])#[[2, 2, 1, 0]] # in um units

elif reg_method == 'tobias':
R.SetMetricAsMattesMutualInformation()
R.SetGlobalDefaultNumberOfThreads(1)
R.SetNumberOfThreads(1)
R.SetOptimizerAsConjugateGradientLineSearch(learningRate=1e-5,
numberOfIterations=400,
convergenceMinimumValue=1e-6,
estimateLearningRate=False)
R.SetMetricSamplingPercentage(0.01) #smallest sampling percentage found which
    converges to good Metrics
tx = sitk.CenteredVersorTransformInitializer(fixed, moving, sitk.
    VersorRigid3DTransform()) #Setting the transformation parameters
R.SetShrinkFactorsPerLevel([5, 1])
R.SetSmoothingSigmasPerLevel([5, 0])
P.optimize = [1, 1, 1, 1e-5, 1e-5, 2e-5]

elif reg_method == 'skip':
measurements_to_save = np.array([-1,-1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
    0])
return (index, (moving_in, measurements_to_save, 0, 0))

```

```

R.SetInitialTransform(tx)
if mask_bool != None:
    sitk_mask_bool = sitk.GetImageFromArray(mask_bool)
R.SetMetricFixedMask(sitk_mask_bool)
R.SetMetricMovingMask(sitk_mask_bool)
R.SetOptimizerScales(P.optimize)
R.SetInterpolator(sitk.sitkLinear)

R.SmoothingSigmasAreSpecifiedInPhysicalUnitsOff()
R.SetMetricSamplingStrategy(R.RANDOM)

cmd_val = [] #Initiate measurement containers for Registration method
cmd_pos = []

R.AddCommand( sitk.sitkIterationEvent, lambda: cmd_val.append(R.GetMetricValue
()))
R.AddCommand( sitk.sitkIterationEvent, lambda: cmd_pos.append(R.
    GetOptimizerPosition()))
if P.reg_method == 'coarse':
if index == P.fxd_ndx: #give back input image if image == fixed image (avoids
    errors during registration)
measurements_to_save = np.array([-1,-1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
    0])
return (index, (moving_in, measurements_to_save, 0, 0))

if P.verbose:
P.tmp_frame_ix = index
def command_iteration(method, P):
import logging
import time
logger = logging.getLogger('do_reg_command_iter')
try:
if method.GetOptimizerIteration() == 0:
logger.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
ch = logging.StreamHandler()
ch.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
fh = logging.FileHandler(P.meta_fldr + 'debuglog_doreg_command_iteration_%05d.
    log' % P.tmp_frame_ix)
fh.setLevel(logging.DEBUG)
formatter = logging.Formatter('%(asctime)s [%](levelname)s]%(name)s:%(funcName)
    s:%(lineno)d): %(message)s')
ch.setFormatter(formatter)
fh.setFormatter(formatter)
logger.addHandler(fh)
logger.addHandler(ch)
logger.info('Starting first command_iteration()')
logger.info("Estimated Scales: %s" % str(method.GetOptimizerScales()))
logger.info("{0:3} = {1:7.7f} : {2}".format(method.GetOptimizerIteration(),
    method.GetMetricValue(), method.GetOptimizerPosition()))
except:
import sys
logger.error(sys.exc_info()[0])
R.AddCommand( sitk.sitkIterationEvent, lambda: command_iteration(R, P) )

try:
outTx = R.Execute(fixed, moving)
resampler = sitk.ResampleImageFilter() #Interpolate by Resampling
resampler.SetReferenceImage(fixed);
resampler.SetInterpolator(sitk.sitkLinear)
resampler.SetDefaultPixelValue(np.nan) ##### in order to pick up these frames
    by the interpolation I should set them to pretty negativ or NaN
resampler.SetTransform(outTx)
outReg = resampler.Execute(moving)

mov_min = np.float64(np.min(moving_in)) #Normalize back to input range
mov_max = np.float64(np.max(moving_in))
iwfilter.SetOutputMinimum(mov_min)
iwfilter.SetOutputMaximum(mov_max)
outReg = iwfilter.Execute(outReg)
reg = sitk.GetArrayFromImage(outReg).astype(np.float32)

```

```

measurements_to_save = np.array([cmd_val[0], cmd_val[-1], cmd_pos[0][0],
    cmd_pos[0][1], cmd_pos[0][2], cmd_pos[0][3], cmd_pos[0][4], cmd_pos[0][5],
    cmd_pos[-1][0], cmd_pos[-1][1], cmd_pos[-1][2], cmd_pos[-1][3], cmd_pos
    [-1][4], cmd_pos[-1][5], distance.euclidean(cmd_pos[0][:2], cmd_pos
    [-1][:2]), distance.euclidean(cmd_pos[0][3:], cmd_pos[-1][3:])])
if P.verbose:
logger.info('Success. do_reg() returning')
return (index, (reg, measurements_to_save, cmd_val, cmd_pos))

except:
#import sys
#logger.error(sys.exc_info()[0])
# try again with CC metric
# R.SetMetricAsCorrelation()
# try:
#     R.Execute()
# except Exception as e:
#     logger.exception(e)
measurements_to_save = np.array([0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0,
    0])
if P.verbose:
logger.info('Failure. do_reg() returning with dummy return value')
return (index, (moving_in, measurements_to_save, 0, 0))

def preprocessing():
"""
Checks if you want parsing or JSON inputfile, reads arguments and gives back
single parameter / measurement-object. Initiates, loads, crops and filters
dataset and gives back preprocessed image object, ready for registration
"""
#initiate the parameter object
global start
start = time.time()
P = RegParam()
P.load_parser(parse_parameters())
P.initiate_pathnames()
log = P.initiate_logging()
check_postprocessing(P, log)
time_to_log(start, log)
imgs, mask_crop = P.load_images(log)
time_to_log(start, log)
fixed_prefft = P.initiate_fixed_image(imgs, log)
sns.set(style="ticks")
mask_gauss = FFT.make_FFTmask(P, fixed_prefft, log) # make FFT Mask and filter
all files.

if mask_gauss.any():
time_to_log(start, log)
sns.set(style="darkgrid")
imgs = cut_rim(P, imgs.applyValues(lambda imagestack_prefft: FFT.
    FFT_Grid_Filter(P, imagestack_prefft, mask_gauss, log, more_info = 0)), rim
    =0)
log.info("Finished filtering all images")
time_to_log(start, log)

log.info('Fixed frame indices: %s' % str(P.fxd_ndx))
log.info(np.shape(mask_crop[0]))
#preregistration
if P.prereg:
if not P.list_of_stable_indices:
if P.fxd_ndx > 100:
fixed = np.array(imgs.first()[1])
else:
fixed = imgs[P.fxd_ndx]
log.info("Quick rigid registration")
imgs_temp = imgs.filterOnKeys(lambda x: x < 150).apply(lambda (index,
    image_to_reg): run_reg(P, index, image_to_reg, fixed, mask_crop[0], 'coarse
    ')).cache()
measures = imgs_temp.applyValues(lambda tuple_reg_and_measure:
    tuple_reg_and_measure[1]).astype(np.float32, casting='unsafe').collect() #
measures is a List not an Array at this point

```

```

list_of_stable_indices = Get_Exframes_Plot_Metrics_result(P, measures, '_pre')
if len(list_of_stable_indices) > 30:
list_of_stable_indices = list_of_stable_indices[:30]
log.info("Averaging %3.1f percent of the most stable frames to make the fixed
image. The indices are:" %(100*(np.size(list_of_stable_indices)/np.float32(
P.timepoints))))
log.info(list_of_stable_indices)
fixed = imgs.filterOnKeys(lambda x: x in list_of_stable_indices).mean()
log.info("New fixed image shape:")
log.info(np.shape(fixed))
P.list_of_stable_indices = list(list_of_stable_indices)
else:
if P.fxd_ndx == 0:
fixed = np.array(imgs.first()[1])
else:
fixed = imgs[P.fxd_ndx]
log.info("Fixed and Mask sizes:")
log.info(np.shape(fixed))
np.save(P.data_fldr + "fixed_img.npy", fixed)

P.save()
log.info("Saved input variables to /para/parameters.JSON")
return P, imgs, log, fixed, mask_crop

def processing(P, imgs, log, fixed, mask_crop):
"""
If desired, the preprocessed images are registered, measures saved and analysis
figures plotted. The output is a tuple of (index_of_image, (image,
measurements))
"""
time_to_log(start, log)
if P.do_reg == 1:
time_to_log(start, log)
log.info("Registration start")
imgs = imgs.apply(lambda (index, img): run_reg(P, index, img, fixed, mask_crop
[0], P.reg_method)).cache()
measures = imgs.applyValues(lambda tuple_reg_and_measure: tuple_reg_and_measure
[1]).astype(np.float32, casting='unsafe').collect() # measures is a List
not an Array at this point
imgs.applyValues(lambda tuple_reg_and_measure: tuple_reg_and_measure[1]).astype
(np.float32, casting='unsafe').rdd.saveAsPickleFile(P.data_fldr + "
measurements/")
log.info("Plotting Metrics")
Get_Exframes_Plot_Metrics_result(P, measures, '_' + P.reg_method)
log.info("Registration finish")
else:
imgs.apply(lambda (index, image_not_to_reg): (index, (image_not_to_reg, 0))) #
to provide same tuplestructure for future steps / does not work yet I think
....
time_to_log(start, log)
return imgs

def postprocessing(P, imgs, log, mask_crop):
"""
The image object is interpolated, converted to a timeseries and images written
out.
"""
time_to_log(start, log)
log.info("Interpolation Start")
ts = imgs.applyValues(lambda tuple_reg_and_measure: tuple_reg_and_measure[0]).
toTimeSeries().applyValues(lambda int_over_time: interpolate_voxeltimeTrace
(P, int_over_time, P.min_valid_timepoints)).cache()
log.info("Interpolation Finish")
time_to_log(start, log)
if P.bool == 1:
log.info("Saving Boolarray")
ts.applyValues(lambda bool_and_ts: bool_and_ts[0]).rdd.saveAsPickleFile(P.
bool_fldr)
time_to_log(start, log)

onlyts = convert_tstuple_to_16_bit_ts(log, ts).cache()

```

```

if P.ts == 1:
log.info("Saving Timeseries")
time_to_log(start ,log)
onlyts.saveAsBinarySeries(P.ts_fldr)#.rdd.saveAsPickleFile(P.ts_fldr)
time_to_log(start ,log)
if P.tiff == 1:
log.info("Saving Tiffs. Total Number:")
imgs = onlyts.toImages().cache()
if P.MIPtiffs == 1:
log.info("Saving MIP Tiffs")
P.MIP_fldr = P.im_fldr + 'MIPs/'
if not os.path.isdir(P.MIP_fldr):
os.makedirs(P.MIP_fldr)
imgs = apply_mask(imgs, mask_crop[1]) #here the boolmask is used
log.info(imgs.apply(lambda ndx_img: save_as_tiff(P, ndx_img[0], ndx_img[1])).
count())
time_to_log(start ,log)
log.info( "
-----Finish-----
" )
end = np.empty([2, 2])
np.save(P.outdir + "Success.npy", end)
return

if __name__ == '__main__':
## Read Parameters ##
P, imgs, log, fixed, mask_crop = preprocessing()
## Processing ##
imgs = processing(P, imgs, log, fixed, mask_crop)
## Postprocessing ##
postprocessing(P, imgs, log, mask_crop)

```

6.3.5 Code of "ParameterClass.py" to initialize the program, paramters and image objects

```

class RegParam(object):
global os, np, sitk, json, glob, logging, itemgetter
import os
import numpy as np
import SimpleITK as sitk
import glob
import json
import logging
from operator import itemgetter

def __init__(self):
self.fixed = None
self.indir = None
self.outdir = None
self.crop = None
self.start = None
self.stop = None
self.optimize = [1., 1. ,0.1, 0.00002, 0.00002, 0.00005]
self.FFT = 1
self.FFT_grid_param = [0, 0, 5, 4, 60, 6, 6, 12, 12, 2]
self.excl_thrslid = 2.5
self.excluded_frames = 0
self.data_name = 'data'
self.meta_name = 'meta'
self.para_name = 'para'
self.JSON_file = None
self.sitk_spacing = [150/11./20., 150/11./20., 4.] #sets it to um for this
magnification
self.do_reg = 1
self.interp = 1
self.min_valid_timepoints = 0.5
self.tiff = 1
self.excl_width = 0

```

```

self.shrink_factors = [2, 1]
self.sigmas_per_level = [2, 1]

def initiate_logging(self):
logging.basicConfig(filename=self.meta_fldr + 'debuglog.log', level=logging.
    INFO, format='%(asctime)s %(message)s')
logging.info('
    -----Start-----
    ')
logging.info('Initiated Log of reconstruction of:' + self.im_fldr)
return logging

def load_JSON(self, filelocation = None):
"""
Loads a JSON file at the file location defined under self.JSON_location and
updates the parameters if present.
"""
if filelocation == None and self.JSON_file != None:
filelocation = self.JSON_file
elif self.JSON_file and filelocation == None:
print "No file found"
return

with open(filelocation) as data_file:
paradict = json.load(data_file)
self.__dict__.update(paradict)

def load_parser(self, args):
"""
Loads a dictionary from parser and updates the parameters
"""
if self.JSON_file != None:
self.load_JSON()
self.__dict__.update(vars(args))

def save(self):
"""
Saves all parameters as a JSON dict to the specified file location
"""
from collections import OrderedDict
dicttosave = OrderedDict(self.__dict__)

# maybe we have to filter out the functions, because they can't be written to
JSON...
with open(self.para_fldr + 'parameters.JSON', 'w') as outfile:
json.dump(dicttosave, outfile, indent=4, separators=(',', ': '))

def initiate_pathnames(self):
"""
creates all pathnames and outdirectories used in the course of the program if
the do not exist
"""
dirlist_to_check = [self.indir, self.outdir, self.data_name, self.meta_name,
self.para_name]
self.indir, self.outdir, self.data_name, self.meta_name, self.para_name = [self
._check_bslash(x) for x in dirlist_to_check]
self.data_fldr, self.meta_fldr, self.para_fldr = [self.outdir + x for x in [
self.data_name, self.meta_name, self.para_name]]
[os.makedirs(x) for x in [self.outdir, self.data_fldr, self.meta_fldr, self.
para_fldr] if not os.path.isdir(x)]
self.im_fldr = self.data_fldr + 'images/'
if not os.path.isdir(self.im_fldr):
os.makedirs(self.im_fldr)

#Spark.rdd.saveAsPickleFile does not like already existing folders. Delete
existing if present:
self.meas_fldr = self.data_fldr + 'measurements/'
self.ts_fldr = self.data_fldr + 'timeseries/'
self.bool_fldr = self.data_fldr + 'bool_indicator/'
self.stdev_fldr = self.data_fldr + 'stdev/'
if self.excluded_frames != 1:
import shutil

```



```

pre_crop_x, pre_crop_y, pre_crop_z = imgs.dims
log.info('Image Dimensions: x(%i) y(%i) z(%i)' %(pre_crop_x, pre_crop_y,
pre_crop_z))
if self.crop:
log.info(">>>>>>>>>> cropping pictures")
self.crop_thunder = (self.crop[2], self.crop[0], self.crop[4]), (pre_crop_x-
self.crop[3], pre_crop_y-self.crop[1], pre_crop_z-self.crop[5])
imgs = imgs.crop(self.crop_thunder[0], self.crop_thunder[1]) # self.
crop_thunder = ((xmin,ymin,zmin),(xmax,ymax,zmax)) tuple for cropping in
thunder
log.info(">>>>>>>>>> cropped pictures")
self.x, self.y, self.z = imgs.dims
log.info('Image Dimensions after cropping: x(%i) y(%i) z(%i)' %(self.x, self.y,
self.z))
self.ratio = float(self.x)/self.y
return imgs

def initiate_fixed_image(self, imgs, log):
"""
Reads fixed image which has to be within range of start<= fixed_index <=stop
Input: imgs = thunder_img_obj
Output: Initialized fixed volume of frame as np array
"""
self.fxd_ndx = self.fixed #self.fixed is only for better user readability.
if self.fxd_ndx == None:
log.info("No fixed image provided, using first image as fixed images")
self.fxd_ndx = 0

if self.fxd_ndx > self.stop - self.start:
log.info("Fixed Image has the index %i but is not within the range of images
selected. Setting fixed image to start image" % (int(self.fxd_ndx)))
self.fxd_ndx = 0
log.info("Fixed Image has the index %i." % (self.fxd_ndx))
fixed_array = imgs.get(self.fxd_ndx)
return fixed_array

#Collection of outdated functions
def _make_todo_filelist(self):
"""
Creates "self.infiles" list of files which will be Registered.
Takes already finished files into account if requested by self.commence=1 and
sorts them.
"""
infiles = self._sort_infiles(self.indir)
if os.listdir(self.data_fldr):
already_done_files = self._get_already_done_files(self.data_fldr)
if self.commence == 1:
infiles_temp = []
for framename in infiles:
if os.path.split(framename)[1] in already_done_files:
print ("Commencing Previous run. Skipped "+ os.path.split(framename)[1])
else:
infiles_temp.append(framename)

infiles = infiles_temp
if self.commence == 1 and len(infiles) == 0 :
print "No files to commence, aborting run. You should use --postpro 1 to plot
the results"
exit()
infile_indices = np.empty(shape = np.shape(infiles), dtype = int)
cnt = 0
for filename in infiles:
fnb, _ = os.path.splitext(filename) # Timepoint_X1
infile_indices[cnt] = int(fnb.split('X')[-1]) # 1
cnt +=1
infile_indices
if self.start == None:
self.start = get_ndx_from_impact(infiles[0])[0]
if self.stop == None:
self.stop = self._get_ndx_from_impact(infiles[-1])[0]
return infiles, infile_indices

```

```

def _get_already_done_files(self, pathtodirectory):
    """
    searches in a directory for files and returns filenames
    """
    already_done_files_full_path = self._sort_infiles(pathtodirectory) #sorts the
        files as 1, 10, 11, 12, ..., 2, 20
    already_done_files = []
    for full_filepath in already_done_files_full_path:
        already_done_files.append(os.path.split(full_filepath)[1])
    return already_done_files

def _sort_infiles(self, path_to_image_dir):
    """
    Sorts and returns filenames in inputpath from 1, 10, 11, 12, ..., 2, 20
    terribly inefficient and complicated from smallest to largest.
    Result: 1, 2, 3, 4...10, 11, 12
    """
    infiles = sorted(glob.glob(path_to_image_dir + '*.tif')) #sorts the files as 1,
        10, 11, 12, ..., 2, 20
    tmp = np.empty(shape=(np.size(infiles), 2))
    cnt = 0
    for filename in infiles:
        ix, _ = self._get_ndx_from_impath(filename)
        tmp[cnt, 0] = int(ix)
        tmp[cnt, 1] = int(cnt)
        cnt += 1
    tmp_sorted = self._sort_for_first_index(tmp)
    infiles_sorted = np.empty_like(infiles) #FUCK!
    cnt = 0
    for index in tmp_sorted[:,1]:
        infiles_sorted[cnt] = infiles[int(index)]
        cnt += 1
    return infiles_sorted # Pew that was though...

def _check_bslash(self, folderpath):
    """
    Private method that adds last backslash to secure proper concatenation of path
    and filename
    home/Filefolder --> home/Filefolder/
    """
    if folderpath[-1] != '/':
        folderpath = (folderpath + '/')
    return folderpath

def _get_ndx_from_impath_old(self, filename):
    """
    takes a full path filename and returns its index and filename
    /home/dir/Timepoint_X1.tif --> [1, Timepoint_X1.tif]
    """
    _, fn = os.path.split(filename) #fn = Timepoint_X1.tif
    fnb, _ = os.path.splitext(fn) # fnb = Timepoint_X1
    ix = int(fnb.split('X')[-1]) # ix = 1
    return ix, fn

def _get_ndx_from_impath(self, filename):
    """
    For Files padded with 5 leading zeros
    takes a full path filename and returns its index and filename
    /home/dir/Timepoint_01001.tif --> 1001, Timepoint_01001.tif
    """
    _, fn = os.path.split(filename) #fn = Timepoint_01001.tif
    fnb, _ = os.path.splitext(fn) #fnb = Timepoint_01001
    ix = int(fnb[-5:].rstrip("0")) #ix = 1001
    return ix, fn

def _sort_for_first_index(self, matrix_to_sort):
    """
    Sorts a matrix depending on its first index. Used to sort for timepoints.
    [[3,2,5],[1,5,2],[2,8,1]] --> [[1,5,2],[2,8,1],[3,2,5]]
    """
    out_sorted = np.empty_like(matrix_to_sort)

```

```
matrix_to_sort = sorted(matrix_to_sort, key = itemgetter(0)) #this messes up
                    the matrix, dont know why.
for ix in range(len(matrix_to_sort)):
out_sorted[ix] = matrix_to_sort[:,ix] #reshaping of the matrix to get back to
                    original shape. certainly better solution possible
return out_sorted
```